

**Examining the Influences and outcomes of TNE
Market Orientation in UK Universities: The
Managers' Perspectives**

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DEDICATION

This doctoral research is primarily dedicated to my mother Rachida Bachra, my wife Kahina Belabraham, then to my twin girls, Israa Ouardia Benazzouz and Judy Zouhra Benazzouz, as well as my daughter, Salwa Benazzouz, and my son, Azzam Benazzouz, whose presence provides constant support and motivation for me.

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AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I, Mehdi Benazzouz, declare that the ideas, research work, analyses and conclusions reported in my DBA thesis "*Examining the Influences and Outcomes of TNE Market Orientation in UK Universities: The Managers' Perspectives*" are entirely my effort, except where otherwise acknowledged. Also, I certify that this thesis contains no material that has been submitted previously, in whole or in part, for the award of any other academic degree or diploma. Except where otherwise indicated, this thesis is my own work.

ABSTRACT

This thesis investigates ‘Transnational Education (TNE) market orientation’ and its significance in the higher education marketing of the United Kingdom. The aim is to develop a model that conceptualises and interprets engagement in TNE market orientation, elucidating the factors contributing to the successful of a TNE business from a managerial perspective. This builds on the extant literature, where theories of export marketing have predominantly concentrated on conceptualising the export market orientation of goods. However, in terms of services, few studies examined the export market orientation concept with relation to TNE, despite its importance in guiding direct TNE marketing. Also, not much methodical research has explored the impacts of the components of higher education export market orientation from the perspective of managers, nor verified the correlation between the dimensions of TNE market orientation, its antecedents, and consequences.

A mixed method research approach, of two main phases, was adopted. The first phase focused on conducting key information focus groups and interviews with TNE marketing managers of UK HE establishments. The analysis of key themes with the literature review contributed to develop research hypotheses and shape the study model. The second phase involved testing the model with a survey that includes a sample of 336 TNE marketing managers from 142 UK HE establishments. Analysis of a Moment Structures (AMOS) structural equation modelling was used to analyse responses of the survey. The structural model reflected a good fit to the data, and good convergent, discriminant and nomological validity, then stable reliability.

The overall findings revealed that there is a strong link with the antecedents (TNE coordination and developed country higher education image perception) and TNE market orientation, but unexpectedly, the university international ranking position does not impact TNE market orientation. Further discovery showed strong link to the university international ranking position and developed country higher education image perception. Also, TNE market orientation had greater impact on higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. However, unexpectedly, the association between higher education international reputation and TNE business performance was not significant.

The contribution of this study is to advance the understanding of TNE market orientation in UK HE establishments to improve exporting of higher education business and maintain dominance in this market, a topic where there is limited previous research.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. INTRODUCTION

The theme of this research is transnational education (TNE) market orientation in UK universities. It is processed by promoting and examining an experimental model connecting TNE market orientation, universities export-specific variables, higher education international reputation, and TNE business performance.

This chapter begins with a discussion of the study background including scholars' perceptions on TNE phenomenon, its relation with market orientation, development, and importance. Problems and gaps from the literature were determined concerning UK universities' practice and aim to develop TNE over the last forty years. Then, four objectives and four questions were set to investigate further the existing studies, regarding how UK universities manage and perceive market orientation in their TNE services to international students. For the research methodology, I will provide a brief description on steps that will be followed in the interpretivism and positivism paradigms, where quantitative approach is predominant supported by qualitative data (exploratory interviews). Then, I will highlight the significant research contributions at the theoretical level, and how it would assist managers, academics, and policy-makers. Finally, I will provide a brief structure with the aim of each chapter.

1.2. STUDY BACKGROUND

TNE is an effective instrument that attempts to reach overseas students with no need to leave their home countries (Healey, 2018). Educational scholars have been attracted by the importance of higher education, and particularly the role of TNE, which aims to create a competitive advantage for universities (Keay et al., 2014; Kleibert, 2023; Knight, 2016; Olssen, 2016). A well-managed TNE market orientation will lead to a sophisticated university's competitive advantage and reputation, ensuring the university's business performance, and attracting an increased number of international students and educational partners.

The focus about TNE is a recent phenomenon; the mid-1980s reflects the starting point of TNE when western universities began to launch a new phase of higher education (Rowley and Skipper, 2021). TNE communicates a significant new global tradable business, that serves the local universities, host universities, overseas students, and economies (Hou et al., 2014; Spring, 2009). With the increasing number of overseas students seeking higher education in Western countries and the expansion of business philosophies within the higher education sector, special attention is paid to TNE as a substitute option for students desiring education and degrees from overseas universities. This highlights the importance of developing the TNE sector.

The marketisation of the higher education sector has been presented as a “paradigm shift” and an “epidemic” (Bobe and Kober, 2015; İpek and Bicakcriogulu-Peynirci, 2020; Molesworth et al., 2011) within the context of the delivery of university education in the Western world (Rowley and Skipper, 2021). The increase of global marketisation related to higher education creates pressure on higher education institutions to set an international marketing strategy to benefit from international students (Wright and Shore, 2017). However, in the past there was a domestic focus towards education marketing, compared to the last two decades, where this sector has been witnessing a massive growth of higher education institutions in international marketing. Unfortunately, despite all efforts toward marketisation, the outcomes from education sectors still display a lack of improvement (Nixon et al., 2018).

‘Market orientation’ can be defined as the foundation of corporate marketing strategy which helps an organisation’s management to understand both present and potential customer needs. This is achieved by providing superior customer value through the gathering and sharing of market information related to customers and competitors (Jaworski and Kohli, 1993; 2017). The TNE market orientation embraces characteristics that allow a university to outperform and distinguish itself from other universities engaged in TNE (Caruana and Montgomery, 2015; Chung, 2012; Dwyer, 2022). A TNE market orientation increases a university’s ability to identify matters and opportunities related with the development of TNE programmes (Asaad et al., 2015, Cadogan et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2014). Assessing TNE market orientation (how marketing managers perceive TNE operation in universities) is significant, as TNE represents a crucial aspect of growth (Asaad et al., 2015) used to increase universities’ market share and forge educational partnerships (Healey, 2015; Olssen, 2016; Silva et al., 2023).

TNE is growing in the educational sector, and students in developing countries are increasingly embracing this phenomenon (Healey, 2018). Entrepreneurs in higher education communicate with marketing managers to enhance the university's significance as a source of providing high-quality education (Hou et al., 2014; Olssen, 2016; Dwyer, 2022; Wright and Shore, 2017) through the elements of TNE Market Orientation. The prime elements that influence a TNE Market Orientation are: 1) TNE coordination (Wilkins and Huisman, 2021), 2) university international ranking position (Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016), and 3) developed country higher education image perception (Asaad et al., 2013). So, why is TNE market orientation imperative?

TNE market orientation is among the crucial strategies for a university to deliver its curriculum and programmes on the largest scale globally (Vangelis et al., 2018). Developing and extending the scale of TNE delivery is a management process that reveals the university's efficiency to operate in the international market (Caruana and Montgomery, 2015). It is very costly and challenging for the university to deliver its curriculum and degrees (Yencken et al., 2021) and university managers are responsible for ensuring that TNE students are treated as they have expected before enrolment, to secure satisfaction and credible connection to all TNE stakeholders (Firmansyah et al., 2023; Hailat et al., 2019; Olssen, 2016; Yencken et al., 2021).

TNE market orientation is the framework for managers related to TNE in universities (Knight and John, 2017). The notion of TNE market orientation is linked to the concept of TNE business performance. Researchers, including Asaad et al. (2013) and Caruana and Montgomery (2015), assert that export market orientation is an instrument for better global higher education dissemination, influencing the TNE stakeholders' decisions and behaviour (Caruana and Montgomery, 2015). Hence, TNE market orientation is classified as extension elements of export market orientation that have emerged with the increase of the export philosophy in higher education (Asaad et al., 2013).

1.3. RESEARCH PROBLEM STATEMENT

The creation of a TNE market orientation is a difficult task for universities, but it is a crucial means of directing the future of a university in the TNE market, and it encompasses the performance of the university's TNE practices (Healey, 2013; Olssen, 2016; Yencken et al., 2021). Universities practicing TNE have interest to maximise international students' information with the aim to develop a credible and effective position in the TNE market (Asaad

et al., 2015; Grecic, 2022), thereby adding more value to the reputation of university (Foroudi et al., 2019; Tienari and Aula, 2011). TNE market orientation is used as a measuring tool for a university practicing TNE (Chung, 2012; Yencken et al., 2021) to increase awareness regarding issues related to TNE and gives support for its development, hence acts as a channel of communication between local university and TNE stakeholders (Healey, 2018; Kayabasi et al., 2016).

A TNE market orientation influences a university's internal and external activities and has tangible impacts (Asaad et al., 2015) on its achievements in TNE globally (Yencken et al., 2021; Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016). International students react favourably to foreign higher education because they expect a high quality of education and anticipate receiving a globally recognised degree that enhances career prospects (Casidy, 2014), compared to their local curriculum and degrees (Yencken et al., 2021). The interest that international students hold about the TNE programme is related to the feedback from TNE graduates and the needs of job market (Healey, 2018). "TNE has become more popular, and international students expect the learning experience to enhance their career" (Healey, 2018, p.246). According to scholars such as Asaad et al. (2013), TNE market orientation is a significant tactic for delivering education outside the main campus borders.

TNE market orientation is at the root of TNE performance (Dwyer, 2022) to assure the effectiveness of TNE operation for all stakeholders (Firmansyah et al., 2023; Hailat et al., 2019; Jules, 2018; Olssen, 2016). TNE market orientation is the main element of an effective TNE delivery (Caruana and Montgomery, 2015; Dwyer, 2022), adapted to enhance a university's presence in the TNE market and its importance as a path to develop partnerships with educational institutions worldwide and increase intakes (Guruz, 2011; Olssen, 2016). Universities must ensure the delivery of education similar to that in their main campuses through their TNE programmes and understand their market through the effective use of market orientation (Chankseliani, 2017). For these reasons, universities put great effort into developing international partnerships; create an effective TNE chain worldwide; and delivering knowledge that can shape the universities' and students' future through TNE market orientation (Wilkins and Huisman, 2021).

A few marketing scholars investigating in the field of higher education exportation (e.g., Asaad et al., 2013; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; Dwyer, 2022; Grecic, 2022) have investigated how export elements of higher education, such as the developed country higher education image perception, TNE coordination and international ranking position, impact the number of international students enrolled in TNE programmes (TNE business performance). Meanwhile, three studies (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2018; Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016) on market orientation in higher education have investigated and attempted to comprehend the export of higher education. Previous studies have extensively noted that educational marketing literature lacks a systematic study on the effect of market orientation on the future of TNE in the UK (Jules, 2018; Kleibert, 2023).

Managing TNE market orientation efficiently enables universities to reap more interest towards their TNE programmes and making action more quicker regarding issues that might affect a university's development in the TNE market (Brown, 2011; Kleibert, 2023; Vangelis et al., 2018), therefore acquiring an added value. Thus, TNE market orientation can be the ideal tool for securing the effectiveness in orientating TNE from a managerial perspective. Seeking the truth starts when there is a lack of certainty, a perspective common among philosophers and researchers, and one that frequently applies to the development of activities in higher education sectors (Kleibert, 2023). However, what influence does market orientation, in turn, have on TNE perceptions in universities? Huge effort is required to answer this type of vital question, emphasising a gap in TNE activities and in understanding how universities explicate TNE market orientation as a development tool for their TNE activities (Vangelis et al., 2018).

TNE market orientation is likely to advance, in the long term, the international reputation of a university and its business performance. Consequently, by setting an effective orientation, there will be a high chance that the range of internal activities related to TNE market orientation will affect the management and perception of its export of higher education towards international students (Bennell, 2022). There is still much to be studied regarding the relationship between TNE market orientation, its elements, antecedents, and consequences (Healey, 2018; Olssen, 2016).

1.4. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS

The aim of this research is to develop a model to conceptualise and interpret engagement in TNE market orientation, elucidating the reason behind a successful TNE business. Four specific objectives are set to investigate TNE market orientation and address the main goals:

1. To critically analyse existing literature to understand an absence of empirical research into the specificities of TNE market orientation.
2. To investigate, using mixed methods, the perceptions of managers engaged in management to clarify the relation of TNE market orientation's dimensions with its antecedents and consequences.
3. To develop a model that combines TNE practice and market orientation for effective TNE expansion and development.
4. To produce research relevant to TNE managers, policy-makers and academics.

In particular, this study, with regards to the above objectives, plans to respond to the following research questions:

1. How do universities in the UK perceive and practice TNE activities?
2. What are the elements that shape TNE market orientation in the UK?
3. What are the key factors that influence TNE market orientation in the UK?
4. What are the consequences/benefits of TNE market orientation according to UK universities?

The accomplishment of these research objectives increases the chances of this investigation adding value to the present knowledge on TNE market orientation and equipping practical insights to managers and academics related to TNE.

1.5. RESEARCH DESIGN AND ANALYTICAL METHOD

This research employs both interpretivism and positivism paradigms, utilising a predominantly quantitative method, with the support of some qualitative input based on exploratory interviews (Churchill, 1979; Creswell, 2013; Foroudi et al., 2021a) and enhanced with focus groups. As this field of research is relatively underdeveloped (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2018; Olssen, 2016), UK universities will be targeted for assessment (Arenas et al., 2015; Bleiklie et al., 2017; Healey, 2013). The purpose of the qualitative research is to generate valuable information and increase understanding of the phenomena; review and refine all hypotheses and the conceptual framework; filter the questionnaire measures; and enhance findings in terms of validation and the content of the conclusion (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Churchill, 1979).

The first phase adapts an interpretivism paradigm centralised on a qualitative method, which is deemed appropriate for this research according to TNE market orientation unclarity and lack of understanding regarding its effectiveness and relationship (Asaad et al., 2015; Saunders et al., 2007). Thus, adapting Churchill (1979) is valuable as it integrates a qualitative paradigm that enables effective generation of information at the beginning of this study through survey. Regarding the qualitative data analysis, NVivo software was used to code and extract information generated from interviews and focus groups. Mixing qualitative methods with quantitative methods aims to test a field where not much attention has previously been paid to data, which lacks understanding or is unknown (Creswell, 2013; Foroudi et al., 2021a). Therefore, it is preferable to employ quantitative methods in the next phase of this study.

In the second phase of this study, a positivist paradigm will be used, focusing on a quantitative method to examine the current hypotheses with their causal relationship and validation of scale. Every scale will purify through both quantitative and qualitative assessment. Concerning the satisfaction of the measurements' content validity, an academic group will contribute to appraise the items resulting from interviews and focus groups. Their recruitment will help to remove unnecessary measures and guarantee that the items will be representative of the scale's domain (De Vaus, 2002; DeVellis, 2003).

To gauge the perceptions of TNE managers regarding the influence of TNE market orientation on TNE business performance, a self-administrated questionnaire was distributed in UK universities. The questionnaire will feature a seven-point Likert scale ranging between (1) which represents ‘strongly disagree’ to (7) which represents ‘strongly agree’. The use of this scale aims to provide participants with an ideal distribution of options that would satisfy their responses (Creswell, 2014). This study tests the perceptions of international office managers in UK universities, and a total of 142 UK universities will be invited to participate and share their experience with TNE market orientation. The survey will be applied to bodies related to TNE in UK universities, and a total of 336 questionnaires were collected for this study.

Conducting the descriptive statistics for the entire sample, the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was utilised. Churchill (1979) recommended ‘Exploratory Factor Analysis’ (EFA) and coefficient alpha as essential techniques; hence, they will be used in the primary phase of this study regarding scale validity to decrease the total number of observed research indicators (Field, 2013). The quality of the measurement model will be determined through ‘Structural Equation Model’ (SEM) by using Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) 25.0 and also by testing the causal relationship among constructs. Achieving a solid technique for modelling relies on SEM (Teo, 2011), as this technique is considered a fundamental approach to test a marketing theory (Foroudi et al., 2021a). Therefore, the two-stage procedure by Anderson and Gerbing (1982) was utilised. First, the ‘Confirmatory Factor Analysis’ (CFA) was used to permit strict assessment to construct uni-dimensionality. Then, based on the measurement models, the examination of every subset of items will inwardly make consistent and validate the constructs (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982). The second step will involve testing the structural model fit via indices of goodness-of-fit and estimating paths among constructs to evaluate the hypotheses of study.

1.6. STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE

The current study aims to supply additional strands of research to the previous attempts to gain a better understanding of the TNE market orientation concept and contributing to export market orientation theory. Thereby, the study’s results assist academics, managers and public policy-makers interested in TNE (full details will be available in Chapter 8.2 Implications of research findings).

A fundamental contribution of this study occurs through its response to gaps found in the literature, i.e. How do universities in the UK perceive and practice TNE activities? The following is the summary of literature gaps:

- 1) There is a scarcity of research on how decision makers in TNE select partners or countries for expansion (Raymundo-Delmonte, 2023). This highlights the necessity to revisit this topic and gather additional insights on the criteria for success among TNE providers (Grecic, 2022; Olssen, 2016).
- 2) Numerous universities lack the advanced business capabilities essential for constructing comprehensive TNE business cases and overseeing international movements of individuals and finances across borders (British Council, 2018; Healey 2016).
- 3) The systematic studies in marketing literature do not cover the effect of effective TNE market orientation on universities' TNE expansion and development (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2018; He et al., 2018; Kleibert, 2023).
- 4) A common challenge in TNE involves complying with the rules and regulations of host countries, such as program approval and taxation, due to the lack of accurate data on TNE (Healey, 2020).
- 5) The area of TNE market orientation lacks theory building studies and explanatory models (Asaad et al., 2015; Grecic, 2022; Harris, 2020).
- 6) Despite the UK's past leadership in international student recruitment, it has lost ground to its competitors. This gap underscores the need for UK universities to reassess their strategies and address factors contributing to this decline, particularly in increasing revenue through TNE programs (Universities UK, 2018).
- 7) The marketing literature lacks empirical research into the specificities of TNE market orientation (Asaad et al., 2015, Healey, 2018; Melewar et al., 2018).

The researcher attempts to illustrate those mechanisms that connect TNE market orientation, higher education international reputation, and TNE business performance in the UK. Thus, the current study extends findings of previous research to contribute to existing knowledge. For instance, some researchers (Asaad et al., 2013; Boyd et al., 2010; Zebal and Goodwin, 2012) mention that export market orientation is related to TNE business performance; however, this relationship has rarely been examined. Although a few recent studies (Casidy, 2014; Healey, 2018; Khuwaja et al., 2017) have examined export market orientation, but they were not related

to UK TNE or its business performance. The results offered by higher education marketing researchers help to fill gaps in existing theory in this area of research (Yu et al., 2018; Healey, 2018; Kleibert, 2023).

This study makes theoretical contributions to existing knowledge by providing alternative insights into TNE market orientation. This empirical study is considered as the first of its kind to cover the effect of TNE market orientation on UK managers' evaluation of their activities (Grecic, 2022; Healey, 2018; He et al., 2018; Kleibert, 2023). Also, this study is qualified to support and clarify research in the field of TNE market orientation. It will add value to the export market orientation literature in higher education by improving and proving a scale which determines the framework of influence applied by TNE market orientation.

This research also enhances the understanding of the study constructs, in addition to the dimensionality and operationalisation of the study concepts based on a managerial perspective. Regarding the theoretical contribution, this thesis sets a threefold academic contribution. Starting with theory extension (through empirical testing, conceptualisation verification, and constructs' measurement), then theory testing, and theory generalisation.

This study has the capability to contribute to marketing theory. Export market orientation has attracted the attention of several prominent marketing researchers (Asaad et al., 2015; Olssen, 2016; Kleibert, 2023). However, this contribution is to bring a comprehensive view of TNE development plus marketing through researching whether the combination of TNE market orientation impacts TNE business performance through higher education international reputation in the UK's universities based on managers' perspective.

The results of this study, in relation to the managerial implications, suggesting that the focus of TNE managers should increase regarding practicing and managing TNE market orientation. Managers related to TNE need to unify their performance to target issues of TNE from similar points of view (Knight, 2016; Wilkins and Balakrishna, 2013). Therefore, the study provides a collaborative atmosphere between these managers to generate a mutual understanding of the concept of business performance in the TNE market.

This research, additionally, determines the critical factors necessary to fulfil an effective TNE market orientation. Therefore, findings generated are of extreme importance to public policy-makers for better export of higher education. A direct correlation, according to findings, between TNE market orientation and both the higher education international reputation and TNE business performance has been confirmed.

Future research should emphasise the efficiency of the suggested tactic in this study. First, because the current study is limited to UK universities, it does not guarantee similar results to TNE management in other countries. Second, there is limitation in terms of the number of tested variables related to TNE market orientation, and by investigating other variables, valuable significance will be added to the literature of this knowledge. Finally, the current study is limited in terms of the investigated perspective, limited to managers, which might vary from the perspective of other TNE stakeholders.

1.7. THE THESIS STRUCTURE

This thesis comprises eight chapters, together with references and appendices, structured as follows:

Chapter 1. Introduction

It frames the aims and importance of studying TNE market orientation from the perspective of UK universities. The discussion covers the study background, problems, and gaps related to this phenomenon in the marketing literature. It then provides an overview of the adopted method and methodology, then a presentation of its contribution to managers, academic, and public policy-makers.

Chapter 2. Literature review

It represents the background that supports the business philosophy in the context of higher education, including developments in the marketing of universities and logic towards TNE export marketing. It then identifies gaps found in higher education export marketing literature. The rest of the chapter discusses the relevant literature pertaining to transnational education (TNE), market orientation (MO), and TNE market orientation (TNEMO), which is covered by export market orientation (EMO) based on several research opinions, and it includes research on antecedents and consequences.

Chapter 3. Conceptual framework and research hypotheses

It delivers the conceptual model revealing a range of factors which are considered as antecedents to TNEMO and clarifies the consequences of TNE market orientation. There are eight constructs that form this study's conceptual model. Hence, this chapter will characterise the suggested marketing managerial-level conceptual framework, in addition to several hypotheses that have a conceptual relationship between each of them from literature.

Chapter 4. Methodology and research design

It discusses the mixed research methodology, which is dominated by quantitative method, and data analysis techniques (confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modelling). It highlights and explains the data analysis techniques and statistical packages (NVIVO for qualitative data analysis and SPSS and AMOS for quantitative data analysis) which underlie the assumptions.

Chapter 5. The qualitative findings

It identifies the findings of the qualitative research: eight interviews and four focus groups with managers related to TNE (which will support the quantitative findings covered in Chapter 6). The purpose of qualitative research in this study was to address its aim by developing a good understanding of TNEMO and its impacts on higher education international reputation and TNE business performance, and to address the research questions.

Chapter 6. Data analysis

It expresses all results of the quantitative study, including results that reflect the development of scale and purification through three phases, each covering several steps. The first phase includes techniques applied for data preparation, accuracy, and examination. Six items were removed from six constructs after reliability tests and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) using 'SPSS'. The second phase relies on confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and the third phase covers the evaluation and development of this study's structural equation model (SEM) using 'AMOS 25' on 336 cases. Fourteen of seventeen hypotheses were accepted.

Chapter 7. Discussion

It examines and debates findings from the previous two chapters (qualitative and quantitative studies), and discusses all steps and procedures related to the data analysis to fulfil the research objectives by examining the connections in the studied conceptual framework and responding

to research questions. Most suggested connections among the constructs were confirmed and are statistically significant, except for three connections.

Chapter 8. Conclusions

It addresses both the importance of results and their implications, along with the limitation of this research. Some directions for further research are suggested within a context that relies on the research findings. References and appendices are presented next.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. INTRODUCTION

The current chapter critically evaluates the associated literature, using an academic analysis and incorporating research in marketing management. It aims to present the current status of the study of the study by comprehensively understanding and endorsing the research conceptual model, which includes models, theories, hypotheses, and concepts. The TNE market orientation is related to various disciplines, such as the marketisation of higher education, exporting in universities, university business approach, higher education customers, export market orientation in universities, and export market orientation and export performance (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2016; Grecic, 2022; Harris, 2020; James and Derrick, 2021; Silva et al., 2023).

This chapter will include seven sections following this brief introduction. The next section focuses on the business paradigms surrounding higher education export marketing, specifically examining the business philosophy related to universities. This section involves defining higher education's core business, understanding universities' customers, and measuring business performance from the export market orientation (EMO) perspective. This will illustrate the different concepts and models linked to TNE marketing, emphasising gaps in higher education export marketing. Then, as TNE market orientation is originated from market orientation (MO) philosophy, the third section will communicate the development of TNE and MO models to understand the theoretical concept related to (TNEMO). The fourth section discusses the three elements of TNEMO by examining its measurement dimensions. The fifth section explores different antecedents to TNEMO. The sixth and seven sections shed light on higher education international reputation and TNE business performance, considering them as consequences of TNEMO, followed by a summary section.

2.2. THE PARADIGMS OF TRANSNATIONAL EDUCATION AND MARKET ORIENTATION

2.2.1. Universities business approach paradigm

In the current globalised world, knowledge, according to Rinaldi et al. (2018), is the most crucial resource for rethinking and innovating economies. Bamberger et al. (2019) have noted that, within this context, universities are required to change their role in society, particularly concerning their contribution to social, regional, cultural, and economic development. While Gouvea et al. (2013) state that universities, at a regional scale, should actively involve in the growth of groups or clusters of geographically-related components and effectively engage with them.

The foundation of universities targeted education as their main objective, with teaching, as mentioned by Caruana and Montgomery (2015), being the primary activity in universities. In the first academic revolution during the nineteenth century, universities began to expand their activities, make research one of their core activities. Towards the end of the 20th century, universities adopted a new mission, evolving their studies impact on society after the 1980s, (Abbasov, 2019; Grecic, 2022; Vangelis et al., 2018). The emergence of the second academic revolution has contributed to the creation of the entrepreneurial university model. Some researchers argue that, according to this model, universities enter into triple helix partnerships with government and industry (He and Hutson, 2018; Rinaldi et al., 2018; Williamson, 2021), leading to innovation-driven approaches and subsequently to regional and international economic development (Gouvea et al., 2013; Musselin, 2018; Yencken et al., 2021).

The international business of universities, or academic capitalism as defined by Thoenig and Paradeise (2016), relies on the movement and operation of people, ideas, and information overseas. Since the 1990s, the global movement of programmes, institutions, students, and staff has reached a modern standard (Tomlinson, 2017; Wilson et al., 2016). According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the number of international students receiving higher education outside their home countries exceeded 2 million by 2000 (Bleiklie et al., 2017). By 2010, this number had increased to more than 4.1 million, and it was expected to reach 7 million international students in 2020 (Agasisti and Soncin, 2021). However, Bilecen (2020) argues that the Covid-19 pandemic affected negatively the growth of TNE business, particularly in the UK, USA, Canada, and Australia (Foroudi et al., 2021b).

The increase in universities' international business coincides with an unprecedented growth in world trade (Bowles and Brindle, 2017). This fact led Grant (2013) to the perception that universities need to play two roles simultaneously. First, as globalisation agents, encouraging students to engage in international higher education movements, and second, as a business with responsibility to respond to globalisation's consequences. Jones et al. (2012) observed the competition between UK universities and aggressively marketed competitors worldwide (Healey, 2018) as an increasing sign of challenges in higher education international business.

Building on the previous view, Vangelis et al. (2018) added that international competition faced by UK universities can be influenced by two prime styles. First, universities focus on increasing their reputation via the development of international research, and second, by intensifying efforts to generate incomes from international students' tuition fees (Marginson, 2016). As a result, staff working in the UK higher education sector might perceive the internationalisation of their universities only as an opportunity to explore markets with high potential for recruiting international students (Ashwin and McVitty, 2015; Dollinger and Lodge, 2019; Grant, 2013).

On the other hand, researchers, including Asaad et al. (2013), David (2016), Healey (2013), and Dwyer (2022), recommended that the university needs to show high performance in each of its fields. This includes having innovative faculties with a clear and tangible influence on students and staff, active engagement with students (in various learning opportunities), the local community, and business. Additionally, universities should show a sustained commitment of higher education providers to undertake enterprise and entrepreneurship, which in return will support the economy's development (David, 2016; Dwyer, 2022).

Rossano et al. (2016) delved deep and criticised academics, claiming that academics intending to present themselves as promoters of university-business cooperation need to expand the orientation they practice beyond teaching or research. David (2016) added to this claim, emphasising that academics must consider and manage the cultural differences among businesses and academia. While Caruana and Montgomery (2015) stated that academic must balance their entrepreneurial engagements and regular academic duties with businesses, as these activities require significant efforts and time (Bamberger et al., 2019). Therefore, the quality of teaching may be negatively affected by academics' entrepreneurial engagements (Jones, 2014; Rossano et al., 2016).

2.2.2. Higher education customers paradigm

Higher education is considered a service (Bunce et al., 2017; Guilbault, 2018), which includes TNE with several customers and stakeholders. In marketing theory, customers are viewed as individuals seeking to acquire a specific product or service by paying to receive the desired benefit (Asaad et al., 2013; Edirisinghe et al., 2020; Vangelis et al., 2018). This reality is accepted in the context of higher education, especially for students who are the ones paying for the education they will receive. The marketing concept also confirms that students are primary customers by emphasising the notion of interaction (Ashwin and McVitty, 2015). Guilbault (2018) supports this view, describing students as the core customers for universities, followed by employees, employers, and parents.

In another confirmatory concept to the above view, a senior marketing executive declared that “Students are customers, and I would challenge anyone to suggest otherwise. We are charging our customers nearly £50,000 over three years, and for that cost, they deserve to know that they will receive the very best service” (Dollinger and Lodge, 2019). In line with this statement, Marc C. Taylor said, “to deny that higher education is a product and students are customers is to duck the tough questions we should be asking” (New York Times Editors, 2010, para. 8). Therefore, the student transformation to customers became a phenomenon which is experienced in all universities, however, it appears to function particularly effectively in western universities with competitive markets (UK, Australia, and the USA).

Student trust in higher education, as outlined by Zepke (2015), is a key element in developing student recruitment. Building trust relies on students’ perceptions of friendliness, the openness of the university, truthfulness, and genuineness (Safdar et al., 2020). Therefore, the increase in trust is seen to be related to the increase in students’ (customers’) satisfaction. These statements emphasise the mindset of university customers, including customers of TNE (Naylor et al., 2021).

2.2.3. Marketisation of higher education paradigm

To compete effectively, educational institutions should differentiate themselves to a level that limits competition (Kwiek and Massen, 2012; Nixon et al., 2018) by creating a unique image of value that can easily reach students, parents, and employers (Naidoo and Williams, 2015) and guarantee they remain in a competitive position (Rowley and Skipper, 2021). Therefore, this perception reflects positively on the education institution's quality and its perceived value (Yayla et al., 2018). University management is beginning to realise that they will not attract students by standing passively and waiting for them (Nixon et al., 2010; Tomlinson, 2017). Therefore, Molesworth et al. (2011) believe in the necessity to promote universities to potential students, and for attracting and retaining students, universities must adopt a marketing approach (Molesworth et al., 2011). However, judging service quality in education remains a challenging process (Brown and Carasso, 2013), as it is among the most intangible services (Ball, 2012; Olssen, 2016).

Recently, the marketisation of the higher education sector has been presented as a 'paradigm shift' and an 'epidemic' (İpek and Bicakcriogulu-Peynirci, 2020; Molesworth et al., 2011) in what is considered the Western world's delivery of university education (Bobe and Kober, 2015). The increasing global marketisation related to higher education creates pressure on universities to establish an international marketing strategy to benefit from international students (Wright and Shore, 2017). Unfortunately, despite all the efforts toward marketisation, the outcomes from education sectors display a lack of improvement (Nixon et al., 2018).

A historical trends analysis across the UK, New Zealand, Australia, and the United States concludes that results from these leaders of the higher education sector display similar approaches regarding an extensive marketisation policy (Firmansyah et al., 2023). However, the conclusion of these researchers states that the purported system-wide benefits of education's marketisation have not yet been realised. Universities, under the pressures of enrolment, are compelled to apply aggressive promotion and marketing strategies targeting international students (Maisuria and Cole, 2017; Naidoo and Williams, 2015; Nixon et al., 2018), resulting in a big business contributing to the development of the marketisation of higher education. From the perspective of some higher education institutions, this is increasing the generated revenues from tuition fees of international students, which helps their financial stability.

Furthermore, promoting the student experience as a reference could create unrealistic expectations for new students. Some research indicates that students may choose a profession based on an idealistic view, relying on the lifestyle associated with that profession rather than the profession itself (Brown and Carasso, 2013; Palfreyman and Tapper, 2016). This aspect has been selected for use in the marketing of courses, reflecting only the positive side of certain programmes.

Nixon et al. (2018) were the first to highlight the need for universities to facilitate easy access to information to support students in making informed decision about their investment in education (Nixon et al., 2018). Results from research emphasise that a wrong choice of programme or university can negatively impact the success, engagement, and retention of students (Firmansyah et al., 2023; Naidoo and Williams 2015). The prevailing effect of marketisation in the UK and the subsequent increase in student fees have sparked a new debate about students as consumers. This debate is centred on the idea that students should have the right to receive the information necessary to evaluate an offer of a programme. Universities are required to follow and adhere to guidelines issued by the Competition and Markets Authority (the competition regulator department in the UK) to regulate the type of information students should find about the programme and university through the university's marketing (Rowley and Skipper, 2021).

Therefore, critics' research confirms that the marketisation of higher education has not been clear, particularly considering the different challenges faced by universities in marketing their programmes to international students (Brooks, 2019; Chubb and Watermeyer, 2017). The cost of marketing activities presents another challenge, leading higher education institutions to reallocate their scarce resources and priorities elsewhere. However, universities' marketing activities do not guarantee that students will be positively influenced when making their decisions (Paul and Sanchez-Morcilio, 2019). On the contrary, the literature also documented that some universities are successful in increasing the number of students they recruit, while others struggle to maintain their international average enrolment despite the efforts invested in marketing activities (Menendez and Castilla, 2021; Tomlinson, 2018).

2.2.4. Exporting in universities paradigm

During the 1980s, sending students to study abroad to enable them to socialise and study with peers from other cultures, was known as internationalisation (Abbasov, 2019; Khanna, 2021). The common definition of internationalisation is that of Brown (2011): “a complex and multi-levelled set of reasons which evolve over time and in response to changing needs and trends” (p.204). Then, in 2012, Chung considered the concept of internationalisation as a phenomenon that exceeds exporting educational services with its engagement to activities that contribute to increase the international profile of institutions. Universities exporting has been influenced by economic interests which diversified its global contexts (Carasso and Locke, 2015; Chankseliani, 2017; İpek, 2019; Kantola and Kettunen, 2012; Wilkins and Rumbley, 2018). The mid-1990s witnessed the rise of universities exporting from an economic rational context (Altbach and de Wit, 2020; Wilkins, 2016; Wilkins and Rumbley, 2018).

Carey (2018) illustrated that intercultural, international, and global dimension process seen as related to all university’s aspects by exporting and delivering services of education. The perception of Carey was adopted by Davey (2015), believing that this concept is expanding over time to cover partnerships related to educational institutions globally including exchange of curriculum, programmes, activities, and students. Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2015b) were able to detect the common strategies among universities, such as international movement of academic staff; students and research; international relationships among countries via scholarship; open learning technologies; curriculum development and collaboration in research; public diplomacy partnerships; fundraising and studying in a foreign language.

Export of education, according to Altbach and De Wit (2020), is experiencing a growth which makes it a huge phenomenon equivalent to the commercialisation and globalisation of education. Exporting education, now, is presented in several countries with a purpose to develop their societies’ educational systems (Hu and Willis, 2017). Terho et al. (2015) observe that developing countries are experiencing a mute multidimensional revolution in education, which must be evaluated deeply regarding the flow in higher education from the perspective of its internationalisation and privatisation. Universities’ services have been transformed by export to become commodity products with the ability to enter the international market of trading, hence, service export has changed and influenced higher education sector, then employed this fact to modify university’s activities (Knight, 2016; Keay et al., 2014).

Hancock (2015) and Khanna (2021) noted that providers of export education, such as the UK, the USA, and Australia, are increasingly treating cross-border educational services as a business, charging international students full-price tuition compared to local students. This explains the growing interest of international universities in expanding and engaging in business-orientated trading. As a result, the competition among universities to recruit international students is witnessing an increased desire to expand internationally (Abbasov, 2019; Bovill et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2016; Garrett et al., 2016; Hoyt and Howell, 2012). This trend is amplified by the fact that students, facing limited access to high-quality education at their home universities, are exploring alternatives such as TNE. The challenges associated with travelling to another country for higher education, including academic, emotional, and socio-cultural aspects, as well as the financial burden, contribute to the appeal of TNE (Sasson, 2018; Yudkevich, 2016).

2.2.5. Export market orientation in universities paradigm

The theories of market orientation created by Narver, Slater, Kohli and Jaworski are the most widely accepted theories in studies conducted on this subject (Gnangnon, 2021; Kohli et al., 1993; Narver and Slater, 1990). They defined the market orientation as an extension of the marketing concept, describing it as a set of beliefs and values that prioritise customers above all else (Fang et al., 2014). Based on their findings, market orientation involves processes characterised by the continuous creation of additional value for customers. Again, Kohli and Jaworski (1993), delving deeper, assert that the market orientation concept is rooted in the philosophy of the marketing concept, focusing on both organisational profits and customer needs (Kohli, 2017). This judgement involves generation of required information about customers, the dissemination of the generated information among managers, then responsiveness to the information that is disseminated (Asaad et al., 2015).

The export market orientation concept poses a universal dilemma as it lacks full and common acceptance of its conception (Beneke et al., 2016; Cadogan et al., 2012; Kohli et al., 2017). İpek and Bicakcriogulu-Peynirci (2020) suggest that export market orientation should firmly include behavioural and attitudinal aspects. Conversely, Lin et al. (2014) found that export market orientation is attached to the development of both customer and product. In another study, He et al. (2018) perceived export market orientation as a process that characterises elements in the market value chain of behaviours, culture, actions, processes, and performance.

Chung (2012) suggested that market orientation perception should take into account influencing factors such as regulatory, social, and macroeconomic factors.

Several studies have indicated that universities potentially benefit from market orientation (Asaad et al., 2015; Casidy, 2014; Gnanngnon, 2021). According to James and Derrick (2021), the application of this philosophy might be true for non-profit organisations and could also be linked to superior business performance for the organisation. Therefore, a number of practices and discourses, provided by managerial ideology, have transferred from the corporate world to higher education (Yu et al., 2018). Furthermore, research conducted by Hult and Ketchen (2017) illustrates that operational managerial models can be valuable for academic literature if the autonomous niches of education are protected. The theory of export market orientation proposes that a well-developed export market orientation is related to excellent export performance (Cadogan et al., 2012; Cadogan et al., 2016).

Universities adopting market orientation in their settings benefit from developing a student-oriented environment. Woodall et al. (2014) stated that customer and competitor orientation, along with inter-functional coordination, are facts that contribute to supporting the management of the university in understanding and structuring their institutions' environment effectively. However, to make this orientation effective, university management should believe that influencing students will be appropriate. Asaad et al. (2013) were among the first to investigate the export market orientation in universities, illustrating that market-oriented universities must generate, disseminate, and respond to relevant market information (Asaad et al., 2015; James, 2021; Yu et al., 2018). The necessity to implement these activities, relying on information, is seen to be greater in an export setting due to the variety of marketing and the complexity of the environment (Cadogan et al., 2012; Diamantopoulos and Cadogan, 1996).

In higher education, Asaad et al. (2015) illustrated that a continuous communication is reflected by export coordination especially among universities' departments, via official means such as intranet portal, reports, and meetings, or unofficial means like daily communication among managers about key foreign market developments and trends (Diamantopoulos and Cadogan, 1996; İpek, 2020; Yu et al., 2018). The mechanism of coordination illustrates the role of the accumulation of effort from different schools and departments in a university and the wide responsibility.

2.2.6. Export market orientation performance paradigm

Export performance is used by business owners to stay updated on the status of their organisation's goals and objectives (Hill et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2018), while investors use this approach to measure particular productivity and financial indicators (Alotaibi and Zhang, 2017; Hill et al., 2014). Management employs export performance to analyse previous performance and then make necessary adjustments, whilst employees use it to pursue productivity to achieve their bonus pay criteria (Acikdilli, 2015; Kaplan, 2001; Racela and Thoumrungroje, 2014). Kaplan (2001) states that management performance and strategic performance have begun to be tracked by non-profit organisations, with aim to compete for funds from donors, scarce resources, government resources, and foundations.

Export market orientation plays a significant role in the marketing strategy and export performance due to environmental changes and competition intensity (Casidy, 2014; Birru, 2019). Ghorbani et al. (2014) argued that export performance is affected by market-oriented resources, which provide important preferences in creating and preserving robust customer relationships. Organisations which are highly market-oriented constantly aim to achieve customer value creation and improvement of business performance (Zebal, 2012; Chang and Fan, 2015). In international markets, according to the study by Murray et al. (2011), the survival and success of organisations depend on the application of market orientations in the context of export.

There are various efforts to measure export performance (Beneke et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2011; Lin et al., 2014). However, a number of studies employ objective measures, such as sales growth, export sales, and export intensity, while others support the application of subjective measures, such as the accomplishment of export goals or satisfaction with export performance. While these initial studies feature a blend of objectivity and comparability, emerging markets often encounter issues of unreliability or unavailability of much of this data (He and Wei, 2011; Gruber-Muecke and Hofer, 2015).

Almost all empirical studies conducted on export performance have demonstrated a positive link among export market orientation and export performance. Cadogan et al.'s framework in 1999, 2009, 2012, and 2016 established the common structure of EMO, presenting it through three variables (export market intelligence generation, export market intelligence dissemination, and responsiveness to market intelligence). Consequently, studies on this topic

has primarily focused on indicators of higher education business performance rather than examining business performance in the TNE context, leaving a gap in research regarding a theory that would conceptualise and operationalise TNE business performance.

2.3. TRANSNATIONAL EDUCATION MARKET ORIENTATION

2.3.1. Transnational Education Emergence and its Development

2.3.1.1. Cross-border education

The phenomenon of cross-border education is not new to literature, where some UK universities (Red brick universities) engaging in this activity as far back as 1858 (Healey, 2015). Australian universities also provided education, between the 1950s and 1980s, to thousands of international students (Harris, 2020; Knight and John, 2017). Cross-border education, in its diversified forms, is considered as a very common phenomenon globally (Healey and Michael, 2015; Knight and John, 2017).

The cross-border education has largely been addressed in higher education literature as a mean of exporting higher education, encompassing the movement of course materials, providers/institutions, programmes, students, and teachers across national borders (Harris, 2020; Healey, 2013), rather than from a business perspective. This type of higher education involves several modalities, ranging from the face-to-face styles, including campus abroad programmes and students traveling internationally, to distance learning, heavily reliant on various technologies, especially e-learning. In this field of research, certain indicators, such as public and private providers, whether for-profit or non-profit, have dominated the discourse.

Also, researchers have predominantly focused more on factors surrounding the necessity of international regulatory involvement in organising cross-border education, including the General Agreement on Trade and Services (GATS) and the World Trade Organisation (WTO) (Bowles et al., 2017; Rienties, 2019). While these studies attempted to reveal the understanding of the most popular modes of this international education service, referred to as the four modes of supply under GATS: (Mode 1) Cross-border Supply, (Mode 2) Consumption abroad, (Mode 3) Commercial presence, and (Mode 4) Presence of natural resources (Healey, 2018).

2.3.1.2. Transnational education (TNE)

Students who pursue their studies at foreign universities without physically relocating to another country are considered participants in transnational education (TNE) (Burgess and Berquist, 2012; Healey, 2015; Lien and Keithley, 2020). Consequently, educational material, staff, and information transcend national borders to reach students in the host country (Healey, 2015). TNE can manifest in various forms, including the virtual or physical movement of individual curricula or training programmes overseas through distance learning, face-to-face interactions, or a blended combination of modalities (Harris, 2020; Knight, 2016).

TNE activities in the literature are positioned between two perspectives among researchers. Healey (2020) and Knight (2011) assert that motives behind TNE are related to host universities, with their governments encouraging foreign universities to support capacity building. In contrast, other perspectives advocate for the home university to invest more in TNE, aiming to establish a global brand through marketing activities (Bennell, 2022) and generate additional commercial revenue (Wilkins and Rumbley, 2018).

The following are the four TNE activities:

International branch campus (IBC)

An international branch campus is established by a university overseas to deliver and confer degrees upon students in the host country (Wilkins and Huisman, 2021). Some academic staff is locally recruited to reduce operating costs (Yencken et al., 2021). Quality assurance for the IBS is typically under the control of the host country (Ones et al., 2021).

Distance-learning

This TNE activity involves replacing textbook-based correspondence courses with online provision due to the emergency of the internet (Rienties, 2019; Yudkevich et al., 2016). Therefore, it enables the university to maintain full control over students' admission, teaching, and assessment. However, in practice, distance learning often necessitates a network of local partners to provide students with on-the-ground support (Bowles and Brindle, 2017; Healey, 2015).

Franchise

A franchise relies on the authorisation granted by a university to a foreign partner institution in a host country to provide degrees on its behalf (Healey, 2015; Henderson et al., 2017). The franchise programme, with its different components including the degree title, teaching material, syllabus, and assessment, is purely related to the corresponding degree offered on the home campus. However, due to the differences in each country's circumstances, the university might permit variations, such as incorporating modules on local business law (Rienties, 2019). In this TNE activity, the home university allows its partner to have significant control over the programme's management, as opposed to the international branch campus (Bamberger et al., 2019).

Validation

Validation occurs when the home university only authenticates a degree developed and delivered by a foreign partner (Abrahams and Brooks, 2019; Guerrero et al., 2015). This TNE activity goes beyond accreditation, as the partner is authorised by the home university to offer its own degree as if it were developed by the home university (Caruana and Montgomery, 2015; Bovill, 2017). In validation, control is greatly in the hands of the overseas partner, but assessment undergoes oversight by the awarding university (Bovill et al., 2015; Healey, 2018).

2.3.1.3. Transnational education demand globally

According to recent trends, TNE is seen to be growing rapidly. Countries with a substantial number of providers include the USA, Australia, and the UK. In addition, Europe, New Zealand, and Canada have recently emerged as notable regions and countries in this sector. Non-traditional TNE providers, including Singapore, Malaysia, India, and China, are also gaining recognition (Lien and Keithley, 2020).

According to Healey (2008), in 2006, there were more than 2,000 programmes offered to 500,000 students globally, with 300,000 enrolled in British TNE programmes. Further, Chankseliani (2017) notes that after ten years (2016), the number of offshore students enrolled in UK TNE programmes exceeded 700,000, representing an annual growth of 8%. Similar increases have been witnessed in Australia and USA (Bachan, 2017). The number of IBC globally experienced a growth of 100% in the last decade, rising from 162 IBCs in 2009 to 325 IBCs in 2018 (Lien and Keithley, 2020). The Middle East and the Asia-Pacific are the regions

hosting the most IBCs, as report by the Observatory on Borderless Higher Education (Girdzijauskaite et al., 2019). Therefore, strategies such as market orientation is needed in universities to maintain effective growth in the export of higher education (Asaad et al., 2015).

2.3.2. Market orientation theory and its development

The market orientation theory relies on the longstanding recognition of the significance of the marketing concept (Glaveli and Geormas, 2018; Gruber-Muecke, 2015). The marketing concept illustrates that an organisation's success depends on its ability to understand the needs and wants of the target market, and then to offer the desired satisfaction better than competitors (Kohli, 2017; Dwyer, 2022). This is achieved by the firm's mastery in offering a relevant customer value over its competitors (Jaworski and Kohli, 2017). However, in higher education marketing, very little academic interest has been dedicated to this field (Asaad et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2018). Therefore, establishing a link between market orientation and one of the marketing concepts, as described by Kohli and Jaworski (1990), became significant within several types of organisations (Cadogan et al., 2013).

After clarifying the market orientation concept, scholars and practitioners of marketing have shown a significant interest in this concept (Devece et al., 2017; Firmansyah et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2011). Drucker (1954) is one of the scholars who previously targeted the value of customer focus, suggesting that the functional activity of marketing is not solely reliant on specialisation but represents the perspective of customers across the entire envisioned business. Despite several previous studies indicating the development of market orientation concept and its capacity to generate sustainable competitive advantage, it has found its place in various significant research models, drawing on the foundation works of Narver and Slater (1990) and Kohli and Jaworski (1990).

In the work of Kohli and Jaworski (1990), the conceptualised market orientation is an effective instrument used by the organisation to generate market intelligence relevant to its customers' current or future needs. It involves disseminating the generated intelligence among the organisation's departments and responding to this intelligence. From the cultural perspective, as represented in Narver and Slater's 1990 work, market orientation refers to the organisational culture capable of creating needed behaviours most efficiently and effectively. The aim is to deliver superior value to customers, thereby maintaining a business with superior performance (Dwyer, 2022; Firmansyah et al., 2023).

2.4. COMPONENTS OF TNE MARKET ORIENTATION

As described earlier in this chapter, Diamantopoulos and Cadogan (1996) proposed the export market orientation (EMO) concept as an extension of the market orientation applied in exporting organisations. Again, as it was defined in this chapter, TNE is considered an activity that falls under export. Therefore, TNE market orientation aligns with the literature in a similar concept as export market orientation (Asaad et al., 2015), but within a very specific context. Thus, TNE market orientation focuses on the implementation of marketing in a setting of service export (Jaworski and Kohli, 2017), particularly in higher education, where marketing managers must value the current and future needs of international students and fulfil those needs (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2012; Firmansyah et al., 2023; James and Derrick, 2021; Yu et al., 2017). Therefore, TNE market orientation, in line with Cadogan et al.'s (2016) statement on EMO, comprises three coordinated activities: generating, disseminating, and responding to TNE market information.

Scholars have illustrated that both market information generation and dissemination are empirically and conceptually firmly linked, shaping an institution's information activities (Boso et al., 2018; James and Derrick, 2021; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014). Information activities conducted by an exporting university include gathering and distribution information after a thorough foreign market analysis (Asaad et al., 2013; Boyd et al., 2010). Bovill (2015) indicates a strong link between market information and a firm's ability to effectively select and implement marketing strategy. Thus, all the aforementioned activities within the exporting context can be applied to develop TNE market intelligence.

The dispersal of information across all organisation levels in an exporting context represents the dissemination of export market information, where collected information is conducted by one or both of the following approaches: local or foreign market research companies and/or an internal department delegated for such purposes (Chung, 2012; Hancock, 2015). The dissemination of export market information, linked to international students and competitors (universities) within the institution, supports the creation of a platform for information sharing among top managers and employees (Chen et al., 2016; He et al., 2018). This, in turn, reinforces greater information development via collaborative experience sharing among individuals, departments, and branches of a university (Yu et al., 2018; İpek and Bicakcriogulu-Peynirci, 2020).

Relevant to the strategy implementation of customer-focused sales, responding to market needs overseas hold significant importance for institutions seeking to increase their performance (He et al., 2018; Morgan et al., 2012). Therefore, information generation and dissemination are substantial components of a TNE sales approach, as they contribute to sales mission objectives by effectively segmenting international students, determining and choosing the most profitable markets, fostering efficient resource allocation, and establishing effective international connections (Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; James and Derrick, 2021).

Building on descriptions provided above regarding export market orientation, the components of TNE market orientation can be outlined as follows:

TNE information generation:

This term refers to the activities conducted by marketing managers to cover the opportunities or threats that would affect their TNE (Asaad et al., 2015; Bovill et al., 2015; Keay et al., 2014; Knight, 2016; Vangelis et al., 2018).

TNE information dissemination:

This term refers to the activities conducted by marketing managers to share the collected information on the TNE market (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2015; Henderson et al., 2017; Vangelis et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018).

TNE information responsiveness:

This term represents how marketing managers respond to TNE market information that has been generated and disseminated (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2015; Henderson et al., 2017; Vangelis et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018).

2.5. ANTECEDENTS OF TNE MARKET ORIENTATION

2.5.1. Transnational education coordination

Coordination concept in organisation

Coordination in business management is understood as the effectiveness of interaction between members in relation to their positions within an organisation (Cadogan et al., 2016; James and Derrick, 2021; Jules, 2018). In this context, coordination, as described by Diamantopoulos et al. (2014), is evident when there are logically coherent and consistent work activities among parties. Jules (2015) argued that conflict is inevitable in business management but should be controlled via coordination. Therefore, managers should be guided into a shared goal, emphasising mutual complementing and supplementing (Sukoco et al., 2021; Morgan et al., 2012).

Coordination in export

Export coordination, as described by Cadogan et al. (2012), encompasses various overlapping and interrelated themes. These themes involve working toward shared goals, the absence of work conflict, and fostering cooperation within the firm, which includes assisting and helping others. Asaad et al. (2015) discussed internal organisational culture based on responsibility acceptance and shared understanding facilities via communication among all staff members in all departments. Furthermore, Cadogan et al. (2016) stated that export market orientation activities can be effectively performed when the export coordination of the organisation is identified through high levels of inter- and intra-functional cooperation.

Drawing on diverse empirical research that has explored the antecedents specific to export market orientation, significant advancements have been made in the literature of export marketing (Cadogan et al., 2012; Crick, 2021; James and Derrick, 2021). While coordination is acknowledged by exporters across several industries, Abbasov (2019) highlights the necessity of including certain industries, such as higher education, in research due to potential differences in market forces.

TNE coordination

TNE coordination involves fostering a positive work environment between managers from different departments with a university concerning TNE matters (Asaad et al., 2015; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; Healy, 2020; Feng et al., 2013). From transnational perspective, educational coordination is not fundamentally different from traditional organisational coordination, as TNE coordination relies on similar aspects to export coordination (Chabowski et al., 2018; Morais Silva, 2009; Chang et al., 2014), utilising hierarchical techniques or meta-steering, as previously described. In TNE, coordination is essential for aligning university activities across borders, encompassing educational exchange and technical activities (Guruz, 2011; Girdzijauskaitė et al., 2019; Wright and Shore, 2017).

Therefore, TNE coordination is viewed as synonymous with the structuring, deepening, and consolidating of partnerships of higher education through dialogue of educational policy between TNE stakeholders. Further research could explore the influence of its key characteristics on TNE market orientation (Chabowski et al., 2018).

2.5.2. University international ranking position

Rankings in literature are not a new phenomenon; in 1925, the first academic ranking was delivered by the 'National Academy of Sciences' in US (Bobe and Kober, 2015). However, academics still do not completely agree on university rankings, and some consider them harmful, self-interested, and not fully understanding the crucial features of teaching and research (Bobe and Kober, 2015). The international ranking position of universities assesses the quality and performance of higher education internationally (Ghobehei et al., 2019; Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016; Rutter et al., 2017).

Altbach and de Wit (2020) illustrated that the concept of university international rankings is neither stable nor sustainable. This observation encourages personnel involved in export marketing activities to align their efforts with the objectives of the university. Ghobehei et al. (2019) asserted that a high international ranking position does not necessarily indicate a successful university. Different guidelines and methodologies for ranking can influence a university's position, but managers are a key element to spot defects in programmes delivered and guide EMO. Hazelkorn (2018) perceives rankings, in general, as creating an audience of reference and instilling managerial confidence in marketing strategies used for orientation.

The literature suggests that EMO in higher education can be influenced by university ranking positions, with top-ranked universities paying less attention to EMO compared to those at the bottom of the ranking list (Asaad et al., 2015; Christensen et al., 2018; Hazelkorn, 2018). Christensen et al. (2018) explained that top-ranking universities often rely on their status to enlarge international student enrolments. Zhou and Wu (2016) argued that an organisation's ranking can either increase or decrease its chances of engaging in export activities. Thus, this perception can also be applied in the higher education sector.

Thus, researchers (Asaad et al., 2015; Ghobehei et al., 2019) have determined that ranking in higher education helps in managerial measurements regarding EMO. Therefore, it is useful to determine specific factors related to universities' export operations that could either discourage or facilitate TNE market orientation activities.

2.5.3. Developed country higher education image perception

The ‘developed country higher education image perception’ refers to how stakeholders of universities in these nations perceive and evaluate the image of their higher education institutions (Asaad et al., 2015; Foroudi et al., 2019; Hailat et al., 2019). Literature suggests that the investigation of marketing higher education image is a recent phenomenon, yet it is witnessing increasing growth. Publications addressing this topic were few until the beginning of the 21st century when many researchers began to engage with this subject (Ghobehei et al., 2019; Bennell, 2022). Many of these investigations were conducted between 2007 and 2018 due to scholars’ recognition of how the image of Western universities plays a role as organisational actors in fostering international higher education development (Ghobehei et al., 2019).

Employers consider students with UK qualifications as qualified candidates, as they believe that UK higher education provides students with skills that employers need (Jimenez-Castillo et al., 2013). Therefore, according to Henderson et al. (2017), managers’ perception is also associated with growth of graduates’ employability, as marketing managers use this aspect to polish the higher education institution’s image worldwide. This is based on the concept of export dependency, which calls on organisations to effectively use related export information for cost-effective (Baker and Ballington, 2011; Foroudi et al., 2019). Therefore, the way managers perceive their country’s higher education image is positively related to TNE market orientation.

Researchers have expressed that students and academic staff are the main stakeholders for universities and are significant contributors to the growth of the university image process (Bennell, 2022; Firmansyah et al., 2023; Ghobehei et al., 2019). However, Healey (2020) argued that marketing managers’ experiences regarding the perception built around a particular university image provide signals for effective marketing strategies. Cadogan (2013) conceived that managers’ experiences help organisations better understand the consequences of their activities and formulate effective responses. Nonetheless, according to Koris et al. (2015), previous studies on higher education image primarily focused on students’ perceptions rather than those of managers. Palfreyman and Tapper (2016) suggested that research covering managers’ perceptions and experiences, which could reflect their relationships and activities, is needed in the context of exporting higher education.

2.6. HIGHER EDUCATION INTERNATIONAL REPUTATION AS CONSEQUENCE

The concerns and uncertainties of TNE's stakeholders shrink due to the value of a good reputation, which also increases trust in the value, differentiation, and quality of programmes delivered (Czinkota et al., 2014; Espeland and Sauder, 2016). Acquiring a good reputation enables the university to build support and credibility with its stakeholders (Feldman and Sandoval, 2018). Also, reputation is one of the main intangible assets for organisations, serving as a source of a sustainable competitive advantage that increases over time and influences decision-making (Bastedo and Bowman, 2010; Lozano et al., 2018). Hence, an entry barrier is created for potential competitors and contributes to the growth of organisations with positive reputations, as establishing such reputation requires time and is not easily imitated (Feldman and Sandoval, 2018; Miotto et al., 2020). Therefore, most studies on services exports agree that good reputation is linked to the positive results of organisational export market orientation (Espeland and Sauder, 2016; Feldman and Sandoval, 2018; Lozano et al., 2018).

A higher TNE reputation is projected by a range of judgments and beliefs that observers make about a university, where value increases through good market orientation (Miotto et al., 2020). The literature on organisations' EMO, and especially the gathering and use of market information, is positively related to reputation (Boyd et al., 2010; Wilkins et al., 2012a). Vercic et al. (2016) argued that positive influence of good information on reputation is justified by the need of associated marketing information on the trust of stakeholders about organisational services, while Czinkota et al. (2014) indicated that the trust of stakeholders in an organisation is a key element in reputation. However, Guilbault (2016) emphasised that TNE market orientation influences remain effective with the presence of responses to marketing information.

Marketing staff and university management work together to develop and create a reputable university that would satisfy students aligned with other internal and external stakeholders (Foroudi et al., 2014; Foroudi et al., 2017). In this context, Wilkins and Huisman (2016) note, "as universities have become more exposed to competitive market forces, export market orientation has become more important in contributing to the creation of reputable institutions that will help attract students, staff and resources" (p. 177). Therefore, universities that have a positive strategy of EMO contribute to improve and maintain the reputation of the university internationally (Davey, 2015; Menendez and Castilla, 2021).

2.7. TNE BUSINESS PERFORMANCE AS CONSEQUENCE

Business performance is the positive outcome of managers' activities, reflecting their efficiency in satisfying and achieving the set plans for business growth (Assad et al., 2015; Hailat et al., 2019; Healey, 2013; Murray et al., 2011). The literature on export and international performance illustrates a positive correlation between them (Cadogan et al., 2016; He and Wei, 2011; Birru et al., 2019; Pascucci et al., 2002; Warwick 2014). Export performance, according to Makri et al. (2017), can be seen from different perspectives, where financial measures (market share, international sales, growth measures, and profit) are one way to express export performance, while Chung (2011) outlined the non-financial measures, which include assessing management satisfaction regarding goal achievement and exporting (Chang and Fang, 2015).

The success of a business venture relies mostly on its financial performance; this is supported by the research of Healey (2008), which concluded that "success is directly linked to the performance of the firm" (p. 342). In the business management literature, the long-run success of a business is often described in terms of its performance (Birru et al., 2019; He and Wei, 2011). The aim from this context is the effective application of a range of management strategies, such as EMO, to determine the self-performance of the business. However, according to Makri et al. (2017), there is "compelling evidence that businesses have limited lifespans" (p. 633). This is based on the hyper-competition and creative destruction theories, even with the presence of businesses that have been operating for a long time (Asaad et al., 2015).

Several scholars have identified various competencies through which organisations gain excellent export performance (Mac and Evangelist, 2016; Makri et al., 2017), such as managerial systems to control and monitor export activities, export market awareness, and official strategies for pursuing, identifying, and planning export opportunities. Among these competencies, some are conceptually related to export market-oriented activities (Warwick, 2014). According to previous research on export business performance, several customer-focused and information-oriented activities are associated with collecting and disseminating information, as well as responsive behaviours of an entity with EMO (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2016). Thus, creating a market-oriented business fosters successful behaviour.

Performance in higher education literature has been primarily targeted from an academic perspective, focusing on aspects such as research productivity and degree quality, rather than a business perspective (Alotaibi and Zhang, 2017; Frosen et al., 2016). Caruana et al. (2008), Binsardi and Ekwulugo (2003), and Boyd et al. (2010) were the first researchers to discuss the business performance of universities. Later, Asaad et al. (2015) combined university EMO with performance, while other studies focused on indicators such as delivering value for students, satisfaction of students, and universities' ability to attract private funding to represent university performance. However, the study by Singh and Mahmood (2013) illustrates the significance of the growth in international market shares as an export performance indicator in universities. The aim from these studies was to identify indicators' importance in university business performance and to examine performance measurement within the context of education. Therefore, research in higher education needs to develop an effective theoretical framework that conceptualises TNE business performance in relation to the effect of TNE market orientation within the context of management.

2.8. GAPS IN HIGHER EDUCATION EXPORT MARKETING

The literature on EMO has addressed the concept of higher education services, but not specifically from a TNE context. The prevailing studies in the literature relevant to this study have provided a significant amount of evidence about market orientation in higher education as a significant and essential element in creating value for the universities' activities overseas (Nixon et al., 2010; Tomlinson, 2017) and its impact on the growth of TNE. However, this literature review illustrates a number of directions that need additional research. This section reveals the research gap in TNE export marketing that this study determined.

In spite of the advancement of EMO research within the service sector, particularly in area like higher education, scholars have not yet investigated the essence of EMO as perceived by universities in Western countries aiming to generate profits through TNE (Asaad et al., 2015). Also, the previous discussion highlights the lack of a clear conceptualisation and operationalisation of TNE business performance. It suggests adopting a multidimensional approach incorporating financial and non-financial indicators. Nevertheless, TNE business performance should be contextualised within the university's operational environment (Healey, 2018; Melewar et al., 2018).

There is a gap in the declining position of the UK in international student recruitment compared to rival countries such as Australia and Canada (Han 2016, British Council, 2018). Despite the UK's past leadership in this area, it has lost ground to its competitors (Wang 2018). This gap underscores the need for UK universities to reassess their strategies and address factors contributing to this decline, particularly in sustaining revenue through TNE programs. Specifically, there's a need for UK universities to focus on protecting their brand reputation and enhancing the academic experience and employability of TNE graduates to remain competitive in the global education market (Asaad et al., 2015).

The significant potential market has prompted UK universities to invest in TNE activities. However, an increasing number of academic studies have underscored the risks associated with TNE partnerships (Emery and Worton 2014, Healey 2016, Wilkins 2016). For instance, in China, concerns regarding the quality of TNE provision by UK universities resulted in the Ministry of Education abruptly revoking licenses of many Higher Education Institutions and terminating numerous partnerships in progress (British Council, 2018, Wang 2018). This is because many universities lack the advanced business functions necessary for crafting robust business cases and managing international movements of people and money (Healey 2016).

Also, a significant gap exists in addressing the central challenge of complying with host countries' regulations due to the lack of precise and consistently collected data. This gap is particularly evident in the sporadic and disorganised nature of data collection, hindering comprehensive analysis and exacerbating difficulties in maintaining successful partnerships (Ziguras and McBurnie, 2011). Additionally, higher education providers venturing into foreign markets encounter various complexities related to legislative, cultural, and political landscapes (Bentley et al., 2017). Therefore, the ambiguity surrounding this topic delivery further complicates efforts to establish standards equivalence in TNE partnerships.

The literature of higher education has addressed university performance using academic terms such as research productivity or degree quality (Acikdilli, 2015; Kaplan, 2001; Racela and Thourungroje, 2014), rather than considering it as business performance. This further underscores the lack of conceptualisation and operationalisation regarding TNE business performance within universities.

Studies related to higher education export marketing were limited to interpreting marketing within a narrow framework defined by marketing communications. Many of the studies examined EMO in universities are general, focusing more on general marketing principles rather than targeting the specificities of higher education export marketing. This is despite the understanding of EMO research, which has not been extensively applied to the services sector, such as TNE. Therefore, an examination of the nature of export market orientation from the TNE perspective is necessary (Yu et al., 2018).

From another perspective, the majority of this literature is focused on the customer (student) behaviour approach as the main element to investigate the phenomenon between international students and universities. Studies that tackle the examination of EMO from a managerial TNE are rare (Asaad et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2018). Hence, the concept of TNE market orientation remains a field that still requires further investigation. Furthermore, the literature indicates that particular factors unique to higher education exports impact a university's level of export market orientation. Nonetheless, there remains insufficient empirical evidence to validate the impact of critical activities, such as TNE, on market-oriented behaviours (Olssen, 2016).

2.9. SUMMARY

The internal stakeholders of higher education institutions involved in marketing are aware of the value and power of export market orientation and its importance in efficiently conducting large-scale exports. This awareness helps identify potential obstacles to TNE growth through continuous generation, dissemination, and responsiveness to TNE market information. Through this theoretical examination of TNE market orientation, researchers addressed the importance of EMO as an effective means of maintaining control in the international higher education market, making it the primary mission of universities exporting higher education to expand their global market (educational partners and students) (Healey, 2018).

This chapter sheds light on the main approaches to TNE market orientation. The 'exporting perspective' concerns TNE market orientation through university management studies, focusing on how the management of TNE market orientation enhances service exporting through market orientation. 'Higher education marketisation' focuses on how universities can create a unique value image that can easily reach students, parents, and employers, ensuring

they remain competitive. The 'customers' perspective' centres on students as core customers of universities when dealing with marketing in higher education institutions, reflecting the business aspect of universities. This suggests that TNE market orientation management is related to the concept of profit. Lastly, the business approach addresses the internal objectives involves in TNE and their long-term goals.

CHAPTER 3: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

3.1. INTRODUCTION

In Chapter 2, the literature review tackled studies on TNE market orientation, reflecting outcomes that rely on the research setting and context. The development of a conceptual model for this research relied on the theory of export market orientation. It starts with a range of factors that consider antecedents to TNE market orientation and clarifies its consequences. The eight constructs forming this study's conceptual model are TNE coordination, university international ranking position, developed country higher education image perception, TNE market information generation, TNE market information dissemination, TNE market information responsiveness, higher education international reputation, and TNE business performance.

This chapter will characterise the suggested marketing managerial-level conceptual framework, along with several hypotheses that conceptually relate each of them from literature. Apart from this introduction (3.1), four sections will fulfil the purpose of this chapter. Section 3.2 covers the research framework and the development of hypotheses. The relationship between TNE market orientation and its antecedents will be presented in section 3.3. The prime benefits from TNE market orientation will be discussed in section 3.4. Eventually, section 3.5 will summarise this chapter.

3.2. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND DEVELOPMENT OF HYPOTHESES

A TNE market orientation embodies the process of incorporating activities and concepts of market orientation within the export programme activities of universities through marketing strategy and performance, resulting in environmental changes and increased competition intensity (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan, 2012; Healey, 2018; ; İpek and Bicakcriogulu-Peynirci, 2020; Kleibert, 2023). Managing TNE requires a thorough understanding of the international higher education market, particularly regarding export market orientation as a means of TNE expansion. Additionally, the methodologies commonly employed to research a business' expanding market have several disadvantages. Many practitioners and academics have raised concerns about the necessity to investigate higher education from an export context. Consequently, researchers have increased the conceptual literature volume on export market orientation in higher education since the 1990s (Asaad et al., 2015; Dwyer, 2022).

The research did not concentrate on TNE market orientation at the managerial level. As stated by Boyd et al. (2010), Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2015b), Asaad et al. (2013), and İpek and Bicakcioglu-Peynirci (2020), the limited understanding of TNE market orientation is a subject for academics and researchers to focus on through pluralistic research, where both qualitative and quantitative methods are merged to explore areas with unfamiliar identities that have not been deeply investigated. Various studies have adopted experimental methods as a tool to investigate and enhance understanding about TNE (Asaad et al., 2015, Healey, 2013; İpek, 2019; Knight, 2016; Yu et al., 2018). This research differs from previous studies in that it develops a conceptual model based on the perceptions of managers and seeks to explain the function of different factors and fundamental links between various variables impacting TNE market orientation.

The role of the theoretical framework will be based on a mixed-method study, which enables the researcher to determine supplements and develop previous qualitative studies. For the description of the research model, Bryman (2015) argues that when there is a need to clarify the ambiguities covering a phenomenon, then qualitative research is most effective. But researchers such as Guilbault (2016), Healey (2013), İpek (2019), Knight (2009), and Voegtler (2017) advocate for quantitative research, measuring TNE via an ‘experimental aesthetic’ with well-advocated questionnaires. The literature contains various research on the importance of EMO in a way that helps in developing the basis of expanding an exporting service such as TNE, which impacts higher education’s international reputation (Espeland and Sauder, 2016; He and Hutson, 2018; Murray et al., 2007; Wallace and Dunn, 2013).

Therefore, this research complies with the request by Asaad et al. (2015) to investigate the influence of particular antecedents of EMO to demonstrate differences related to international higher education reputation and TNE business performance. The development of a framework model for this study has been completed (Figure 3.1) to test several relationships that were determined in the previous chapter of the literature review, developing a managerial-level conceptual framework related to EMO theory illustrating the relationship among TNE market orientation and its elements. This framework examines factors that either support or discourage its consequences or benefits for universities, as well as the association among different empirically and theoretically specific variables. The connection among concepts and the relevant hypotheses will be discussed in the next section of this chapter, based on previous studies and the coverage of this field of research.

Figure 3.1: The conceptual framework

Guide: Ha; Hb; and Hc represent each of the TNEMO sub construct, and each hypothesis (H1; H2; and H3) will be linked to the three of them.

3.3. TNE MARKET ORIENTATION AND ITS ELEMENTS

The essential element of TNE market orientation is formed by the factors which foster, weaken, or predict the perceived TNE market orientation during its application. The next section will discuss these factors in detail.

3.3.1. TNE coordination and TNE market orientation

TNE market orientation, as the main element of TNE exporting, is the major driver of higher education internationalisation (Knight and John, 2017), aiming to coordinate the service of exporting (Firmansyah et al., 2023; Krücken, 2021; Wilkins and Rumbley, 2018; Healey, 2020) and to acquire and maintain a competitive advantage. Some researchers mentioned in chapter 2 have highlighted the lack of research in this area and the necessary improvements to overcome this issue. Higher education marketing researchers including Asaad et al. (2015), Caruana et al. (2008), Healey et al. (2014), Knight, (2016) have focused on TNE coordination as a motif of TNE market orientation, while Cadogan et al. (2012) argue that organisational coordination is not an antecedent to EMO but an important part of it.

A range of researchers including Altbach and de Wit (2020), Bovill et al. (2015), de Wit and Altbach (2021), Healey (2018), Larsen (2016) perceive TNE as the result of a good management system, employees, and mission statements of a university. TNE relies on several organisational phenomena, including coordination, communication channels, sharing work, common goals, as well as conflict between employees (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2006; Cadogan et al., 2012; Rowley and Skipper, 2021). TNE in universities with the mentioned organisational themes reflects high export coordination, as described in the literature review (section 2.5.1).

TNE marketing requires avoiding the experience of dysfunctional conflict regarding the relationship among the TNE managers, the TNE department, and the university's schools. Universities with different work-related goals enable TNE to be internally and globally oriented, and make expansion precede the market needs (Murray et al., 2011), whereas good communication plus the control of dysfunctional conflict between all departments contributes to the TNE delivery and supports the application of an effective market orientation (Altbach, 2021; Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2012).

TNE coordination and TNE market information generation – Universities that deliver TNE seek strategies that unify their different units and level of management through strategies such as coordination, which facilitate their functional operations (Cadogan et al. 2012; Healey, 2020; Jules, 2018; Kleibert, 2023), whereas coordination can assist university activities in collecting market information (Asaad et al., 2013; Healey, 2018). Prior research mentions that institutions can use their coordination culture to ensure effective usage of customers' opinions. A high level of coordination enhances the development and growth of universities' information generation. Therefore, TNE coordination links with TNE market information generation.

H1a: If TNE is well-coordinated, the generation of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

TNE coordination and TNE market information dissemination – TNE market information dissemination requires both collaboration within the university and cross-departmental integration to increase the volume of information and communication to a level that aligns with TNE goals (Cadogan et al. 2012; Healey, 2020; Larsen, 2016; Jules, 2018). Previous studies illustrate how likely it is that the extent of market information dissemination can be impacted by the quality of coordination in an organisation (Asaad et al., 2015; He et al., 2018). Coordination of the knowledge and efforts obtained by managers is a significant element for market information dissemination strength (Cadogan et al. 2012). Therefore, it is concluded that universities with a high level of TNE coordination has a relation with the TNE market information dissemination.

H1b: If TNE is well-coordinated, the dissemination of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

TNE coordination and TNE market information responsiveness – The coordination efforts between the different missions are effective in terms of the responsiveness of the organisation to customers' needs (Kohli and Jaworski, 1990). TNE coordination, according to this context, relies on the efforts applied by university employees to fulfil the needs of international students (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al. 2009; Jules, 2018). The lack of conflict among TNE's employees supports the increase of responses to the flow of market information (He and Hutson, 2018; Rumbley and Altbach, 2015). Therefore, TNE coordination has an influence on TNE market information responsiveness.

H1c: If TNE is well-coordinated, the responsiveness to TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

3.3.2. University international ranking position and TNE market orientation

The university international ranking position factor is considered as very relevant to the TNE perspective. Universities with more than half a century of experience are most likely to dominate the international market due to their high ranking position compared to new universities established after 1992 (Asaad et al., 2013; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Hazelkorn, 2018). This is explained by the way international ranking measures function, where there is a strong focus on the historical review of a university in addition to postgraduates' career, research, and the percentage of students deciding to pursue further education at the same university based on their satisfaction with the education received (Hoyt and Howell, 2012).

Healey (2018) noted that transnational experience, which reflects the long history of universities involved in higher education exporting, does not have a positive link with EMO. This is consistent with the findings of Cadogan et al. (2012) and Asaad et al. (2015) on export experience. TNE delivered by well-established and top-ranked universities is not anticipated to have high TNE market orientation, owing to the prestige of these universities and their focus on maximising international students' enrolment. Meanwhile, new universities with lower ranking positions are using aggressive marketing activities to increase their TNE market share (Keay et al., 2014). Additionally, new universities, which are less prestigious, pursue and favour a market-driven model of TNE that aligns with the needs of higher education and addresses economic and social factors related to export of higher education.

According to Asaad et al. (2013), new universities with a low-ranking position need to adopt a business approach and apply marketing strategies such as 'market orientation' properly (Bobe and Kober, 2015). As most well-known universities for global market expansion (TNE) are the new higher education institutions, especially in those countries that prioritise the identity of the university's home country over the ranking position of the university (Hazelkorn, 2018).

University international ranking position and TNE market information generation – The interaction of students or competitors with university international ranking position (Ghobehei et al., 2019; Hazelkorn, 2011; Ghobehei et al., 2019) permits a university to access and obtain crucial information reflected by its ranking position (Healey, 2018). Ranking position authorises universities to measure their performance through students' reaction and perception. Hence, a university's international ranking position provides an advanced understanding of its standing relative to other universities' position (Bobe and Kober, 2015; Bastedo and Bowman, 2010). The knowledge gained enables universities to effectively respond to ranking position matters (Hazelkorn, 2011). Therefore, the university's international ranking position can positively impact TNE market information generation.

H2a: If a university's international position is top ranked, the generation of TNE market information in the university will be enhanced.

University international ranking position and TNE market information dissemination – Practicing information dissemination in a university requires several departments to unite to enhance every function of the university. Therefore, a spirit of cooperation develops among the different university departments, fostering trust and dependence while receiving feedback on the ranking of the university (Brankovic et al., 2018; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Hazelkorn, 2011). University international ranking position is suggested to be of great support for TNE market dissemination. The vast volume of markets reflecting their opinions on rankings lists allows university managers to be open to different opinions and different thoughts (Hazelkorn, 2018). Thus, the university's international ranking has a link with TNE market information dissemination.

H2b: If a university's international position is top ranked, the dissemination of TNE market information in the university will be enhanced.

University international ranking position and TNE market information responsiveness – The information gained from a university's international ranking position determines its points of strength or weakness and identifies competitors (Asaad et al., 2013; Espeland and Sauder, 2016; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Hazelkorn, 2011). The literature is clear about how highly responsive institutions need to keep an eye on their competitors' behaviours (Cadogan et al., 2012). By closely monitoring competitors' ranking, a university can be aware of their strategic

moves and investigate them to understand the reasons for their ranking position improvement or otherwise. Thus, it can develop the necessary strategies to enhance its reaction to competitors' challenges (Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016; Healey, 2018). Therefore, a university's international ranking position can be positively associated with TNE market information responsiveness.

H2c: If a university's international position is top ranked, the responsiveness to TNE market information in the university will be enhanced.

3.3.3. Developed country higher education image perception and TNE market orientation

Developed country higher education image encompasses a concept that relies on projecting the image of the product-country. This image reflects the perception of managers, academics, and students regarding a developed country, such as the UK (Baker and Ballington, 2011; Firmansyah et al., 2023). Developed countries distinguish themselves through their product-country image, which impacts stakeholders' evaluation of a particular product or service, especially if they are intangible services like higher education (Hailat et al., 2019; Watkins and Gonzenbach, 2013; Williams and Omar, 2014).

With the importance of product-country image as an influencer on the appraisal of international students or decision-makers, marketing managers need to ensure the image projected about the country and formulate strategies for TNE based on marketing (Baker and Ballington, 2011; Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka, 2015b). Therefore, the perception of marketing managers towards product-country image impacts TNE marketing applications such as TNE market orientation.

Moreover, country image has the power to expand globally, making entry to new overseas markets either easier or more difficult. The image of a country helps in the marketing activities of exporting a product or service (Rowley and Skipper, 2021; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Jimenez-Castillo et al., 2013). Some countries practice TNE market orientation more than others, owing to the country's higher education image (Acikdilli, 2015; Zhou and Wu, 2016). The higher education image of a developed country such as the UK is considered highly favourable compared to Australia or Canada (Watkins and Gonzenbach, 2013); this illustrates the extent of effort that UK higher education marketing managers are putting in. Thus, the perception of

marketing managers in developed countries impacts decision-making regarding entering or expanding their TNE activities.

Developed country higher education image perception and TNE market information generation – International students seek higher education in developed countries (Assad et al. 2015; Foroudi et al., 2019) based on the image of those countries and their potential impact on students' careers. Developed country higher education image perception can help universities in their plans to obtain effective market information overseas (Hailat et al., 2019; Watkins and Gonzenbach, 2013). Literature mentions that institutions can leverage their perceived image to ensure critical use of customers' opinions (Baker and Ballington, 2011; Zhou and Wu, 2016). These perceived images can increase the growth and development of an institution's information generation. Thus, developed country higher education image perception might have a positive link with TNE market information generation.

H3a: If the higher education image of a developed country is positively perceived by managers, the generation of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

Developed country higher education image perception and TNE market information dissemination – Developed country higher education image perception can increase the impact of TNE market information dissemination, where intelligence dissemination needs an open and democratic functional environment in terms of communication, acceptance, and application of new ideas and concepts (Assad et al. 2015; Foroudi et al., 2019; Ghobehei et al., 2019). A well-perceived image of an institution reflects a passion of integrity, enhancing communication channels and instilling confidence in making related topics subject to discussion among employees (Amaia et al., 2018). Asaad et al. (2015) agree that institutions with a highly positive image perception can foster an internal organisational culture with greater integration and cooperation between departments. Therefore, it is anticipated that developed country higher education image perception has a link with TNE market information dissemination.

H3b: If the higher education image of developed country is positively perceived by managers, the dissemination of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

Developed country higher education image perception and TNE market information responsiveness – Developed country higher education image perception often influence its universities' perception, which reflects on potential outcomes (Assad et al. 2015; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Koris et al., 2015). With the assistance of the country image, universities in a nation with a highly perceived country image can easily market themselves (Amaia et al., 2018; Watkins and Gonzenbach, 2013). Therefore, this support allows managers more confidence to participate in international fairs, meet students, obtain new opportunities with other educational organisation overseas (Palfreyman and Tapper, 2016). Hence, developed country higher education image perception has a link to TNE market information responsiveness.

H3c: If the higher education image of a developed country is positively perceived by managers, the responsiveness to TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

3.3.4. University international ranking position and developed country higher education image perception

In every field, there is a successful organisation whose performance influences the perception of customers regarding its country's image (Bastedo and Bowman, 2010). The positive or negative attitude of customers towards a product or service of a country has the special power to maintain or change the perception that customers hold about the image of that country (Acikdilli, 2015; Bastedo and Bowman, 2010; Cadogan, 2012).

According to Cooley and Snyder (2015), the organisation's image contributes to impacting the product or service image of a country (Ghobehei et al., 2019). Thereby, the image of universities influences the higher education image of that country. Also, the ranking position of the university reflects its performance (Jimenez-Castillo et al., 2013); operationalised universities' image is built upon their ranking position. Well-established universities' ranking position develops good perception about their country image (Ghobehei et al., 2019). Furthermore, leaders, academics, and students have high confidence that universities they belong to are highly ranked, which contributes to a positive perception and creates a good image of the university's country (Hoyt and Howell, 2012; Hazekorn, 2011). Hence, university international ranking position influences the higher education image of a developed country.

H4: If a university's international position is highly ranked, the higher education image of a developed country will be enhanced.

3.4. OUTCOMES OF TNE MARKET ORIENTATION

3.4.1. TNE market orientation and higher education international reputation

Market orientation in literature has a positive influence on the international reputation of an organisation (Bastedo and Bowman, 2010; Wilkins and Huisman 2015). The international reputation of an organisation would be enhanced by market orientation, where the market can be highly influenced by the organisation applying market orientation (Wilkins et al., 2012b; Yudkevich et al., 2016). Continuous interaction with the market allows the organisation to gain more favourable word-of-mouth that supports its reputation (Foroudi et al., 2017). Several researchers supported the perception of marketing communication as a means to achieve a strong reputation (Javanmard and Hasani, 2017). Foroudi et al. (2019c) noted that higher education reputation is enhanced by effective marketing communication from the majority of universities in a country. Likewise, Lozano et al. (2018) argue that the way to build a strong reputation is through engagement in strategic marketing activities that primarily rely on market orientation. Therefore, universities with effective market orientation activities can increase international higher education reputation.

TNE market information generation and higher education international reputation – Through previous studies, researchers tended to demonstrate a significant positive correlation between export organisations employing an increased level of both customer orientation and reputation outcomes (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012; Thatcher et al., 2016; Wilkins and Huisman 2015). Universities using intelligence generation also focus considerably on international student orientation (Feldman and Sandoval, 2018). Studies such as Guilbault (2016), Miotto et al. (2020), and Wilkins et al. (2012) have shown that the practice of information generation can support institutions in increasing consumer-oriented reputation (Foroudi et al., 2019). To develop and retain an international reputation within a higher education context, universities must closely engage with their potential international students through market intelligence (Asaad et al., 2015). This practice helps universities receive feedback from international students about the quality of service (Wilkins et al., 2012b; Yudkevich et al., 2016). Thus, TNE market information generation contributes to higher education international reputation.

H5a: If generation of TNE market information is enhanced, the higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.

TNE market information dissemination and higher education international reputation – In the context of information dissemination, an increased level of cross-functional information sharing can enhance institutions' ability to manage organisation-wide reputation (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012; Thatcher et al., 2016). Global development fosters a competitive environment; sharing market information throughout the entire organisation has been deemed highly significant for preparing to face and adapt to market changes (Wilkins et al., 2012a). The continuous movement and circulation of market intelligence (internal exchange of information) among the different departments of a university may develop trust and increased levels of dependence between all operational departments (Miotto et al., 2020; Thatcher et al., 2016). Based on this information, well-shared TNE market information can contribute to a positive higher education international reputation.

H5b: If dissemination of TNE market information is well enhanced, the higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.

TNE market information responsiveness and higher education international reputation – The responsiveness of universities towards their challenges contributes to the growth of higher education international reputation (Thatcher et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2018). Institutions, according to the literature, that proactively address new challenges from competitors or customers' needs are more capable of identifying their own weaknesses and strengths (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012). Several studies indicate how a responsive organisation can become internationally reputable (Asaad, 2015; Feldman and Sandoval, 2018; Foroudi et al., 2019). Managing to deliver advanced services allows the organisation to maintain customers satisfaction and ensure its reputation objectively (Espeland and Sauder, 2016; Watkins and Gonzenbach, 2013). Therefore, TNE market information responsiveness can contribute to higher education international reputation.

H5c: If responsiveness to TNE market information is well enhanced, the higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.

3.4.2. TNE market orientation and TNE business performance

Several researchers (Foroudi et al., 2016a; Hailat et al., 2019; Wilkins and Huisman, 2021) have determined that many characteristics are fundamental for the export of higher education, including factors that impact TNE business performance such as TNE market awareness, TNE planning, and controlling and pursuing the business of TNE. Researchers consider these activities as related to an organisation's export market orientation (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2016). Organisations with effective connections to customers and ability to detect customers' expectations will satisfy their needs and avoid competition (Mac and Evangelist, 2016; Makri et al., 2017).

The study of Qu (2009) provides significant evidence of the positive connection between market orientation and the business performance of university activities. In the realm of export literature, the need for active information generation is increasing, especially with the diversification of market needs and competitors' competencies (He and Wei, 2011; Mac and Evangelist, 2016). However, collecting information related to customers or competitors overseas is not easy (Asaad et al., 2015). TNE market orientation activities enable managers involved in TNE to familiarise themselves with market needs, competitor strategies, and opportunities to address market challenges (Kleibert, 2023). Therefore, with the enhancement of TNE market orientation, universities would be able to expand in the TNE market (increasing enrolment with a larger volume of international students under different TNE programmes). Given that TNE market orientation encompasses a range of effective activities controlled by managers' decisions, the evaluation and satisfaction of managers towards TNE business performance are more effective with the application of market orientation theory.

TNE market information generation and TNE business performance – As the literature shows (Chung, 2012; Hailat et al., 2019; Palfreyman and Tapper, 2016; Mac and Evangelist, 2016), market information is significantly linked to institutions' capability to choose and proceed with marketing strategies, and is effective in increasing performance (He and Wei, 2011), while other researchers have argued that market information generation has limited or negligible influence on export business performance (Murray et al., 2007; Kleibert, 2023). The fact that an organisation is interested in collecting information relevant to customers' needs or challenges of competitors helps managers to target the right aspects that would allow for more expansion of the business. Therefore, methods used by organisations for information

generation support the increase of business performance possibilities (Wilkins and Huisman, 2021). Thus, TNE market information generation can influence TNE business performance.

H6a: If generation of TNE market information is well-enhanced, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed.

TNE market information dissemination and TNE business performance – The process of sharing export market information affects competitors and customers through the clear image that top managers receive via the information-sharing platform created between employees (Chung, 2012; Hailat et al., 2019; Mac and Evangelist, 2016; Palfreyman and Tapper, 2016). In return, an effective increase in information is firmly owed to the influence of collaborative experience shared between the institution's individuals, units, and departments. Bunce (2017) notes that the ease and rapid practice of market information dissemination help enhance strategic insights, where decisions-making on TNE activities becomes more effective. In contrast, if there are difficulties in practicing TNE market information dissemination within a university, then this can shrink and minimise opportunities for effective strategic decision-making or dealing with unfamiliar situations (Hailat et al., 2019). Therefore, TNE market information dissemination can influence TNE business performance.

H6b: If dissemination of TNE market information is enhanced, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed.

TNE market information responsiveness and TNE business performance – The above two activities of market orientation are the basis that enable a university to respond effectively to the current and future customers' needs, hence, to determine and adjust to global market easily (Chung, 2012; Kleibert, 2023). Market information responsiveness activity has suggested an effective and powerful influence on export business performance (Mac and Evangelist, 2016; Palfreyman and Tapper, 2016). Institutions with a motive to increase performance prioritise greatly the responsiveness which covers the implementation of related customer-focused sale strategies (Chung, 2012; Hailat et al., 2019). Responsiveness activity is expected to support the university's operational strategies tasks including customers' segmentation by determining and tackling highly profitable customers, creating effective networking, and successful distribution of university resources (He and Wei, 2011; Warwick, 2014). Thus, TNE market information responsiveness can influence TNE business performance.

H6c: If responsiveness to TNE market information is well enhanced, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed.

3.4.3. Higher education international reputation and TNE business performance

Kumar et al. (2011) determined a positive relationship among reputation and business performance. Gouvea et al. (2013), in line with this concept, illustrated that organisation revenues may increase owing to its positive reputation. In the higher education context, prestige and reputation concepts are very important as the reputation of universities can impact market segment volume (Guilbault, 2018). Universities that tend to cover international markets require a good reputation, hence, higher education programmes are subject to reputation appraisal, especially from international students (Molesworth et al., 2011; Vangelis et al., 2018). The international reputation of universities enables international students to evaluate universities' programmes pre-enrolment (Larsen, 2016). Thus, higher education international reputation seems to be significant in the international students' process of choosing a university (Yu et al., 2018). This fact has positive influence on TNE business performance through the increase of enrolment volume within TNE programmes that enhance the market share and revenue of the university. Therefore, favourable higher education international reputation influences TNE business performance.

H7: If higher education international reputation is guaranteed, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed as well.

3.5. SUMMARY

This study has significant implications for university by quantifying the importance of TNE market orientation in achieving growth objectives. The examination of this research provides a comprehensive approach to test the relationship between reputation and business performance resulting from TNE market orientation. This chapter reviews the literature on TNE market orientation to integrate insights from various perspectives and build the conceptual framework presented in Figure 3.1. The literature explores the correlation among TNE market orientation, its antecedents, and outcomes, while developed hypotheses are presented in Table 3.1 and clarified in Figure 3.1. Both the conceptual research framework and the hypotheses illustrate the range of connections among the eight constructs.

The limited availability of theoretical sources directly related to TNE market orientation necessitates reviewing the literature on export market orientation, which has already been explored. The support provided by the related literary covered many important guidelines and directions that clarify the prior compatibility of the relationship logic between constructs in this study. From the literature review, 17 hypotheses were developed. The following chapter details the research methodology to a standard that can expand scales for the conceptual framework and examine the suggested model.

Table 3.1: Research hypotheses list based on research questions

Hypotheses	
RQ 1: How do universities in the UK perceive and practice TNE activities?	
RQ 2: What are the elements that shape TNE market orientation in the UK?	
Research Question 3: What are the key factors that influence TNE market orientation in the UK?	
H1a	If TNE is well-coordinated, the generation of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.
H1b	If TNE is well-coordinated, the dissemination of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.
H1c	If TNE is well-coordinated, the responsiveness to TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.
H2a	If the university's international position is top ranked, the generation of TNE market information in the university will be enhanced.
H2b	If the university's international position is top ranked, the dissemination of TNE market information in the university will be enhanced.
H2c	If the university's international position is top ranked, the responsiveness to TNE market information in the university will be enhanced.
H3a	If the higher education image of the developed country is positively perceived by managers, the generation of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.
H3b	If the higher education image of the developed country is positively perceived by managers, the dissemination of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.
H3c	If the higher education image of the developed country is positively perceived by managers, the responsiveness to TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.
H4	If the university's international position is highly ranked, the higher education image of the developed country will be enhanced.
Research question 4: What are the consequences/benefits of TNE market orientation according to UK universities?	
H5a	If generation of TNE market information is enhanced, the higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.
H5b	If dissemination of TNE market information is enhanced, the higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.
H5c	If responsiveness to TNE market information is enhanced, the higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.
H6a	If generation of TNE market information is enhanced, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed.
H6b	If dissemination of TNE market information is enhanced, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed.
H6c	If responsiveness to TNE market information is enhanced, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed.

H7

If higher education international reputation is guaranteed, the TNE business performance will be guaranteed as well.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND METHODS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter explains the purpose and rationale for the research methodology and selected methods for this thesis by elucidating and justifying the process used to examine the suggested hypotheses and conceptual framework developed in the previous chapter. In order to find answers to the research questions and ensure the proposed model's validation, section 4.2 will explain the research methodology by describing the reasons behind its selection and by determining possible patterns in the data. Section 4.6 discusses the survey as the main method of research, where a self-administrated questionnaire with a random sampling technique was used, while section 4.7 discusses the seven-point Likert scale questionnaire design. Section 4.8 presents the adopted data analysis in two stages. The first stage is the confirmatory factor analysis to evaluate the measurement properties related to the validity of existing scales using SPSS techniques. The second stage is the structural equation modelling to examine all hypotheses and avoid potential links between measurements and structural models using AMOS techniques. Section 4.9 outlines the primary ethical issues. Finally, section 4.10 summarises this chapter.

4.2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY JUSTIFICATION

The marketing paradigm is very important (Hunt, 1990; Foroudi, 2019b; 2020; Morgan, 1980), as it allows the researcher to define a range of underlying assumptions that facilitate the delivery of a comprehensive understanding of the subject, in addition to arriving at valid and reliable findings.

Denzin and Lincoln (2017) argue that paradigms are interrelated systems encompassing assumptions of ontology, epistemology, and methodology. There are several ways to classify the paradigm concept. The ontological perspective concerns the researcher's view of the form and nature of social reality (Denzin and Lincoln, 2017). The epistemological perspective pertains to the process used to acquire knowledge, as well as the links between the phenomena studied, such as sources, nature, and limits of knowledge (Denzin and Lincoln, 2017; Harvey and Alston, 2011). The methodological perspective relates to the techniques employed by a researcher to establish certainty; this paradigm is relevant to a study's questions and techniques to generate and advocate experimental evidence (Creswell, 2013; Denzin and Lincoln, 2017).

When deciding on one of the paradigms to conduct an accurate investigation, researchers must consider the nature of research questions and objectives. Deshpande (1983) encourages marketing researchers to focus on the idealism and the positivism paradigms (generation and verification of theory) with the purpose of preventing method bias, which is the outcome of employing a single paradigm. The current study relies on positivism and incorporates some features of realism, including the existence of social facts, as paradigms should not be treated as mutually exclusive (Braman, 2015) (Table 4.1 describes these paradigms). The generation of theory permits a development of several propositions tested later by the researcher through the implementation of verification theory using quantitative methods.

The adaptation of both paradigms by the researcher has two significant effects. The first effect reflects the support offered to determine a developed range of scales that can help measure the constructs of marketing. The idealism paradigm, at the start of this research, focuses on a qualitative method (i.e., adapting interviews and focus groups) to determine the factors that influence TNE market orientation and whether a TNE market orientation can enhance TNE business performance. What are the main influences of TNE market orientation as a strategy for exporting higher education and as a differentiator for building TNE business? The researcher includes the qualitative study to acquire preparatory insights for research problems, creating the right scale to measure TNE market orientation, which can help later to examine theories and hypotheses.

Table 4.1: Names of alternative paradigms

Interpretive	Positivist
Qualitative	Quantitative
Subjectivist	Objectivist
Humanistic	Scientific
Revolutionist	Traditionalist
Phenomenological	Experimentalist

Source: Creswell (2013, p. 126).

The second effect reflects the improvement of marketing research reliability, validity, and generalisability (Bryman, 2016; Creswell, 2013) through the involvement of a positivist

paradigm as a tool to examine the model (Cohen et al., 2011), and the hypotheses, in addition to their causative relevance (Shiu et al., 2009). The quantitative methodology (hypothetico-deductive) was employed to perform the current research; the use of the qualitative study (inductive) was imposed due to the lack of appropriate existing scales to measure TNE market orientation as discovered in the literature. For example, Asaad et al. (2015) illustrate that the EMO in higher education still needs much investigation to be well explored, and its measurement was not conducted in an objective manner.

To test the concept of TNE market orientation as a root of university business expansion (Asaad et al., 2015) and higher education international reputation (Molesworth et al., 2011; Vangelis et al., 2018), a quantitative method is more appropriate compared to qualitative method (Melewar, 2013), as it is more suitable for theory testing rather than the generation of theory (Brayman, 2016) (Table 4.2 reflects the differences among qualitative and quantitative approaches).

Table 4.2: Qualitative approach versus quantitative approach (comparison)

	Qualitative Study	Quantitative Study
Aim	Inductive: discovery plus process oriented Process Meaning Context Detecting unanticipated events, conditions, and influences Theory inductive development	Deductive: verification plus consequence oriented Creating links among variables Precise comparison and measurement for variables Interface from sample to population
Research questions	Process questions Why and how Context (holistic) Meaning Causality (physical) Conceptual framework includes hypothesis	Variance questions Proposition truth Degree or amount Presence or absence Correlation Causality (factual) Hypothesis testing
METHODS OF RESEARCH		

Relationship	Utilise influence to understand (research as part of process)	Reduction/Objectivity of influence (research as an extraneous variable)
Sampling	Purposeful sampling	Establishing valid comparisons Probability sampling
Data collection	Strategies' inductive development Measures seek to be subjective Adapting to situation Collection of visual or textual material	Instruments' prior development Measures seek to be objective Standardisation Measurement/testing- quantitative/categorical
Data analysis	Textual analysis (memos, connecting, coding) Narrative approaches Grounded theory	Numerical descriptive analysis (correlation, statistics) Population variables estimation Testing statistical hypothesis Conversion of textual data into categories or numbers
Validity/Reliability	Valid Self as instrument (the evaluator and the data are close)	Reliable Technology as instrument
Generalisability	Ungeneralisable Case oriented The perspective of insider	Generalisable Population oriented The perspective of outsider

Source: Cohen (2011, p. 190).

4.3. RESEARCH APPROACH SELECTION

To develop additional understanding concerning the problem identified in Chapter 1, the approach of pluralism research is the best fit (Mingers et al., 2013). Mingers (2013) states, “the different research methods (especially from different paradigms) focus on different aspects of reality and therefore a richer understanding of a research together in a single piece of research or research program. Topic will be gained by combining several methods together in a single piece of research or research program” (p. 794). Some researchers, such as Miles et al. (2013), believe that disregarding the possible contribution of methods linked to non-positivist approaches (such as in-depth interviews) might reduce the understanding of researchers who adapt the approach of positivism.

The use of several research methods, such as interviews, focus groups, and questionnaires, maximises the understanding of the phenomenon related to the study as well as producing

unprecedented insights (Creswell, 2013; Palmer, 2011). In relation to the development of the research methodology, and the perceived legitimacy of qualitative and quantitative research, literature in human and social sciences progressively uses mixed-method approaches to generate and test quantitative and qualitative data (Foroudi et al., 2014). This approach, according to Creswell (2013), involves “a quantitative study based on testing a theory in an experiment with a small qualitative interview component in the data collection phase” (p. 176).

To collect data for this research, mixed methods will be used, as mixed methods have shown effective results in relation to social science (Creswell, 2013; Foroudi et al., 2016b). According to Creswell (2013), mixed methods research is a technique that merges both qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis in one study. Together, the qualitative and quantitative approaches were selected consecutively to confirm, corroborate, or cross-validate findings at a single stage in the study process.

The qualitative data analysis in this study is characterised by including the method of content analysis. Two schemes were identified by Bryman (2015) to explain the merging of quantitative and qualitative research, relying on content analysis. One of the schemes is the significant scheme, which was created by Greene et al. (1989) in the assessment research context, where every article is coded in a process of a primary and secondary rationale (Bryman, 2015). The significant scheme combines quantitative with qualitative research through several justifications (Bryman and Bell, 2015) (Table 4.4).

Bryman (2015) argues that “the advantage of the Greene et al. (1989) scheme is its parsimony, in that it boils down the possible reasons for conducting multi-strategy research to just five reasons, although the authors’ analysis revealed that initiation was uncommon” (p. 105). In mixed methods, qualitative research is necessary to understand those social complex phenomena that contribute to the development of themes by a researcher based on the points of view of respondents (Foroudi et al., 2021a), while the quantitative research handles the large quantity of data for the purposes of generalisation. This method permits only the coding of primary and secondary data (Foroudi et al., 2021a). To address this disadvantage, a very detailed scheme was designed.

The approach used displays a similar example to Creswell (2013), which concentrates on quantitative research relying on testing a theory; however, a few qualitative interviews are

incorporated in the data collection phase (Foroudi et al., 2021a). The mixed methods procedures are illustrated in Figure 4.1.

In order to enhance the study’s validity, an inductive approach was employed prior to the fundamental survey, and the collection techniques of qualitative data were used to formulate hypotheses, purify measures, and construct the questionnaire (Bryman, 2015). Some researchers (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2013) suggest that in initial stages of primary investigation, it is preferable to apply a qualitative approach with mixed methods. To test the TNE market orientation concept, the quantitative method as the main method is highly suitable compared to qualitative methods (Gupta et al., 2011; Hair et al., 2012). The quantitative method is more suitable for theory examination compared to theory generation (Cohen et al., 2011).

Figure 4.1: Procedures of mixed methods

Source: Creswell (2013); Foroudi et al. (2021d)

According to the positivist point of view indicated above on the mixed research approach, the current study employed qualitative methods through ‘in depth interviews’ with managers

related to TNE in universities and focus groups with student recruitment agents in the UK. In order to legitimise the scales of measurement, the primary survey, a ‘qualitative research’, was applied to acquire significant knowledge regarding TNE market orientation practices in UK universities. Based on the research questions, the appropriate unit to analyse quantitative data in this study is managers related to TNE activities.

To evaluate TNE market orientation, the current study applies the approach of Churchill (1979) to promote mixed items measures for constructs of marketing, and the approach of Hair et al. (2013) to build a range of valid and reliable scales to set a reliable measurement. A very strong relationship is expected to be generated by adopting this approach instead of employing a one-measure item. Referring to the theory of Churchill (1979), qualitative paradigms are involved while in nature it is predominantly quantitative. The measurement scale development is illustrated in Figure 4.2 as a proposal for marketing constructs.

Figure 4.2: The measurement scale development steps

Source: Churchill (1979, p. 66); Foroudi et al. (2021d)

The primary stage of research design, according to Churchill (1979), relies on exploratory fieldwork. This primary phase will be discussed in the following sections.

4.4. PHASE 1: THE QUALITATIVE ASPECT

The researcher will determine the research questions based on an initial exploratory study. Therefore, this research took the initiative to cover the gap, as no study has produced a reliable and valid scale to measure TNE market orientation, through applying the procedures of Churchill (1979) to develop a suitable scale. The reasons behind the application of an initial exploratory study are to guarantee a good understanding of the study field (Asaad et al., 2015); achieve insights towards TNE market orientation, higher education international reputation, and TNE business performance; understanding the existing area of practice to measure the extent of the related proposed research study; and to gain effective information and understanding of the suggested research questions, produce hypotheses, then purify the questionnaire measures (Churchill, 1979).

A suggestion by previous scholars (Churchill, 1979; Cuomo et al., 2021; Foroudi et al., 2021a), emphasises that those exploratory studies (experience survey) involve “a judgement sample of persons who can offer ideas and insights into the phenomenon” (p. 66). This type of study prefers to commence on a wide scale then shrink it gradually to study development (Saunders et al., 2007). Some techniques, as suggested by Churchill (1979), are utilised to create sample items and contemplate a construct (literature search, exploratory research, focus group, and interview). These techniques are adopted in this study to measure the TNE market orientation construct.

Combining group discussions and in-depth interviews is very beneficial (Palmer, 2011; Ritchie et al., 2013), bringing value to the existing data based on new perspectives (Jerez-Jerez et al., 2021; Ritchie et al., 2013). The generated outcomes (data collection) from interviews and focus groups enrich this study with information and insights to acquire additional data that was not available in the literature review. However, exploratory research does not usually involve huge samples (Malhotra et al., 2017). Therefore, qualitative data were adopted to limit possible weaknesses and create a quantitative study in the form of a questionnaire (Churchill, 1979).

The following section will explain the planning of the qualitative stage, including its management and data interpretation.

4.4.1. Qualitative stage: the planning and management then data interpretation

Conducting this quality study required the researcher to start with grounded theory for testing the data. The coding process of qualitative data analysis was directed by the developed (from literature) conceptual framework. The codes created by the author were based on the understanding of TNE and EMO, including its measures, the antecedents to TNE market orientation, and TNE business performance concept. This created the scope to code and analyse the data. Moreover, codes address each of the research questions, research hypotheses, and problematic areas (Creswell, 2013; Palmer, 2011). The questions and hypotheses were experimentally examined by a careful methodology (Harvey and Alston, 2011).

In the early stages, narrative coding relied on the process of open codes and constructs, which were determined from the literature review. The codes list, according to Miles et al. (2013), must concentrate on “a conceptual framework, list of research questions, hypotheses, problem areas, and/or key variables that the researcher brings to the study” (p. 59). The researcher converted the recorded interviews into transcripts prior the coding stage. The data coding facilitated the search at a level of comparisons to identify those patterns needed for additional search. The data coding process from interview transcripts locates the process in approaches to qualitative analysis (Maxwell, 2012). The descriptive codes helped to organise the collected data, then thematic ideas became visible with the collected data which belonged to similar content (Malhotra et al., 2017; Patton, 2014; Vollero et al., 2020).

The codes were analysed through three coding stages: open coding, axial coding, and selective coding (Brown et al., 2019; Creswell, 2013; Foroudi et al., 2019). The coding of qualitative data was based on Sheppard (2010) and Malhotra et al. (2017). NVivo software (Version 12) was used in this stage of study to administrate data and attain results. Additionally, the NVivo software comprises tools to record, store data, retrieve ideas, link ideas, and explore the interpretation and data patterns (Bryman, 2016). This software’s mission is to assist with qualitative data and contribute to delivering easier, more reliable, accurate, and transparent data for easier analysis (Gupta et al., 2010).

The stage of open codes was categorised and interpreted at prestigious notions, allowing for the emergence of core categories (Foroudi et al., 2016a; 2017a; Hafeez et al., 2016). Then, each transcript was carefully double-checked to detect patterns relevant to the literature. Finding similar or different patterns in transcripts compared to the relevant literature review is the prime

objective of open coding. Applying the open coding to all interview transcripts enabled the researcher to generate a high number of comments and memos, which supported rigorous analysis and helped create the axial code.

The axial coding stage attempts to create contrast and links among the sub-categories and core categories to enhance pattern identification in the interview transcripts. This unique approach does not mislead the data analysis, as it deems the set of open codes all together in a single case (Saldana, 2013). The axial coding procedure reflects a constant comparison process based on similarities and differences found in the open coding stage.

The selective coding (last stage) has a role to merge the arising theory. This approach is considered the highly complicated stage in the analysis of grounded theory. In order to generate a theory that is qualified to suit the data, it is vital to express the incidents carefully (Saldana, 2013). The selective coding, according to Saldana (2013), started during the stage of axial coding through drawing the link between all axial codes.

The factors contributing to form a study, analyse findings, and judge the research quality are validity and reliability (Hafeez et al., 2016). Validity signifies being well-grounded, while reliability signifies the sustainability to specify the data strength, reliability, and validity of research, in addition to improving the evaluation of its findings through the triangulation method. Therefore, triangulation, along with validity and reliability, are related research notions, especially when qualitative methods are used to ascertain truth. The techniques used in this study to increase trustworthiness are presented in Table 4.3. A theoretical sample was used by the researcher instead of the random statistical sample, believing that theoretical sampling, according to Saldana, (2013), can “maximise opportunities for comparing concepts along their properties for the similarities and differences enabling researchers to define categories, to differentiate among them, and to specify their range of variability” (p. 149).

Table 4.3: Meeting the criteria of trustworthiness

Traditional criteria	Trustworthiness criteria	Techniques employed to ensure trustworthiness
Internal validity	Credibility	Quality access (the researcher was provided with an office desk, computer, access to company intranet, email address, freedom of talking to and interviewing anybody, freedom of getting any company documents, including lots of confidential strategic documents.) and extensive engagement in the field. Multiple triangulations Peer debriefing Constant comparison
External validity	Transferability	Detailed description of the research setting Multiple cases and cross-case comparison
Reliability	Dependability	Purposive and theoretical sampling Cases and informant's confidentiality protected Rigorous multiple stages of coding
Objectivity	Confirmability	Separately presenting the exemplar open and axial codes. Word-by-word interview transcription Accurate records of contacts and interviews Writing research journal Carefully keeping notes of observation Regularly keeping notes of emergent theoretical and methodological ideas

Source: Based on Creswell (2013)

4.4.2. Interview

In-depth interviews were conducted with managers related to TNE. The researcher contacted (by emails and phone calls) 15 universities from Scotland, Wales, and England that deliver TNE programmes, to consult them, identifying the right people for this study topic, and to contact them directly about their interest in taking part in this research (Diamantopoulos and Cadogan, 1996; Palmer, 2011; Shiu et al., 2009). The researcher was able to receive contacts and phone numbers from only six universities, while the others refused to participate due to the pressure of the pandemic (Covid-19) or their tight schedules. Therefore, the in-depth interviews were conducted with eight managers from different universities (Table 4.4 shows the interviewees' details).

The pandemic (Covid-19) made face-to-face interviews impossible; therefore, all interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams. Most of the interviews lasted for more than 40 minutes, where the researcher recorded and transcribed verbatim to guarantee reliability (Andriopoulos and Lewis, 2009). The applied technique for in-depth interviews was the semi-structured, personal, direct, and undisguised interview. The researcher designed a question sheet to ensure discussion of all areas of interest (Appendix 4.1).

Table 4.4: The in-depth interviews' details for international marketing managers of universities

Interview date	University location	Interviewee position	Duration (roughly)
International marketing office and transnational education department			
15.05.2020	England	International Marketing Manager	40 min.
18.05.2020	Scotland	International Partnership Development Manager	30 min.
20.05.2020	Wales	Management and Planning Team Manager	45 min.
27.05.2020	England	Senior International Officer	30 min.
08.06.2020	England	Marketing Manager, Senior Lecturer and MBA Courses Director	60 min.
09.06.2020	Scotland	Head of International Office	50 min.
12.06.2020	England	Transnational Education Programmes Development Manager	40 min.
12.06.2020	Wales	Marketing Manager	35 min.

Source: The researcher

4.4.3. The focus groups

Researchers in marketing employ the focus group method for its excellent provenance of qualitative data. The researcher's use of the focus group increases the chances of receiving more insights concerning what managers think about TNE market orientation and its link with higher education international reputation and TNE business performance (Cadogan et al., 2016; He et al., 2018; Miotto et al., 2020).

Four focus groups of 12 women and 9 men were conducted to enhance appropriate group interaction and foster conversation (Creswell, 2014). The participants were selected based on their background in TNE, which contributes to the valid of the study (Smithson, 2000). Additionally, the researcher was able to collect additional information related to the research topic through the various responses (Silverman, 2015).

The focus groups were compromised of student recruitment agents from UK agencies with experience in TNE. Table 4.5 demonstrates the details of the focus group interviews. This method is effective for collecting information, testing assumptions, and promoting understanding of TNE market orientation. Appendix 4.2 illustrates the focus group protocol. Gathering data via this method facilitates the collection of information quickly compared to interviews and more positively benefits from the dynamics of the group.

Table 4.5: The focus group: participants' details

Date of interview	Participants' number	Interviewees' position	Age range	Duration (roughly)
02.06.2020	4	Marketing managers with different levels of experience in student recruitment agencies	30-42	45 min.
03.06.2020	5		27-45	40 min
03.06.2020	6		24-30	55 min
06.06.2020	6		27-36	50 min

Source: The researcher

The process of combining information to develop a questionnaire is described in the next section.

4.5. PHASE 2: RESEARCH INSTRUMENT AND SCALES DEVELOPMENT

The current section aims to create reliable and valid measures for the theoretical constructs via determining the scope of the search based on the literature review and qualitative study. In the initial phase, many items were generated. Among these items, there were equivalents or duplicates that needed to be excluded by the researcher for the sake of brevity. The items generated from the qualitative research were evaluated by several academics, who then removed unnecessary measures to guarantee the accuracy of these items and their relevance to the scale domain. A description of how information was used to build the questionnaire is presented in the next section.

4.5.1. Determining the constructs' domain

The related literature and qualitative study are commonly used to determine the content domain, which represents the primary stage of questionnaire development. The paradigm of Churchill (1979) was followed to promote effective measures by producing several items, drawn from the literature, researchers, and interviews, that reflect the domain constructs. To enhance measurement accuracy, the researcher determined the operational dimensions and definitions of the focal constructs. All constructs with their definitions are presented in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: The definitions for this study constructs

Constructs	Definitions	Major references
Transnational Education Market Orientation	A type of higher education exports where marketing managers must value current and future needs of international students, then fulfil those needs.	Asaad et al. (2013); Cadogan et al. 2009; James and Derrick (2021); Yu et al. (2018)
TNE market information generation	The activities conducted by marketing managers to cover the opportunities or threats that would affect their TNE.	Asaad et al. (2015); Bovill et al. (2015); Keay et al. (2014); Knight (2016); Vangelis et al. (2018)
TNE market information dissemination	The activities conducted by marketing managers to share the collected information on TNE market .	Asaad et al. (2015); Healey (2015); Henderson et al. (2017); Vangelis et al. (2018); Yu et al. (2018)
TNE market information responsiveness	How marketing managers respond to TNE market information that has been generated and disseminated.	Asaad et al. (2015); Healey (2015); Henderson et al. (2017); Vangelis et al. (2018); Yu et al. (2018)
TNE coordination	The good work environment between managers of different departments of the university on TNE matters.	Asaad et al. (2015); Diamantopoulos et al. (2014); Healey 2015; Healy (2020) Feng et al. (2013)
University international ranking position	An assessment of the higher education quality and performance of a university internationally.	Brown and Carasso (2013); Ghobehei et al. (2019); Pucciarelli and Kaplan (2016); Rutter et al. (2017)
Developed country higher education image perception	How stakeholders of a university in a developed country see and evaluate the image of their higher education.	Asaad et al. (2015); Foroudi et al. (2019); Hailat et al. (2019)
Higher education international reputation	The international prestige, deference, and honour reflected by stakeholders of higher education internationally due to its previous experience.	Maisuria and Cole (2017); Menendez and Castilla (2021); Merchant et al. (2014); Priporas and Kamenidou (2011); Thatcher et al. (2016)
TNE business performance	The positive outcome of managers' activities in TNE, reflecting their efficiency to satisfy and achieve the set plans for TNE business growth.	Hailat et al. (2019); Healey (2013); Assad et al. (2015); Murray et al. (2011)

Source: Developed for the current study by the researcher

4.5.2. Items measurement creation

The paradigm of Churchill (1979) includes the generation of items measurements as a second step. DeVillis (2003), in developing the scale, recommends the following advice: “avoiding exceptional length; readability level of each item; double-barrelled items; ambiguous pronoun references; and positive and negatively worded items” (p. 70). The researcher, in order to produce the items measurements, employed a mixture of literature and qualitative research (Churchill, 1979; Foroudi et al., 2021a). The items of every construct represented a multi-item scale and were produced based on the existing literature.

The discovery of new insight not covered in the reviewed literature is the first objective of employing qualitative study. According to Churchill (1979), a multi-item scale must be applied for all constructs. Several researchers (Churchill, 1979; Bryman, 2015; Greene et al., 1989; Saunders, 2007; Shiu et al., 2009) recommend paying attention to the examination of the validity and reliability of measurement used in marketing studies. Some of the scales created by the researcher were based on prior research and illustrate increased validity and reliability. The researcher attempted to avoid redundancy among the measures and lengthening the questionnaire by identifying related items. The constructs along with the number of initial items are presented in Table 4.7.

Table 4.7: All constructs including the total of initial items

Constructs		Total No. of initial item
Transnational education market orientation:		28
TNE market information generation		9
TNE market information dissemination		8
TNE market information Responsiveness		11
TNE market orientation elements	TNE coordination	8
	University international ranking position	6
	Developed country higher education image perception	10
Higher education international reputation		7
TNE business performance		9

Source: The researcher

The early item generation resulted in 68 items: 9 items for the TNE market information generation, 8 items for TNE market information dissemination, 11 items for TNE market information responsiveness, 8 items for TNE coordination, 6 items for university international ranking position, 10 items for developed country higher education image perception, 7 items for higher education international reputation, and 9 items for TNE business performance. Table 4.8 presents the constructs with their measurements from both literature and qualitative studies (for the literature review and interviews, see Chapter 2, 3, and 5).

Table 4.8: The constructs' items and domain in extant literature

Construct	Measurement items	Major references
TNE market information generation		
	Our university conducts regular surveys to evaluate international students' attitude about the quality of our transnational education.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2010)
	Our continuous contact with international students aims to quickly spot issues related to transnational education programmes.	Asaad et al. (2015); and qualitative study
	Our university receives a lot of market information regarding transnational education trends (e.g., economic, technology).	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al., (1999); Cadogan et al. (2012)
	Our relationship with different higher education organisations fulfils our needs for transnational education market information.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (2012)
	We monitor the diverse needs of international students via participating in international fairs worldwide.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al., (1999); Casidy (2014); and qualitative study
	Our university keeps up to date about transnational education activities of our competitors in markets where we operate.	Asaad et al. (2015); Casidy (2014); Yu et al. (2018)
	Our international office conducts secondary research about transnational education market trends (e.g., economic, political) in attractive markets.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); and qualitative study
	Our university evaluates the interest of international students concerning the transnational education programmes trends.	Asaad et al. (2015); Casidy (2014); Yu et al. (2018)
	We regularly study the effect of possible changes (e.g., regulation, technology) on transnational education in markets where we operate.	Qualitative study
TNE market information dissemination		
	Our university holds regular meetings between heads of its different departments to discuss transnational education's issues.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); Casidy (2014); Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2010)

Our university disseminates information concerning our transnational education market through its portal.	Qualitative study
The information we receive from international students about transnational education programmes is transferred to other departments to act upon.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2010)
Our international office communicates well with our transnational education's partners, making us more familiar with transnational education markets where we operate.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); and qualitative study
Our personnel exchange information daily about the university activities in the transnational education market (e.g., new partners or programmes)	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); Yu et al. (2018)
Regular reports are raised to the Deans/heads of our schools/faculties, summarising information related to transnational education activities.	Asaad et al. (2015); Casidy (2014); Yu et al. (2018)
Our transnational education competitors' activities are discussed frequently between the heads of different departments in our university.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); Casidy (2014); Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2010)
Our international office advises faculties/schools about international students' needs before designing new transnational education programmes or courses.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (2012)
TNE market information responsiveness	
Our university develops transnational education programmes and courses based on international student market trends.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (2012)
Our university highly supports the transnational education students (e.g., gives access to e-library and Turnitin, orientating students for UK academic skills).	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); Casidy (2014); Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2010)
Our university supplies understandable, clear, and accurate information to transnational education students.	Asaad et al. (2015); Casidy (2014); Yu et al. (2018)
Our university takes the initiative to solve matters related to our transnational education students' satisfaction.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); qualitative study
Our university interventions towards changes in the fee structure of our transnational education competitors are not quick.	Asaad et al., (2015); Cadogan et al., (1999); qualitative study
Our university adapts very quickly to important changes related to our transnational education's environment (e.g., economic, political).	Asaad et al. (2015); Casidy (2014); Yu et al. (2018)
Our university responds to threats of transnational education competitors very quickly.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al., (1999); Yu et al. (2018)

Our university's transnational education programmes are motivated by internal interests rather than market needs.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al., (1999)
All our university departments contribute to develop marketing strategy to increase the transnational education students' enrolment.	Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (2012)
Our university neglects some of our transnational education students' complaints.	Asaad et al. (2015); Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2010)
Our transnational education programmes' quality is reviewed periodically to control international students' satisfaction.	Asaad et al., (2015); Cadogan et al., (1999); Cadogan et al. (2012); qualitative study

TNE coordination	
Our university's departments work collectively as a team to achieve our transnational education objectives.	Asaad (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999); He and Hutson (2018); the qualitative study
Our university's heads are not all contributing to increase transnational education students' enrolment.	Qualitative study
Our international office department receives support in transnational education activities from several key players in the university.	Diamantopoulos et al. (2014); Morgan et al. (2012); Rumbley and Altbach (2015); qualitative study
Our international office personnel share transnational education information with departments in our faculties/schools.	Asaad (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999), and the qualitative study
Our university experiences less departmental conflicts.	Qualitative study
All our schools/faculties' departments contribute to the international strategy related to transnational education.	Hailat et al. (2019); Larsen (2016); Williams (2017)
The working relationship between the international office's head and other departments' heads including transnational education's partners, is very strong.	Cadogan et al. (1999); Diamantopoulos et al. (2014); Healey (2020)
Our university solves conflicts and issues related to transnational education activities via group problem-solving and communication.	Asaad (2015); Cadogan et al. (1999), and the qualitative study
University international ranking position	
Academic quality indicators in university:	
Teaching quality	Bastedo and Bowman (2010); Ghobehei et al. (2019) Qualitative study

Research quality	Pucciarelli and Kaplan (2016); Hazelkorn (2018); and qualitative study
Graduation rates	Pucciarelli and Kaplan (2016); Hazelkorn (2018); and qualitative study
Student/staff ratio	Bastedo and Bowman (2010); Bobe and Kober (2015); Ghobehei et al. (2019); Qualitative study
Entry standards	Bobe and Kober (2015); Pucciarelli and Kaplan (2016); Hazelkorn (2018); and qualitative study
Graduation prospects	Bastedo and Bowman (2010); Hazelkorn (2018); Ghobehei et al. (2019); Qualitative study
Developed country higher education image perception	
The perceived UK higher education image characterised by:	
Positive view from employers towards graduates	Asaad et al. (2015); Baker and Ballington (2011); qualitative study
Excellence guiding icons	Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); Zhou and Wu (2016) Qualitative study
Effective student support system	Qualitative study
High course quality	Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); Baker and Ballington (2011)
Feasible tuition fees	Asaad et al. (2015); Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); Baker and Ballington (2011); qualitative study
Low education standard	Amaia et al. (2018); Baker and Ballington (2011)
Good teaching staff quality	Qualitative study
Allocating high resource level for research	Baker and Ballington (2011); Wu and Naidoo (2016)
Degrees recognised internationally	Qualitative study

Increased rate of employment for graduates	Hemsley-Brown et al. (2016); and qualitative study
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Higher education international reputation	
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The students of UK transnational education receive education and services as they were promised before enrolment.	Espeland and Sauder (2016); Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); and Qualitative study
UK higher education's international reputation is better than other countries.	Asaad et al. (2015); Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); and qualitative study
The reputation of UK higher education is internationally recognised.	Foroudi et al. (2014); Thatcher et al. (2016); Wilkins et al. (2012)
UK higher education offers high standards of education worldwide.	Asaad et al. (2015); Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); Yu et al. (2018); qualitative study
UK higher education has powerful brand names recognised worldwide.	Qualitative study
The UK higher education degree is reputable internationally.	Thatcher et al. (2016); Thatcher et al. (2016)
The UK universities deliver high quality courses internationally.	Espeland and Sauder (2016); Yu et al. (2018)

Transnational education business performance	
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The level of satisfaction between transnational education students.	Ahimbisibwe et al. (2013); Chung (2012); qualitative study
The enrolment volume of transnational education students.	Hailat et al. (2019); Chung (2012)
The percentage of transnational education revenues compared to total revenues of the university.	Qualitative study
The market share of transnational education students' enrolment compared to other UK universities.	Racela and Thoumrungroje (2014); Hailat et al. (2019); Chung (2012)
The number of transnational education students enrolled due to alumni.	Ahimbisibwe et al. (2013); Cadogan et al. (2016) Chung (2012); and qualitative study

The satisfaction of managers with the volume of transnational education students' enrolment.	Palfreyman and Tapper (2016); Qualitative study
The satisfaction of managers with the university market share based on the enrolment volume of transnational education students.	He and Wei (2011); Qualitative study
The target volume of transnational education students' enrolment by managers.	Qualitative study
The target market share of transnational education students' enrolment by managers.	Murray et al. (2007); Terho et al. (2015); qualitative study

Source: Developed for the current study by the researcher

4.5.3. Purifying the measurement scales

Purification of the measurement scales is the third step in the paradigm of Churchill (1979) for superior development. The purification of measures calculation is considered approximately relevant to the adopted measurement model. Hair et al. (2012) declared that validity, by its nature, is “the degree to which what the researcher was trying to measure was actually measured” (p. 227). The researcher conducted two types of validity (content validity and face validity) for the preliminary stage prior to starting the main survey. These types of validity are subjective in nature and help indicate the adequacy of the questionnaire.

To evaluate the items' validity developed for this study's questionnaire, the researcher discussed the first version with six personnel from the international partnership development department at West of Scotland Business School, as they are experienced in this study topic (Lund, 2012). Checking the clarity of the coding and commenting on the items' suitability were the main purposes for contacting them. Therefore, the results of this procedure provide valuable judgments from experienced individuals in the researched topic (Green et al., 1989). The questionnaire was then examined by three lecturers after amendments, for face validity or the effectiveness of item measures in relation to the researched topic. The researcher asked lecturers to answer the questionnaire and express their views on whether the questionnaire measured the intended wording, construct, layout, and ease of completion.

The premier measurement for effective EMO (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2012; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; Harris, 2020; Healey, 2013; Vangelis et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018) recognises the importance EMO in higher education as supportive and beneficial for universities' business performance in TNE. However, most experts and academics commented on two items from the developed country higher education image perception construct: 'excellent guiding icons' and 'low education standard'. They described them as items that do not represent. Therefore, both items were excluded from the questionnaire.

Also, academics and marketing managers commented on the following items 'Our university disseminates information concerning our TNE market through its portal'; 'University position concerning the numbers of TNE partners compared to other UK universities'; 'Target of managers in our university concerning the total of TNE students' enrolment'; and 'Managers' satisfaction with the university position based on the enrolment volume of TNE students' as unclear and not easy to understand. The researcher changed them to 'We disseminate information between personnel on TNE markets using the university portal'; 'Our market share concerning TNE students' enrolment compared to other UK universities'; 'The targeted market share by our managers for TNE students' enrolment'; and 'Satisfaction of managers with the university market share based on the enrolment volume of TNE students'.

Based on the above information, two items were excluded, and four items were rephrased based on the analysis related to the judgment of experts. Three academics oversaw the lexical correctness prior to the questionnaire pilot testing. Table 4.9 illustrates the list of constructs, including the number of excluded items. Thus, the questionnaire become more effective after the pilot testing (Malhotra et al., 2017). The pilot test helps refine the questionnaire to make it easier for respondents to answer questions (Saunders et al., 2007). To refine the measurement instrument, the researcher conducted a pre-test study and made modifications to the measures to generate valid and reliable results.

Table 4.9: The total of final items used in the pre-test for every construct

Constructs		No. of initial items	Final items for pilot study
Transnational Education Market Orientation elements:			
TNE market information generation		9	9
TNE market information dissemination		8	8
TNE market orientation responsiveness		11	11
Transnational education market orientation antecedents	TNE coordination	8	8
	University international ranking position	6	6
	Developed country higher education image perception	10	8
Higher education international reputation		7	7
TNE business performance		9	9

Source: The researcher

Scores and intervals were used in all items using the 7-point Likert-type scale, anchored by 1 = very strongly disagree and 7 = very strongly agree. The respondents were managers selected based on their experience and knowledge of the research topic. They were required to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on the Likert-type scale to evaluate their attitude concerning TNE market orientation. The Likert scale is popular in marketing research as it provides insight into the underlying distribution of responses (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Therefore, the quantitative assessment's results contributed to adjust and submit items for scale purification (see Appendix 4.4).

4.5.3.1. Quantitative evaluation

The exploratory research, after the assessment of the qualitative study, reviewed the questionnaire to examine hypotheses. Consequently, all respondents recommended some important changes to be implemented in this research's survey (Gupta et al., 2011; Malhotra et al., 2017). This was done to determine, based on the pilot study, the validity of the constructs and the reliability of the measurement scales (Crow and Sheppard, 2010).

4.5.3.1.1. Pilot study

The pilot study aims to evaluate the essential aspects of refining the questionnaire, including the sequence of questions, wording, layout and format, response rate, clarity of instructions, participant familiarity, and completion time (Malhotra et al., 2017). Consequently, any ambiguously formulated items will be excluded (DeVellis, 2003) to ensure that participants can answer questions without difficulty (Saunders et al., 2007). Participants in the pilot study provide feedback on the survey's timing and clarity, conduct manipulation checks, and assess construct reliability (Malhotra, 2017).

The pilot study sample, as per Malhotra and Birks (2000), necessitates the participation of 20 to 40 individuals in a small-scale test of the survey, encompassing all activities leading to the final survey (Malhotra et al., 2017). In the pilot study, the researcher collected 69 questionnaires. However, 24 questionnaires were excluded due to low-quality responses or unanswered questions, leaving 45 questionnaires eligible for testing from three UK universities. These respondents will not be included in the final responses (Mingers, 2013). The demographic profile of participants in the pre-test sample is depicted in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10: Participants' demographic profile (pre-test sample includes: N=45)

Number of sample size		N	%
	29 to 35 years	9	20
	36 to 44 years	30	67
	45 to 50 years	6	13
	Total	45	100
	Male	24	53
	Female	21	47
	Total	45	100
	Postgraduate and above	45	100
	Total	45	100
	Marketing managers	6	13
	International officers	18	40
	TNE managers	21	47
	Total	45	100

Source: Developed by the researcher

Additionally, this pilot study includes exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to minimise items and determine patterns in the data (De Vaus, 2002). The scale demonstrated high reliability, with Cronbach’s alpha ranging between .867 and .964 for all constructs. This aligns with Hair et al.’s (1998) assertion that a coefficient alpha of 0.70 and above is highly suitable for research purposes. The results of both the reliability testing and factor analysis are presented in Appendix 4.5.

EFA is used to reduce the number of observed variables, thereby streamlining the items and enhancing control (Field, 2009; Hair et al., 1998). According to Hair et al. (2012), EFA tests the factorial structure of scales by examining the correlation coefficient in the correlation matrix, the required sample size, and the adequacy of the sample. TMR_10, TC_2, and DHIP_3 are items that were excluded due to loading on multiple factors (refer to Table 4.11). However, no items exhibited low reliability (below 0.4) or total correlation less than 0.50; therefore, no further items were removed (Field, 2013) (description in Appendix 4.6).

Table 4.11: The items removed after purification process

Construct	Items deleted	Reasons for dropping the items
TNE market information responsiveness	TMR_10	Multiple loadings on two factors
TNE coordination	TC_2	Multiple loadings on two factors
Developed country higher education image perception	DHIP_3	Multiple loadings on two factors

Source: Developed by the researcher

The researcher, after excluding items, re-analysed the items through a reliability test to assess if constructs with revised items were conducive to finding and ensured that “the measures are free from random error” and “provide a consistent data” (Shiu et al., 2009, p. 222). Subsequently, to evaluate consistency among the number of measurement items, the researcher conducted a reliability test (Field, 2009), assessing the correlation between the same scores of respondents for one measurement item at two distinct points (Hair et al., 2012). Reliability mitigates bias and enhances both the accuracy and consistency of reproducibility related with the generated measurement instruments across different samples and timeframes. The researcher opted for the Cronbach’s α coefficient method to measure reliability (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

The results of Cronbach's α coefficient, after the purifying process, remained higher than the acceptable level, which is 0.60 (Silverman, 2015). Further details can be found in Appendix 4.7. Therefore, based on the EFA, the final number of items in the questionnaire after purification is 63.

4.6. PHASE 3: MAJOR SURVEY

The researcher conducted a self-administrated questionnaire with managers related to TNE in UK universities between January 6th, 2021, and March 9th, 2021, using a random sampling technique known as convenience sampling (Hair et al., 2016). The following sections detail the sampling method and sample size.

4.6.1.1. The targeted sampling and population

Probability and non-probability are two significant samples classified by Bryman and Bell (2015). The non-probability sample is described as a sample that has not been selected using a random selection method. Bryman and Bell (2015) also emphasised that "in the field of business and management, convenience samples are very common and indeed are more prominent than samples based on probability sampling" (p. 199). In this research, the researcher focused on a 'convenience' sample, which is known as a technique of non-random sampling.

This study's population comprises UK universities operating TNE. The population size, obtained from Universities UK International 2020-2021, is 142 universities; hence, the researcher attempted to target all of them. The focus in this stage of research was on the perception of marketing managers concerning TNE market orientation and its impacts on higher education international reputation and TNE business performance in the UK. The researcher contacted the secretary of the British Universities International Liaison Association (BUILA), requesting support to conduct research with bodies related to TNE in all UK universities (142) operating TNE. An email was sent to the BUILA secretary on 17 November 2020, introducing the project study and attaching a link to the online questionnaire along with a participant consent form. A total of 1260 questionnaires were sent to different levels of TNE managers in 142 universities. As a result, 264 questionnaires were returned from 88 universities, with an average of three respondents from each university.

In a survey, not all contacted individuals will respond to the questionnaire, as noted by Malhotra et al. (2017). Additionally, the researcher contacted some student recruitment agents to reach more managers from UK universities. More questionnaires were completed by phone calls as an alternative to face-to-face questionnaire due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Consequently, the total number of questionnaires collected via phone calls was 87, including some responses from five additional universities. A rigorous statistical analysis requires data sampling with at least 300 respondents (Creswell, 2014). If the collected questionnaires are perfectly distributed and have no outlying or missing cases, then, according to Hu and Bentler (1999), it is considered acceptable. The researcher collected a total of 351 questionnaires, and 15 were removed due to a large quantity of missing data. Therefore, 336 completed questionnaires were collected in total from 93 university in the UK after pursuing all possible options to increase the number of completed questionnaires.

4.6.1.2. Appropriate number of participants

Deciding on an appropriate number of participants in a sample size is quite complex. According to Field (2009), the main technique used for determining sample size is linked to the processes of data analysis or techniques. The sample size in structure equation modelling (SEM) is affected by five considerations to gain reliable estimates as noted by Field (2009) and Hair et al. (1998).

First, in terms of multivariate distribution of data, if the data is non-normal, then the respondents' ratio to parameters must be higher. Therefore, having at least five respondents per parameter is considered an acceptable number to mitigate the difficulty arising from deviations from the assumption of multivariate normality in data distribution.

Second, regarding 'model complexity', the size's sample is determined based on the following criteria: if the SEM comprises five or fewer constructs, it is considered to have a small sample size, ranging between 100 and 150. For each construct with more than three measures and communalities of item above 0.6, this range is applicable. Moreover, if any of the communalities are modest (between 0.45 and 0.55), or if a construct includes less than three measures, a sample size of 200 is recommended, as suggested by Shiu (2009).

Third, when employing the maximum likelihood (ML) method, the sample size should ideally fall between 150 and 400 responses. This holds true even when using SME based on the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method. When the sample size surpasses 400 participants, the MLE method tends to become sensitive, and the results of goodness-of-fit measures may suffer as results indicated by Hair et al. (2013).

Fourth, in terms of 'missing data', the sample size must be increased when over 10% of the data is estimated to be missing.

Fifth, in terms of the 'average error variance of indicator', if the communalities of constructs are less than 0.5, large sample sizes are required.

SEM is used for this study, with an empirical recommendation of a minimum of five observations for each estimated parameter (Green et al., 1989). Additionally, communalities higher than 0.5 are proposed (Field, 2009). Therefore, considering the five considerations on appropriate sample size, the sample size of 336 respondents from 93 universities (representing 65% of the total universities operating TNE) in the UK is deemed suitable for this study.

4.6.2. DESIGN OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The respondents assessed the questionnaire based on their own experience with the universities they work with. Due to the nature of this research, it is necessary to assess different universities (Asaad et al., 2013; Healey, 2015; Yu et al., 2018). In marketing studies, the Likert scale is the most popular scale (Foroudi et al., 2021d), where respondents need to determine their level of disagreement or agreement to reflect their attitude towards TNE market orientation. Respondents' attitudes can be reflected in various situations, institutions, or activities, including both self and others (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Churchill and Peter (1984) propose that the seven-point scale decreases measurement error variance and increases construct variance compared to the ubiquitous five-point Likert scale. The questionnaire in this study is based on interval scales and uses a seven-point Likert scale (1 = Very strongly disagree to 7 = very strongly agree) (Shiu et al., 2009).

The lack of understanding regarding the influence between TNE market orientation, higher education international reputation, and TNE business performance (Asaad et al., 2015, Cadogan et al., 2013) has encouraged the researcher to investigate this gap. The study targets the perception of TNE managers to measure their management of market orientation concerning international students' satisfaction, challenges from competitors, and TNE business market share, using distinct scores.

The beginning of this study's survey includes the professional details of marketing managers and characteristics of their universities to assess their backgrounds (Stevens et al., 1997). The questionnaire's questions were meticulously designed with a clear layout, structure, shape, and visual appearance to ensure respondents could easily comprehend and respond to them (Fakhreddin et al., 2021; Tabchnick and Fidell, 2007). Each question in the questionnaire presented a statement aiming at gauging the managers' attitudes towards the university, its TNE market orientation, higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. Demographic details of respondents were placed at the end of the questionnaire. Respondents were instructed to answer the questions carefully to ensure comprehension and accurate responses (Churchill, 1999).

Therefore, this study's questionnaire comprised nine pages, including a covering letter to increase the response rate (Tabchnick and Fidell, 2007) (see Appendix 4.3). The covering letter described key instructions for the study along with a confidentiality guarantee to respondents.

4.6.3. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES AND STATISTICS PACKAGES

Multi-scale development, as advocated by Churchill (1979) and Foroudi et al. (2020), was applied to all constructs in order to maximise reliability and minimise measurement error. Churchill (1979) recommended employing multi-item scales instead of single-item scales. Therefore, the researcher adopted a triple approach for data analysis. The first approach, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), was implemented in both the pilot study and the main study to minimise the number of items and identify potential patterns in the data (Foroudi et al., 2021a). Coefficient alpha was used to evaluate the reliability of the scales and the instrument's quality by checking the qualitative data collected (Churchill, 1979; Hair et al., 1998; Peter, 1979). The second approach, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), was employed in the main survey data to assess the measurement properties related to the validity of existing scales (Field,

2009). The third approach, structural equation modelling (SEM), was utilised to examine all hypotheses and to avoid potential relationships between measurements and structural models (Field, 2009).

Several purposes underling the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) at the initial stage of data analysis (Hair et al., 2016; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The first purpose is coding, editing, and reviewing missing data. The second purpose is to assess the assumptions of normality, multi-collinearity, linearity, and identify outliers. The third purpose is to examine the dispersion and focal tendency of variables by calculating means, frequencies, and standard deviations. The fourth reason is to conduct EFA, supported by descriptive analysis to provide an overview of the sample (Foroudi et al., 2021a). Reliability analysis is also used to evaluate the instrument's reliability and the validity of the data (Churchill, 1979; Peter, 1979); refinement is based on reliability and dimensionality. The purpose of these tests is to assess the scales used for measuring constructs and to refine the measures accordingly.

To assess the proposed measurement model quality and hypothesised structural model quality, the researcher used Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) due to its unique graphical interface. Its implementation involves conducting CFA and SEM (Hair et al., 2016). The features of these techniques are detailed in the following sections, along with the rationale behind adopting the selected techniques.

4.6.3.1. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and coefficient alpha

In the early stages of scale validity, the use of EFA is a significant and helpful technique (Netemeyer et al., 2003). This technique, being exploratory and data driven, is effective in reducing the number of observed variables (indicator) to make them more manageable (Hair et al., 2013; Field, 2009).

EFA, according to Hair (2013), ensures that “any individual factor should account for the difference of at least one single variable” (p. 103). This technique supports researchers in understanding factors that are not dependent on each other, allowing for the recognition of a specific field's structure (Field, 2009). The use of EFA permits researchers to identify the data and gain information about the probable number of factors that accurately represent the data (Field, 2009), making the data ready for SEM (Hair et al., 2016).

The method of principal components was used for factor extraction (Field, 2009; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). This method represents the total variance, including unique, common, and error variance, to estimate the minimum number of factors needed to demonstrate the highest variances. An orthogonal method of Varimax rotation was used, to reduce the number of variables into a smaller groups of uncorrelated variables, thereby facilitating effective prediction techniques (Field, 2009). The determination of the number of factors to extract was achieved using eigenvalues, guided by the latent root criterion (eigenvalue >1.00).

4.6.3.2. Structural equation modelling (SEM)

The use of structural equation modelling (SEM) aims to generate insights diversified relationships and influences, facilitated by the AMOS software package, to identify unattached relationships of every dependent variable (Field, 2013). The literature review was used to test the proposed conceptual framework, and hypotheses were tested by implementing a SME. SME, as described by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), encompasses several statistical techniques allowing testing of associations among single or plural independent variables, either discrete or continuous, and single or plural dependent variables. SEM offers strong explanatory power, where both endogenous and exogenous variables could be factors or measured variables.

Seven reasons encourage researchers to use the SEM techniques as described by Field (2009) and Foroudi et al. (2021a). First, when the researched phenomena are multidimensional and complex, SME is the only analysis that can simultaneously account for many dependent associations among the talent variable and observed indicators using a measurement model. It allows for testing the link between latent variables using structural model via calculating multiple regression equations with highly efficient statistical packages, greater than SPSS. Second, analysis of SEM is considered as model specification, meaning that it is not an exploratory but a confirmatory technique. Third, SEM calculates individually for every construct reliability, validity, and unidimensionality. Fourth, SEM predicts both indirect and direct connections. Fifth, SME is more advanced than other multivariate techniques, permits explicit estimates for measurement errors, and helps testing hypotheses for inferential objectives. Sixth, latent variables are used by SEM to calculate measurement error for offering the overall goodness-of-fit to examine the measurement model. Seventh, question are answered through SME, which includes factors' multiple regression analyses.

4.6.3.2.1. Strategies for structural equation modelling (SEM)

Two stages will be used to analyse the SEM data. The first stage is to examine measurement properties concerning the essential latent variables in the model with the support of the CFA for all constructs. The following reasons underlie the use of the measurement model:

- The measurement model clarifies the reason of relations between the respective latent and observed indicators' constructs (Foroudi et al., 2021a) based on the unidimensionality assumption. Unidimensionality reflects several indicators with a single underlying construct (Field, 2009). The unidimensionality of scale originally examined as another significant property by CFA and further validity by EFA (Steenkamp and Baumgartner, 2000). In this stage, the confirmatory measurement model is used to identify strong links among respective constructs and observed variables (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012), ensuring that the standardised factor loading values are 0.6 and above.
- The construct's validity and reliability are crucial for further theoretical examination. CFA, following EFA, permits for the calculation of additional estimations concerning the construct's reliability (composite reliability) (Handerson and Gerbing, 1982; Field, 2013).

The second stage includes a structural model to examine measurement development, asserting the links among constructs and their indicators, and examining structural model to ensure the causal links between latent constructs (Hair et al., 2010). Latent variables, observed variables, or both, can measure all constructs.

4.6.3.3. Evaluating the model fit

CFA supports reaching a confirmatory stage based on having complete control over the description of constructs' indicators, enabling a statistical examination of dimensionality and goodness-of-fit for a specific measurement model (Field, 2013). The CFA's purpose is to confirm or validate the measurement factors presented in a range of variables connected to the theoretical model (Field, 2013).

The typical approach to assessing reliability involves assuming unidimensional measures (Bollen, 1989). According to Novick and Lewis (1967), coefficient alpha, commonly used as a reliability index in marketing, tends to underestimate the reliability of multidimensional measures. Levine et al. (2006) emphasise that unidimensionality is essential for coefficient alpha's effective application, as well as for evaluating the goodness-of-fit of any model, considering theoretical, statistical, and practical considerations. Following recommendation from the methodological literature on CFA, this study used and elaborated on absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and indices of model parsimony.

Firstly, this study employed both incremental fit indices and absolute fit indices. The absolute fit indices were utilised to collectively scrutinise the structural model and measurement model (Field, 2013). These indices gauge the extent to which the hypothesised model accurately reflects the sample data. They are instrumental in assessing the nomological validity of the measurement models and do not rely on an alternative model as a reference point for comparison. Below, the chosen fit indices are elaborated upon.

- i) Chi-square (χ^2) stands as the primary method for assessing goodness-of-fit, with its statistic being the foremost fit measure presented in Amos output. According to Hair et al. (2012), a low χ^2 value, indicating insignificance, implies a satisfactory fit. This inference arises from the comparison between actual and predicted matrices via the chi-square test, where non-significance denotes no notable difference between them. Concerning model goodness-of-fit, p-values determine whether the model significantly deviates from the null model, typically set at '0' in statistical analysis. A p-value exceeding zero or a high p-value prompts rejection of the null hypothesis, signalling a heightened likelihood of error (MacLean and Gray, 1998). Conversely, a low p-value, approaching zero, furnishes grounds for null hypothesis rejection with a diminished likelihood of error. Ideally, the disparity between the two matrices should lack statistical significance ($p > .05$). Nonetheless, Qu et al. (2013) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) caution against exclusively relying on this fit measure to appraise overall model goodness-of-fit, particularly when χ^2 exhibits high sensitivity to sample size.

MacLean and Gray (1998) proposed that a χ^2 / d.f. ratio of 3 or lower suggests a satisfactory fit for the model. However, the χ^2 statistic is particularly sensitive to sample size, especially when the number of observations exceeds 200. If the data deviates from normality, the χ^2 value may exceed what would be expected from model error alone. Definitive guidelines for the minimum acceptable norm χ^2 , sometimes referred to as *T*, are lacking. Chi-square serves as the original fit index for structural models and should be supplemented with other indices (Field, 2013). It is commonly included in SEM results reporting.

- ii) Joreskog and Sorbom (1982) introduced the goodness-of-fit index (GFI), marking it as the pioneering metric for evaluating model fit while mitigating sensitivity to sample size. The GFI assesses the proportionate variance and covariance within the sample covariance matrix relative to the population covariance matrix. Its values span from zero to one, with values nearing one indicating a favourable fit. Any GFI surpassing one is capped at one, and if it drops below zero, it is adjusted to zero. Ideally, the GFI falls within the range of 0.90 to 1.00. Scores between 0.80 and 0.89 suggest an acceptable fit (Qu et al., 2013), while GFIs under 0.8 are considered unreliable (TZhang, 2020). The concept of variance underscores the foundational principle behind evaluating the goodness-of-fit of a model.

- iii) The adjusted goodness-of-fit Index (AGFI) holds significance in comparing competing models as it adjusts for the degrees of freedom of the model relative to those of the null model (Field, 2013). Both the GFI and AGFI utilise chi-square-based calculations that are independent of degrees of freedom. The AGFI modifies the GFI by considering degrees of freedom, leading to lower values for models with more parameters. It parallels the GFI but substitutes the total sum of squares with the mean sum of squares. An AGFI exceeding 0.90 indicates an acceptable fit (Zhang et al., 2020). AGFI values span from zero to one, with those equal to or surpassing 0.9 regarded as indicative of a satisfactory fit (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Teo, 2011). Values falling between 0.90 and 1.00 are considered favourable fits, whereas those ranging from 0.80 to 0.89 suggest a moderate fit (Qu et al., 2013).

- iv) The Root-mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) serves as a highly informative criterion for assessing model fit. This metric gauges the difference between the sample and fitted covariance matrices per degree of freedom (Steiger, 1990) and is responsive to the number of parameters (MacCallum et al., 1998). RMSEA evaluates the disparity based on the population rather than the sample. According to Field (2013), RMSEA reflects how well a model aligns with a population (p. 748). A value below 0.05 suggests a favourable fit, while values up to 0.08 indicate a reasonable fit. However, a value surpassing 0.08 is considered indicative of a poor and unacceptable fit (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Teo, 2011).

Secondly, the incremental fit indices, as per Hair et al. (2012), assess how well the targeted models conform to a specific null model. The present research sheds light on many incremental fit indices.

The role of normed fit index (NFI) is to compare the nested models (Foroudi et al., 2021a). This comparison process pertains to the recommended model but disregards the degree of freedom. Additionally, it measures the ratio contributing to the model's development in terms of fit compared to the base model (Field, 2013). The NFI facilitates a comparison between the chi-square value of the model and that of the independence model (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). However, this index does not control for degrees of freedom and overlooks fit within small samples (Teo, 2011). An enhanced version of the NFI, known as the comparative fit index (CFI), exists (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Teo, 2011).

The measure of the CFI relies on the non-centrality measures. When the index exceeds 1, it is truncated to 1, and when it falls below 0, it is truncated to 0. A CFI close to 1 indicates a good fit (Foroudi et al., 2021a). Furthermore, it is contingent upon the average size of correlations in the data (Byrne, 2001; Field, 2013; Foroudi et al., 2021a; Teo, 2011). When the average relationship between variables is low, the CFI will also be low.

Regarding the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) or non-normed fit index (NNFI), they compare the model's chi-square value with that of the independence model, accounting for the degrees of freedom of both models (Field, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Teo, 2011). TLI relies on the average size of correlations in the data and mathematically compares the baseline null model to specific theoretical measurement models (Field, 2013). Values of 0.9 and above are considered good, while values between 0.8 and 0.89 are deemed acceptable (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982). Although the TLI is adjusted for parsimony, it is not its primary purpose. The results of a well-fitting model are presented in Table 4.12.

Table 4.12: Good fitting model's results

	Type	Acceptance level in this research
Coefficient alpha (α)		$\alpha > 0.7$ adequate and > 0.5 is acceptable
Standardised Regression Weight (β)	Unidimensionality	Beta > 0.15
Chi-square (with associated degrees of freedom and probability of significant different) (df, p)	Model fit	$p > 0.05$ (at α equals to 0.05 level)
Normed chi-square (/df)	Absolute fit and model parsimony	$< /df < 3.0$
Normalised fit index (NFI) Non-normalised fit index (NNFI) Comparative fit index (CFI)	Incremental fit Compare your model to baseline independence model	Values above 0.8 and close 0.90 indicate acceptable fit
Goodness-of-fit index (GFI) Adjusted goodness-of-fit (AGFI) Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	Absolute fit	0.90 0.90 0.08

Source: Developed from Hair et al. (2006)

4.6.3.4. The unidimensionality

The measures are heavily supported by unidimensionality, which is crucial but insufficient for construct validity (Handerson and Gerbing, 1982). Cronbach (1984) defines unidimensionality as follows: "A set of items is 'unidimensional' if their order of difficulty is the same for everyone in a population of interest" (p. 116). Unidimensionality is typically assessed through the estimated model specification with structural equation analysis, aiming to separate measurement issues (links among a construct and its observed indicators or variables) from structural model issues (links among constructs) (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012).

Operationalising unidimensionality, as described by Anderson and Gerbing (1982), involves utilising structural equation analysis to assess internal and external consistency. Consistency, to fit the data, has been depicted as the model of structural equation (Kenny, 1979). Indicators of consistency, X , x_1 and x_2 , as defined by Anderson and Gerbing (1982), are considered internally stable if the correlation between them is equal to correlation of their X construct. Therefore, two different indicators of X and Z , x and z are consistent if the link between z and x resembles the three correlations. External consistency is ideal for items that “cluster together in a matrix of sorted or ordered similarity coefficients” (Hair et al., 2016, p. 458). A minor feasible difference among the latent variable reliability (ρ) and coefficient alpha (α) for unidimensional constructs with sufficiency is the utilisation of coefficient alpha to assess reliability as a preparatory step.

4.6.3.5. Assessment of composite reliability

CFA permits for the calculation of an additional consideration, composite reliability, also known as construct reliability (Handerson and Gerbing, 1982; Field, 2013). Composite reliability reflects reliability measurements and evaluates the internal measured variables’ consistency, indicating a latent construct (Field, 2013). According to Hair et al. (1998), composite reliability is a crucial measure employed to evaluate the overall reliability of the measurement model for each latent construct. The minimum value for composite reliability should be 0.7, indicating that the total measures consistently represent the same latent construct (Martínez-Lopez et al., 2013). Cronbach’s alpha represents the reliability of the construct and measures the unidimensionality of indicators through their inter-correlation with their latent constructs (Hair et al., 2016).

4.6.3.6. Assessment of average variance extracted (AVE)

The average variance extracted (AVE) quantifies the shared variance in a latent variable (LV), indicating the extent to which the LV’s variance is attributable to its relationship with variance due to random measurement error (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012; Foroudi et al., 2021a; Fornell and Larker, 1981). In essence, the AVE measures the error-free variance of multiple items. According to Fornell and Larker (1981), the AVE serves as a robust indicator of construct reliability compared to composite reliability. The AVE represents the proportion of overall variance captured by the relative indicators after accounting for measurement error, and for the validity of a construct and the assurance of scale validity, it should be 0.50 or higher (Field, 2013).

4.6.3.7. Nomological validity

To attain construct validity in theory development and testing, establishing nomological validity represents a fundamental step (Foroudi et al., 2021a; Anderson and Gerbing, 1982; Hair et al., 2016). Nomological validity involves testing the hypothesised relationships between various constructs and the experimental connections among measures of multiple constructs (Peter and Churchill, 1986). Nomological validity assesses whether the behaviour of measures aligns with expectations, as suggested by Peter and Churchill (1986), and evaluates whether the behaviour of constructs conforms to expectations both empirically and theoretically. To evaluate the nomological validity of measurement models, the use of goodness-of-fit indices is essential (Hair et al., 2016).

4.6.3.8. Convergent validity

Convergent validity signifies the homogeneity of a construct and denotes the extent to which independent measures for one construct converge or positively correlate with different measures of the same construct (Foroudi et al., 2021a; Malhotra et al., 2017). It can be assessed relative to construct reliabilities (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012) and is associated with the internal consistency validity, indicated by either low or high correlations among every item within a construct (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Additionally, it evaluates the significance level of factors and their t-values (Foroudi et al., 2021a). High inter-item correlations within each construct signify convergent validity (Foroudi et al., 2021a; Shiu et al., 2009). Thus, reliabilities of 0.7 and above imply convergent validity, and reliabilities exceeding 0.85 suggest an error variance of more than 50% (Field, 2009).

4.6.3.9. Discriminant validity

Discriminant validity reflects the degree to which measures of one construct are minimally correlated with measures of other constructs (Foroudi et al., 2021a; Malhotra et al., 2017; Peter and Churchill, 1986). Hence, it is valid when there is a lack of significant correlation between the measures of an experiment and all other constructs (Shiu et al., 2009). Therefore, if the correlation between two constructs is below 1.00, discriminant validity is established (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012).

According to Anderson and Gerbing (1982), discriminant validity "can be assessed for two estimated constructs by constraining the estimated correlation parameter (ϕ_{ij}) between them to 1.00 and then performing a chi-square difference test on the values obtained for the constrained and unconstrained model" (p. 416). If the restricted model demonstrates a lower fit compared to the unrestricted model, then it indicates the presence of discriminant validity (Foroudi et al., 2021a). The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) can measure discriminant validity for each construct, and the squared correlation of each of them can be used for comparison (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Malhotra et al., 2017).

When the squared correlation between two latent variables is lower than all of their individual Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values, it is proposed that each construct has more error-free variance (internal or extracted) compared to the variance shared with other constructs (r^2). Additionally, as described by Fornell and Larcker (1981), constructs are highly correlated internally compared to their correlations with other constructs, indicating discriminant validity for the intended extracted variance.

4.7. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Academic studies must adhere to ethical standards related to the study's activities. This is associated with the guidelines provided by the West of Scotland Business School ethics form, as well as the British Educational Research Association. Compliance with fundamental ethical principles in research and understanding their impact on the conducted research is crucial. Social and business researchers alike share several common ethical concerns (Valentine et al., 2014).

All fundamental considerations are addressed in this study. Firstly, the participants' rights are upheld by safeguarding the statutory rights of social investigation groups, avoiding unnecessary intrusion, obtaining participants' consent, and ensuring the protection of their privacy. Secondly, providing a clear description of the research questions' objectives is imperative for ethical research conduct. Thirdly, researchers should be mindful of cultural and social differences. Fourthly, comprehensive awareness of methodologies enhances public confidence in their reliability. Therefore, by addressing the aforementioned considerations, as outlined in the questionnaire's covering letter (see Appendix 4.3), the targeted segment will be more confident to participate. As a result, the researcher obtained approval from the West of Scotland Business School.

4.8. SUMMARY

The methodology, approach, and perspective presented in this chapter were employed to examine the operational model and hypotheses described in the previous chapter. The implementation of several methods aimed to increase the credibility of the findings. The development of the TNE market orientation measurement scale in this research relied on Churchill's paradigm of 1979. The utilisation of qualitative data is intended to understand the perceptions of marketing and TNE managers regarding the TNE market orientation.

The questionnaire was developed based on interviews and focus groups (qualitative findings). The pilot study involved 45 participants (managers from international offices and TNE departments) with the purpose of ensuring the validity and reliability of the research instrument. To gauge respondents' attitudes towards TNE market orientation and determine their level of agreement or disagreement, a seven-point Likert scale was employed. A self-administered questionnaire was conducted in the quantitative study involving 336 managers from UK universities. Additionally, the questionnaire's development was guided by content steps, relevance of operational items to the study's objectives, and appropriate wording and layout management. Data collection techniques included Microsoft Teams for interviews and email for the questionnaire survey. Issues pertaining to data collection were addressed, including the development of the survey instrument, unit of analysis, and techniques used for data analysis: CFA, EFA, and SEM. Ethical considerations were subsequently presented.

CHAPTER 5: QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

5.1. INTRODUCTION

Chapter 4 detailed the significance of the implemented methodology in the current research. Based on qualitative research, the presence of the unstructured inquiry method fosters interview participants to express their opinions the way they prefer, which produces greater effective insights (Creswell, 2013). This section reflects the data collected from focus groups and interviews in relation to the following purposes. The current research attempts to collect significant in-depth information for developing the conception of the TNE market orientation and its impacts on higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. Results from the qualitative study are generated from eight interviews with managers of international marketing, the international office, and TNE departments in addition to four focus group observations. Chapter 4 covered all details related to the qualitative stage in terms of the nature of interviews and personnel's selection for interviews, planning, management, and data interpretation. The next section (5.2) describes the findings from the qualitative study, while section 5.3 covers concluding remarks.

5.2. QUALITATIVE STUDY: RESULTS

This section presents a report of findings and the data that support the developed themes on TNE market orientation dimensions and their outcomes for higher education international reputation and TNE business performance.

The research analysis in this section has identified three elements of TNE market orientation and their influences on TNE business performance. In agreement with the literature, all interviewees insisted on the value of developing an effective TNE market orientation. Consistent with the literature reviewed in Chapter 2, the interview participants confirmed the value of an effective TNE market orientation, noted its impact on the growth of TNE programmes and partners, and highlighted its primary role in maximising the number of international students, especially in today's competitive market.

5.2.1. TRANSNATIONAL EDUCATION MARKET ORIENTATION

5.2.1.1. Transnational education management

Interviewees who participated in this qualitative study all agreed on the perception of TNE as outlined in the literature review in Chapter 2 (Healey, 2015; Lien and Keithley, 2020). They shared almost the same TNE activities, which were reflected in the following four typologies: branch campus, franchising, distance learning, and validation.

When a TNE Programmes Development manager was asked about the practice of these four TNE typologies, he stated:

Our university has achieved significant development in TNE over the last two decades. We have expanded our geographical presence in Hong Kong, Malaysia, Singapore, Oman, Uzbekistan, Kenya, Trinidad and Tobago, Vietnam, and some European countries as well ... Our university was the first British university to operate in many of these countries. (University 5)

Other respondents expressed their early-stage position in the process of TNE. Whereas some of the interviewees confirmed their limited focus towards specific TNE activities due to their limited experience in TNE and fear of giving a negative impression of their universities overseas, which is contrary to what Healey (2018) mentions about the involvement of universities in several TNE programmes being motivated solely by increasing their student market share. A marketing manager said:

I would say we mainly focus on franchises and validation with all our partners. Our aim is to maintain control over the quality of courses delivered in our partners' institutions and to prevent devaluation of our awarded degrees. However, in the future, we might consider other types of TNE, but for now, our concentration is more on franchises and validation. (University 7)

Concerning the management of the four TNE typologies, respondents also agreed on the significant role of the international office and its coordination with other departments in the university for effective management of the current or potential TNE activities. An international partnership development manager commented as follows:

The approach towards national and international TNE collaboration is based on a secure plan and effective risk management, developed and implemented with the involvement of other departments. Management of TNE is much more effective when receiving input from all university departments. (University 2)

While two respondents (the head of the international office and the senior international officer) illustrated that international students feedbacks are contributing to the orientation of their TNE management:

We consider our international students' feedback as an additional tool in the process of making decisions related to TNE management, ensuring high quality learning delivery. (University 6)

We put international students at the heart of everything this university does, including TNE management. (University 3)

5.2.1.2. Supporting the conception of TNE market orientation

When questioning the opinions of interviewees on the definition of TNE market orientation, the responses received were relevant to each other, with all expressing agreement on the definition. Below are some opinions:

I strongly agree with this definition, as working in a competitive market requires a wide collection of information about the needs of international students and partners, as well as other factors (competitors) that might affect their choice or decisions regarding higher education. (University 1)

Yes, I agree, as this definition clarifies the support that marketing orientation can provide for the development of TNE. (University 3)

I can say that this definition targets the effect of market orientation towards TNE as a means to satisfy the needs of international students, partners, and the university within a mutual framework. (University 6)

It reflects the main purpose of TNE market orientation based on important stakeholders of TNE, including valuing the needs of partners, not only the needs of international students. (university 7)

The participants had different responses regarding the level of consideration their universities give to TNE market orientation, reflecting the varying levels of TNE practice across institutions. However, they commonly believe in its positive influence, as illustrated in the literature by Gruber-Muecke (2015). A TNE Programmes Development manager expressed:

Effective responses are required to meet the increasing demand for TNE and to compete effectively, a need fulfilled by TNE market orientation. Our university puts significant effort into this aspect to maintain the success of our TNE practice, unlike many universities that prioritize working on their products rather than market orientation. (University 5)

Those who mentioned that their universities are engaged in limited TNE programmes have similar responses to a marketing manager, who responded as follows:

I believe that the TNE market orientation practice in this university is increasing along with the growth of our partners and TNE programmes... In the future, we plan to pay additional attention to this practice. (University 7)

Elements of TNE market orientation

With regards to the elements that shape TNE market orientation, respondents described them based on the concept of market orientation as covered in the literature review (James and Derrick, 2021; Vangelis et al., 2018). A senior international officer replied:

It is shaped through the understanding of our international students' needs via market intelligence generation. We work closely with different departments in the university, sharing what we know about international students' needs and gathering their feedback. This process aids us in making decisions related to TNE and the necessary reforms. (University 4)

A TNE Programmes Development manager Added:

TNE market orientation in this university relies on how we stay updated on the needs of international students and competitors related to TNE, our collaborative efforts on the generated TNE information, and our prompt response to the collected information. (University 5)

TNE market information generation

The following statements reflect the various ways that universities use to generate TNE market information, according to respondents. All of these methods are centralised around the concept described by researchers such as Asaad et al. (2015), Cadogan et al. (2016), and Larsen (2016) in the literature:

We contact our students' union as the first platform to amplify students' voices. We conduct regular surveys with our international students on issues related to TNE, allowing us to monitor our educational quality and track their perceptions of course content, teaching quality, student support, and satisfaction with academic services. (University 1)

Generating TNE market information relies on the type of TNE our university intends to deliver and with whom we will cooperate. However, we typically prioritize our international students, as we can maintain frequent contact with them. This is followed by the international students enrolled with our TNE partners, with the aim of identifying weaknesses in our TNE. (University 4)

The TNE Programmes Development manager, in a similar comment to the international marketing manager from University 1, added:

... We involve parents in our strategic plan to generate TNE market information as well. (University 5)

When asked how the TNE market information generation practice supports their university, responses were similar to each other as all of them described a positive purpose for the university and TNE progress. The following are some participants' comments:

It supports our decision-making process, such as accepting or rejecting offers of TNE partnerships. It also keeps us updated on changes in the TNE environment in markets where we operate, enabling us to address any issues that might hinder our progress. (University 1)

I can say that it contributes to detecting issues, needs, and opportunities that our TNE management might never be aware of. It improves our experience in TNE by providing information to analyse offers of partnership, enabling us to avoid offers that might damage the international image and reputation of our university.(University 7)

TNE market information dissemination

In line with Asaad et al. (2015), Cadogan et al. (2016), and Larsen (2016), regarding how universities disseminate TNE market information, respondents illustrated numerous common methods. These methods constitute their ongoing process of sharing crucial TNE information with other departments and personnel in the university, as follows:

Different formal or informal meetings with managers from the international office and other departments in our university, as well as with managers of our TNE partners' administration (using platforms like Skype for meetings or webinars for training) are held on a regular basis and during emergencies, such as the Covid-19 pandemic. Heads of our faculties/schools also receive reports on TNE practice or any changes in the TNE environment through emails. (University 1)

All departments receive our monthly internal electronic newsletter via email, which covers the latest news and plans of our university, including TNE. To approve a TNE programme or partnership, the international office manager meets with heads of other departments from our faculties/schools to share information and plans and to gather their opinions and feedback. (University 2)

Sharing information is part of our organisational culture. Every day, personnel from the same or different departments in our university exchange information on the university's issues or its progress. (University 4)

When asking how the dissemination of TNE market information supports the development of TNE in universities, responses described it as beneficial for the university and TNE progress. The following are some participants' comments:

It strengthens the relationships between managers themselves and with employees from the same department or from different departments. (University 3)

It increases awareness about TNE actions and decreases the risks of potential decisions related to TNE. (University 5)

I believe it allows our management to identify aspects that require mutual interaction, thus advancing our actions regarding matters related to TNE and supporting its development. (University 7)

TNE market information responsiveness

Regarding how universities respond to TNE market information, all respondents prioritised the positive effect of responses to TNE market information in alignment with research (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2018). The following comments illustrate the convergence of opinions among interviewees:

It is among our priorities; we respond promptly to anything related to our TNE practices. The responses are based on collective agreements between decision-makers from different departments. Delays in responding might cause an accumulation of tasks, an inability to keep up with market trends, and dissatisfaction among international students. (University 2)

We are very transparent with TNE students. For example, we supported international students applying for e-learning programmes who were unable to take the IELTS test due to the closure of the British Council and other English centres during the Covid-19 pandemic. Our university provided accurate information on the application process and managed an online English test at a low cost. (University 5)

However, in addition to the mutual agreement on the value of TNE market information responsiveness, two respondents indicated their slow response to TNE market information.

We value TNE market information responsiveness in this university, but our actions are somewhat slow due to the precision required in our action plan. (University 1)

Our responses to TNE market information are much quicker when it is related to the main activities of our university's mission statement.(University 7)

When asked how the practice of TNE market information responsiveness supports the development of TNE in universities, responses identify a range of benefits generated from their responsiveness, such as support for marketing activities, creating word of mouth, enhancing the university's reputation, and fostering growth and leadership in the TNE market. The following comments reflect these benefits:

I believe the increase in our international students' enrolment is related to how we respond to TNE market information. (University 2)

Responding to TNE market information provides significant opportunities to grow and lead in the TNE market. (University 3)

Provides much support to our presence in the TNE market in the long term. (University 4)

Reflects a positive image that contributes to increasing our international reputation. (University 7)

Therefore, comparing these statements from heads of marketing or international offices in different universities reflected similar perceptions to those covered in the literature review on TNE market orientation (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2016; He et al., 2018; Rumbley and Altbach, 2015). This research supports the conception of the studied topic as examined in Chapter 3 based on literature review. The development of measurement scales was based on TNE market orientation activities generated by this qualitative study.

5.2.2. Antecedents to TNE market orientation

5.2.2.1. Transnational education coordination

Information-based export marketing activities, entirely managed by the international marketing office (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2012; Jules, 2018), are a significant factor in EMO (Cadogan et al., 2009). Most of the participants agreed with this based on the following statements that reflect their opinions on TNE coordination:

TNE activities can be more supported by the coordination of key players in university departments... Our strong coordination enhances decision-making, provides diverse opinions, and minimizes risks. (University 2)

The effective communication among departments within our faculties/schools contributes to the process of coordinating TNE activities. (University 5)

Big universities with various TNE programmes and partners will find inter-functional coordination between departments very complicated, but not impossible... We are in the process of building coordination between our departments. (University 6)

When asked about how the university coordinates with its TNE partners, participants referred to this by illustrating that constant high-quality communication can be achieved through sharing knowledge, objectives, and mutual respect. The following statements reflect participants' perceptions:

The coordination system between our internal departments is applied to our TNE partners as well. We maintain frequent, timely, accurate, and problem-solving communication with them as a way of sharing goals and objectives. (University 2)

There is mutual adjustment between our university and our TNE partners, where we integrate TNE work in conditions of uncertainty and task interdependence interdependently. (University 5)

However, in accordance with some research (Crick, 2021; Jules, 2018; Morgan et al., 2012), managers' perceptions reflect their belief in the efficiency of coordination, as it allows universities to gain many insights and opportunities to strengthen the quality of TNE market

information generation. When questioning the extent to which TNE coordination impacts the TNE market information that a university generates, there was a common perception. This is illustrated by the following statement:

The TNE coordination in this university, affects positively the generation of TNE market information. (University 2)

Our good TNE coordination facilitates the TNE market information generation, as our contact with partners is already based on effective communication in all aspects. (University 5)

The effects of our TNE coordination contribute to the growth of TNE market information generation. (University 6)

Concerning the relationship between university TNE coordination and TNE market information generation, participants expressed a positive correlation between the two. Good TNE coordination increases TNE market information generation, as found in the research on EMO by Asaad (2013). The following statements reflect participants' perceptions:

It helps dramatically the flow of the TNE market information that our university generates. (University 2)

It increases the positive relationship between key players of our university and TNE partners, which increases the amount of effective TNE market information generation. (University 5)

When asked about the extent to which TNE coordination impacts the TNE market information that a university disseminates, there was a common perception among participants. They believed that efficient TNE coordination makes TNE market information dissemination easier due to the good experience of all key players in communication and their strong relationships (Chang and Wang, 2018; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014). The following statements describe this:

The TNE coordination in this university, affects positively the dissemination of TNE market information. (University 2)

The absence of work conflicts among departments of our universities contributes to the creation of good communication and attitudes between managers, facilitating the dissemination of TNE market information that increases knowledge on threats and opportunities of TNE among different management hierarchies in the university.
(University 5)

When participants were responding to how university TNE coordination is related to TNE market information dissemination, they confirmed a positive relationship between the two measures: good TNE coordination increases TNE market information dissemination, as supported by the literature (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2009; Chung, 2012). The following statements reflect this perception.:

It helps on the flow of the TNE market information that our university disseminates.
(University 2)

It contributes to better TNE market information dissemination results. (University 4)

It increases the positive relationship between key players of our university and TNE partners, resulting in more effective TNE market information dissemination.
(University 5)

Regarding the extent to which TNE coordination impacts the TNE market information responsiveness by the university, managers reflect their belief that efficient TNE coordination increases alertness toward TNE market information responsiveness with several suggestions and proposals, due to the good communication and relationships between all key players (Chang et al., 2014; Chang and Wang, 2018; Cadogan et al., 2006). The following statements describe this:

Our good TNE coordination increases the attention of our faculties/schools' managers towards the TNE market information responsiveness. (University 5)

The effects of our TNE coordination, including our coordination with educational partners, contribute to diversified proposals and plans that facilitate effective interventions in matters related to TNE. (University 6)

Regarding how university TNE coordination is related to TNE market information responsiveness, participants also agreed on a positive relationship between the two measures: good TNE coordination increases TNE market information responsiveness (Asaad et al., 2013; Feng et al., 2013; Healey, 2020). Statements from participants:

It enhances the positive relationship between key players of our university and TNE partners, resulting in improving the effectiveness of TNE market information responsiveness. (University 4)

The results of TNE market information responsiveness become more effective due to continuous coordination across different levels of TNE... Effective strategies can be implemented under the same vision. (Focus group 2)

Therefore, all these qualitative statements agreed on the positive role TNE coordination plays in TNE market orientation.

5.2.2.2. University international ranking position

The international ranking positions of most universities whose managers participated in our qualitative study range between 500 and 1000 globally, except for one, which is ranked among the top 300 universities internationally.

This year we are classified in the 801-900 category by the QS world universities ranking. (University 1)

Our university is classified in the top 600 universities out of 1258 institutions in the 2020 World University Rankings. (University 2)

From between 1620 universities allocated in 82 countries, we are placed in the 501-600 category in the QS World Ranking table. (University 4)

This university maintains its position between the first 300 universities in the last five years and this demonstrates the efficiency of our performance worldwide. (University 5)

However, some of these universities utilise additional strategies to achieve a better international ranking position, such as emerging in the ranking table of new universities established after the end of the last century, or a ranking table related to a specific subject (Brown and Carasso, 2013; Ghobehei et al., 2019). Managers of international marketing and international partnership development managers added to the above statements:

We are also among the best 200 universities for Business in the world according to Times Higher Education. (University 1)

Last year, we were ranked in the top 150 according to the Young University Rankings by Times Higher Education. (University 2)

Responses regarding the elements involved in the classification of universities in international ranking tables by participants illustrated agreement on several factors. These include high quality of teaching and research, implementation of innovation, entry standards, number of enrolled international students, graduation rates, and graduates' employability. Similar findings are supported by some research in the literature (Rutter et al., 2017; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Hazelkorn, 2011).

Our international ranking position relies on high teaching quality such as inclusive innovative teaching, internationally recognised research (including the number of times our academic research has been cited by other scholars), entry standards and graduates' number and prospects. (University 2)

Quality of our education (qualified and experienced professors, researchers, and managers), international students' satisfaction, high demand towards our courses, our graduates are highly wanted by employers, and the amount of our academic publications and the type of journals we publish in. (University 5)

Most participants agreed that the university's international ranking position holds significant importance towards TNE market information generation, supporting the studies by Bose and Kober (2015) and Christensen et al. (2018). The following quotes clarify this idea:

International students are more influenced by universities that appear in the list of universities ranking, which supports our activities to generate TNE market information. (University 6)

An unranked or low-ranking university is a sign that something is wrong with the university operation, resulting in a search for the weak point through TNE market information generation. (University 7)

However, one international marketing manager had another perception towards this matter:

Unranked universities or those with low ranking are presented in the TNE market more than universities with good ranking position and there are some differences in ranking lists which affects the choice making of international students, therefore, the TNE market information generation will not be accurate and valid. (University 1)

Based on the above notes regarding the responses generated from participants after asking them about how the university's international ranking position is related to TNE market information generation, they agreed on the positive relation between the two measures in both scenarios (whether the international ranking position is good or not). This enhances the findings from research by Koris and Nokelainen (2015). As described by some of the managers in their comments:

The good international ranking position of our university contributes positively on TNE market information generation. (University 1)

We increased our efforts regarding TNE market information generation to understand better the weaknesses that prevent our international ranking position improvement. (University 7)

While another had a different argument:

Good TNE market information can be collected from annual reports and number of research publications in good journals rather than international ranking position of a university. (University 3)

It seems from the responses regarding the extent to which the university's international ranking position impacts the dissemination of TNE market information, that in both cases, whether the university's international ranking is high or low, the TNE market information dissemination operates well. However, in the literature on universities' international ranking (Foroudi et al., 2019; James and Derrick, 2021), only a good international ranking position can motivate managers in terms of market information dissemination. The following statements describe this opinion:

If you ignore the ranking position of a university, it will affect the belongingness of managers to that university, but good dissemination of TNE market information is more effective when there is management of how work should be done, where managers are familiar with it. (Focus group 1)

The good international ranking position of this university facilitates TNE market information dissemination, as our personnel are highly satisfied about the outcomes of their efforts and proud to talk about issues related to TNE. (University 5)

I think the pressure that results from having a low international ranking position let key players of faculties/schools raise their capabilities to disseminate TNE market information more than a university with high international ranking position. (University 7)

It can be concluded that participants positively associate a university's international ranking position with TNE market information dissemination. This is consistent with İpek (2019), who asserts that the influence of universities' rankings extends to planning activities and decision-making. A manager from a low-ranked university position declared that it has a positive influence. Hence, managers from both high- or low-ranking universities consider market orientation in their TNE activities, contrary to the opinion of Zhou and Wu (2016) that universities can rely solely on their prestige and history. As described by a marketing manager:

High or low international ranking position of a university can positively support TNE market information dissemination. (University 5)

Regarding the extent to which university international ranking position influences TNE market information responsiveness, findings reflected the same opinions as for the influence of university international ranking position on TNE market information generation and dissemination (Christensen et al., 2018; Foroudi et al., 2019). This can be explained by the following managers' statements:

Our good international ranking position encourages our faculties/schools' managers to respond to the TNE market information to perform better and remain or improve our position in the ranking list. (University 2)

We increased our efforts regarding TNE market information responsiveness to satisfy international students and enhance our international ranking position, regardless of our ranking position. (University 7)

One TNE department manager posed a question concerning the relationship between ranking position and TNE market information responsiveness:

Considering ranking position might bring you several unrelated matters as there are different measures to rank universities, especially high ranked universities, that their name relates to top 10 universities in the world since the foundation of university ranking concept... thus how can ranking serve the TNE market information responsiveness? (University 8)

When asked how the university international ranking position is related to TNE market information responsiveness, participants also illustrate that both high or low international ranking positions increase TNE market information responsiveness. This, again, contradicts Zhou and Wu (2016), confirming that both scenarios can be a motive to practice market orientation in TNE activities. These statements reflect this fact:

Saving the good international ranking position of our university forces us to do better in terms of our TNE market information responsiveness. (University 2)

Being not among the top international ranking position can only give us an enthusiasm to focus more on responses for TNE market information. (University 7)

University international ranking position can be a motive for university marketing activities, whether the ranking is high or low, contrary to the literature where researchers state that there is a negative relationship between university ranking and market orientation (Asaad et al., 2013; Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016).

Meanwhile, a marketing manager said:

Responding to TNE market information should be consistent and the use of international ranking lists should reflect a consistent perception to international students or managers, however high or low, the international ranking position of universities does not deliver the good quality of all programmes taught by a university at different TNE partners' campuses. (Focus group 1)

Therefore, the university's international ranking position is detected to be positively linked to TNE market orientation.

5.2.2.3. Developed country higher education image perception

The perception toward the image of UK higher education was very similar; in line with Hemsley-Brown et al. (2016) and Jimenez-Castillo et al. (2013), participants unanimously perceive that the image of UK higher education is a source of high-quality knowledge, valuable degrees, it delivers qualified and desired graduates, and is the dream of many international students, which emphasises the common positive perception of the UK's higher education image. This explanation is a result of the following comments:

Our universities are a mechanism for social mobility that attracts people from everywhere. (University 1)

The British education has one of the highest qualities of teaching and courses worldwide, reasonable tuition fees, students and researchers receive good support, recognised degrees, graduates are highly wanted internationally. (University 5)

UK higher education, from the perception of participants, consists of the same factors that the literature highlighted (Baker and Ballington, 2011; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka, 2015a). This is related to comments of some participants.

Old universities such as Oxford and Cambridge are reflecting huge impact on the British higher education. (University 1)

Ranking position of British universities worldwide, advanced courses, great career opportunities for graduates. (University 3)

Quality of education and research, inventions, and technology development in different sectors. (University 6)

Regarding the extent to which marketing managers' perceived image of UK higher education affects TNE market information generation, participants describe that the positive image of UK higher education, as they perceive it, helps in the process of TNE market information generation, as described in the literature on higher education marketing (Bennell, 2022; Hailat et al., 2019). From the common responses:

Strong image of our higher education influences positively the choice of international students to participate in our research about TNE market, even if they are not our students. (University 3)

In line with the work of Acikdilli (2015) and Amaia et al. (2018), managers' perceptions about the UK higher education image and the generation of TNE market information seem to have a strong belief in the capabilities of UK higher education in terms of accomplishing marketing tasks such as TNE market information generation overseas. A marketing manager described this as follows:

Higher education image of the UK is influenced somehow by the image of the country itself as it is one of the leading countries, leaving no room for the difference between London School of Economic and London School of Commerce. This supports our marketing activities abroad such as generating information about TNE. (University 5)

Regarding marketing managers' perceived image of UK higher education and how it affects TNE market information dissemination, participants were congruent with Koris et al. (2015), arguing that the strong image of UK higher education is an advantage or motivation to

marketing managers in their efforts to disseminate TNE market information. This fact is clarified by the following statements:

Our belongingness to a satisfying higher education counts as an advantage that increases our self-esteem and makes the process of THE market information dissemination more effective. (Group 2)

The reality that image of the UK higher education is highly favourable motivates our working spirit, especially when it is related to share information about our TNE activities to international students ... we use our higher education image for the positive perception it has. (University 7)

Consistent with Palfreyman and Tapper (2016), the perceived UK higher education image and its relationship to the dissemination of TNE market information, based on participants' responses, was regarded to have a positive relationship. An international partnership development manager and marketing manager said:

Positive perception towards UK higher education image reflects positive attitude, therefore disseminating TNE market information either between university personnel or to international students will be very smooth. (University 2)

For keeping the good image of our higher education, marketing managers attempt to respond to TNE market information in our university quickly. (University 3)

Participants tend to link the perceived UK higher education image from marketing managers to its effects on TNE market information responsiveness. They illustrated that the ideal image of UK higher education strengthens their ability to respond to TNE market information. This supports the hypothesis of perceived higher education country image and EMO (Asaad et al., 2013). The following statements confirm this:

For retaining of our higher education good image, marketing managers attempt to respond to TNE market information in our university quickly. (University 2)

Its effect increases the level of how managers respond to TNE market information. (University 3)

Also, in line with Naidoo and Williams (2015), participants were clear that the positive link between the perceived UK higher education image in their universities and TNE market information responsiveness is based on protecting or maintaining the higher education image perception. The comments of some participants were as follows:

Positive perception towards UK higher education image creates between managers the spirit of assuming responsibility to protect this perception, hence TNE market information responsiveness is one of the means of protection. (Focus group 4)

The good perception of the UK higher education image increases enthusiasm to focus more on responses for TNE market information. (University 7)

Therefore, the above findings of this section are in line with the literature review (Asaad et al., 2013; He et al., 2018; Sidhu and Henderson et al., 2017), and help to confirm the positive link between developed country higher education image and TNE market information responsiveness.

5.2.2.4. University international ranking position and developed country higher education image perception

Concerning the prospect of a link between university international ranking position and developed country higher education image perception, in accordance with Koris et al. (2015), interviewees expressed the suitable extent of influence between them. They were positive about the UK higher education image through the intangible support received from their international ranking position. The following comments describe this concept:

We believe that the increase of international ranking positioning of UK universities supports the perception of UK higher education image to remain valuable. (University 6)

Ranking is related to the image perception of the university then higher education. A higher education's image perception represents its position based on the history of university as it is perceived by international students... international students when they think about the UK universities, they perceive Oxford university as a landmark of the UK higher education based on its history and ranking position. (University 7)

Participants also confirm the positive influence of the university international ranking position on UK higher education image perception through the following statements:

The international ranking positions of UK universities is one of the fundamental factors that intervene the determination of the UK higher education image perception. (University 3)

The good international ranking position of famous UK universities such as University of Oxford and many others increases the image of the UK higher education. (University 4)

The long and increasing presence of numerous UK universities in the international ranking list of universities helps to store our higher education in the minds of higher education stakeholders including international students, then results in a positive perception of the UK higher education image. (University 5)

In line with the literature (Hailat et al., 2019; Mac and Evangelist, 2016; Warwick, 2014), respondents confirm the link between the two constructs and the positive impact of university international ranking position on developed country higher education image perception.

5.2.3. Consequences of TNE market orientation

5.2.3.1. Determinants of TNE market orientation: Higher education international reputation

The shared views of participants in interviews or focus groups demonstrate a good understanding of the participants' aspects related to the international reputation of higher education and their agreement with the marketing literature description (Bastedo and Bowman, 2010; Maisuria and Cole, 2017; Menendez and Castilla, 2021). Whereas respondents confirm that international higher education reputation is a result of what overseas partners and international students are experiencing from the UK higher education as follows:

It is possible to be a good collector of effective TNE market information to guarantee the balance of TNE quality; generating TNE market information could serve international reputation of UK higher education if you collected it right. For instance,

collecting TNE market information from the right people at the right time makes the difference for international students. (University 3)

The international reputation of UK higher education was not built overnight; quality education, research, and inventions are part of our priority to deliver good experience to international students. (University 2)

All UK universities attempt to do their best to satisfy international students or partners, which contributes to support the outcomes of UK higher education, and this can be felt through the domination of UK universities in exporting higher education. (Group 1)

Also, participants clarified that among the factors contributing to the current international reputation of UK higher education is the significant effort that UK universities invest in marketing. This can be linked to the work of Foroudi et al. (2019c) in university reputation literature. A management and planning team manager said:

We cannot deny the significant role and efforts of the marketing managers of UK universities to keep the reputation of our higher education very popular worldwide. (Group 1)

When asked to what extent TNE market information generation in their university affects the UK higher education international reputation, participants commonly see that good practice of TNE market information generation allows universities to gauge how UK higher education reputation is faring internationally. This perception was compatible with Czinkota et al. (2014) and Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013). A TNE manager responded to this question as follows:

TNE market information generation supplies important information about how UK higher education is perceived by our international students. However, it is hard to control as it is a result of collective output of all UK universities but effective for quick interventions. (University 1)

Responses to the question asking how TNE market information generation in your university is related to the UK higher education international reputation, as a positive fact, help to determine countries that need more focus to raise our reputation with them, confirming the

literature findings (Bastedo and Bowman, 2010; Espeland and Sauder, 2016). The second focus group said:

The information collected from TNE students (by UK universities) can tell truth on how UK higher education is considered overseas, helping us detect countries that do not consider our higher education as highly reputed. Hence, work to increase our reputation in countries where level of reputation is low. (Focus group 2)

When asked to what extent TNE market information dissemination in their university affects the UK higher education international reputation, according to their experience with UK higher education, respondents demonstrated that the effective approach of sharing TNE market information has a favourable influence on the international reputation of UK higher education (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012). The following responses reflect their opinions:

The head of our international office applies a good practice regarding TNE market information dissemination with several key players in the university, which increases the opportunities to solve issues related to reputation overseas quickly. (University 5)

It may maximise chances to increase the international reputation of UK higher education. (University 7)

For the question asking how TNE market information dissemination in their university is related to UK higher education international reputation, interviewees correlated them based on the advanced awareness of international students' opinions about UK higher education through TNE market information dissemination (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012). An international partnership development manager said:

TNE market information dissemination increases our personnel awareness of different matters such as international reputation of the UK higher education, hence if managers are conscious ahead of a matter, then they will call for an emergency meeting to discuss and find solutions. Also, good internal TNE market information dissemination can positively advance solving problems related to UK higher education international reputation, while the external dissemination of our good TNE market information

through marketing can positively influence the international students' opinion regarding the UK higher education reputation. (University 2)

When asked to what extent TNE market information responsiveness in their university affects the UK higher education international reputation, as mentioned in the literature (Healey, 2015; Dwyer, 2022), a marketing manager replied:

The head of our international office applies a good practice regarding TNE market information dissemination with several key players in the university, which increases the opportunities to solve issues related to reputation overseas quickly. (University 8)

The increase of international students' enrolment during the previous five years and the expansion of our TNE programmes and courses overseas are results of how effectively we respond to TNE market information and confirm the extent to which international students are satisfied about our higher education; this influences positively their perception of the UK higher education reputation. (University 5)

For the question asking how TNE market information responsiveness in their university is related to the UK higher education international reputation, participants, through similar answers, agreed that actions of universities to satisfy their stakeholders of TNE benefit the UK higher education international reputation indirectly (Cadogan et al., 2012; Healey, 2015). The following statement by a management and planning team manager reflects the view of other participants:

On a small scale, responding to TNE market information aims to serve our university reputation, but this fact reflects positively on the international reputation of the UK higher education as well. (University 3)

From the above comments and in line with the literature (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012; Foroudi et al., 2019; Healey, 2015), an understanding is developed about the role of TNE market orientation in the higher education international reputation relationship. Therefore, the literature and qualitative results support the view that TNE market orientation has a positive relationship with higher education international reputation.

5.2.3.2. Determinants of TNE market orientation: TNE business performance

Participants perceive TNE business performance as a result of the various efforts applied by universities to enhance the delivery of TNE in a manner that increases its demand (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2016). The following statement by an international partnership development manager reflects the views of other participants:

TNE business performance is the results of universities success to establish several strategies to deliver knowledge under different types of TNE and programmes for international students outside of its main campus, then maintain to attract more students and educational partners. It is also a measurement of the university values and capabilities regarding TNE. (University 2)

Participants agreed that the effectiveness of good practice in TNE market orientation can positively impact UK TNE business performance, as illustrated in the literature by Cadogan et al. (2009), Asaad et al. (2013), and Hailat et al. (2019). The following comments describe the views of participants from focus groups and interviews:

Good and efficient practice of all TNE market orientation components can help achieve TNE business performance dramatically. (Focus group 2)

I think yes, as the components of TNE market orientation address fundamental aspect that can support the students' and partners' satisfaction then TNE practice. (University 7)

Regarding the impact of TNE market information generation in their university on TNE business performance, participants commonly believe that good practice in TNE market information generation leads the university to expand its TNE activities and pay maximum attention to matters related to TNE programmes, competitors' activities, and international students' needs (Chung, 2012; Palfreyman and Tapper, 2016; Mac and Evangelist, 2016). The main response was:

The market information we generate about TNE changes the old concept of how we affect the orientation of international students' decision towards our higher education

programmes causing an increase of international attention to our TNE and increases our opportunity to remain active in TNE markets. (University 1)

For the question asking how TNE market information generation in your university is related to TNE business performance, participants illustrate that it is involved in the development and management of TNE strategies and problem-solving, as described in previous research (Murray et al., 2007; Kleibert, 2023; Wilkins and Huisman, 2021). The following statements describe this concept:

The generated TNE market information helps in our calculation towards courses we design and the selection of educational partnerships overseas. (University 5)

The surveys we undertake of our international students indicate a high satisfaction on our TNE, therefore, TNE market information generation is a measurement of TNE business performance. (University 6)

... with the continuous information we collect about TNE from international students or our partners, the achievement of our set targets for TNE partnership or in terms of the number of international students enrolled in our TNE programmes increased and contributes to our TNE business performance satisfaction. (University 8)

When questioning to what extent TNE market information dissemination in your university affects TNE business performance, respondents were in close agreement, as their belief in the significant role of TNE market information dissemination for the success of TNE business was similar to that of researchers such as He and Wei (2011), Chung (2012), and Warwick (2014). The following phrases reflect this fact:

The dissemination of TNE market information contributes between our university and its TNE partners to have a similar background concerning objectives, needs and issues of TNE, which stimulates the chance of a significant development of TNE business performance. (University 1)

It allows a control out of the whole TNE activities either among the university TNE management or with TNE partners, linking events, preparing for potential crisis, coordinating plans, and sharing opportunities or threats. (University 2)

Transnational education business performance is an outcome of marketing activities that our managers perform in different foreign markets. (University 3)

For the question that asks how TNE market information dissemination in your university is related to TNE business performance, interviewees link them through the added value that TNE market information dissemination offers and the mutual support between all departments involved in TNE, as described in the literature (Chung, 2012; Kleibert, 2023). This was described as follows:

Good TNE market information dissemination practice adds value to the work of our TNE personnel or partners' personnel, by balancing their knowledge concerning TNE market information and keeps all parties updated to TNE market news. (University 2)

We work on TNE market information dissemination the way that would enable every department to assist the knowledge of the other departments concerning TNE development; this can eliminate time wasting, offer diversified thinking, and shed light on TNE matters or opportunities well ahead. (University 4)

The collaboration found between our marketing managers, international officers, and TNE managers leaves no space for conflict among them and supports the flow of information, making plans and targets much easier to achieve. (University 8)

When questioning the extent to which TNE market information responsiveness in your university affects TNE business performance, an international marketing manager replied:

The responsiveness to TNE market information helps to extend our presence in the TNE market and enhances our opportunities to maintain the delivery of our British TNE programmes overseas with an increase in international students' enrolment. The more our responses meet the market needs, the better are our opportunities for British TNE business performance. (University 5)

Participants from a focus group also argued that:

The effective responsiveness to TNE market information influences our alumni and leads to an increase in numbers of intakes and the enrolled international students. (Focus group 2)

For the question about how TNE market information responsiveness in your university is related to TNE business performance, participants echoed sentiments consistent with previous research (Chung, 2012; Mac and Evangelist, 2016; Kleibert, 2023), expressing shared perceptions. This was illustrated by an international partnership development manager:

Having more than two intakes and TNE partners in all continents is a result of several improvements that we have done to our TNE curriculums, teaching methodology, research, and publications. (University 4)

Responding to TNE market information can ameliorate the outcomes of our TNE practice, including increase of enrolment volume and revenues, where a large part of the enrolment comes from our alumni. This describes the satisfaction of international students and therefore affects positively the satisfaction of our university on TNE business performance. (University 5)

The findings support the positive relationship between TNE market orientation and TNE business performance in UK universities, as described in Chapter 3.

5.2.3.3 Higher education international reputation and TNE business performance

Concerning the link between higher education international reputation and TNE business performance, interviewees, when asked about the extent of influence and relationship between them, demonstrated a significant impact:

The good reputation of UK higher education internationally increases the number of our intakes related to TNE programmes, as in addition to the two biggest intakes of September and January we implement other intakes to satisfy the demand of all students' applicants. This fact contributes to our growth in the TNE market. (University 6)

In our university we do take advantage of the strong international reputation of famous UK universities as it reflects positively on the whole UK higher education, hence it facilitates our TNE marketing activities to increase the volume of TNE students' enrolment and our revenues in general. (University 7)

In line with the literature (Kumar et al., 2011; Gouvea et al., 2013), most participants also confirm the positive influence of higher education international reputation on TNE business performance through the following statements:

International students when they apply to study in our university, the majority mention in the section of how you heard about us that either through family/friends or Google search and both are the result of UK higher education international reputation, which contributes to our satisfaction as managers and encourages us to use it more in our marketing for better performance. (University 2)

The UK higher education international reputation is one of the intangible elements that adds support to new UK universities in terms of marketing, using the phrase of the UK higher education, UK flag, or any famous British icon is enough to attract the attention of our targeted segment from international students towards our TNE programmes. (University 5)

While one of the focus groups had a different opinion:

The reputation of the UK higher education attracts the attention of international students, but we cannot confirm that all the UK universities that shape the higher education of this country are reputedly equal. (Focus group 4)

In agreement with the literature (Kumar et al., 2011; Molesworth et al., 2011; Vangelis et al., 2018), interviewees confirm the link between the two constructs and the positive impact of higher education international reputation on TNE business performance.

5.3. SUMMARY

This chapter elucidates the analysis and findings derived from the interviews and focus groups. The qualitative research conducted in this study aimed to fulfil the objectives by fostering a comprehensive understanding of TNE market orientation and its ramifications on higher education international reputation and TNE business performance, while also addressing the research question. The analysis and results encompass all pertinent themes identified in the literature review. Thus, both the literature review and the qualitative study played integral roles in crafting the framework model delineating the determinants and execution of TNE market orientation.

CHAPTER 6: DATA ANALYSIS

6.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter aims to achieve the research objectives by analysing and detecting the links between the dependent and independent variables. Chapter 4, which focuses on research methodology, details all the steps planned to complete this thesis, with a significant portion devoted to the research methods used. Additionally, it targets the experimental analysis supporting the project and outlines the results of research based on the major study represented in the preceding chapters. Section 6.2 describes the stages of preparing, editing, coding, and screening the gathered data. Section 6.3 interprets linearity, normality, multicollinearity, and outliers of the gathered data. Non-response bias is illustrated in Section 6.4. Section 6.5 explains the use of confirmatory analysis to reassess the resulting solutions. Structural equation modelling (SEM) is discussed in Section 6.6 to test the hypothesized links among the project constructs as presumed in the conceptual framework and to appraise the overall compatibility among the suggested conceptual model and the gathered data. Finally, Section 6.7 contains the chapter summary.

6.2. THE MAJOR SURVEY

The main purpose of conducting the survey in this study was to gather data for additional hypothesis testing and scale purification. Table 6.1 provides the demographic characteristics, showing that the majority of participants were from universities in England (75.9%), followed by those from Scotland and Northern Ireland (14.9%), and Wales (9.2%). The most popular modes of TNE were Franchised programmes (78.57%), Top-up programmes (78.57%), and Joint degrees (72.32%). Asia and Africa together represented the highest destinations for TNE, accounting for 43.5% of participants. Among the participants, those who declared having TNE partnerships with 51 to 100 countries represented the highest proportion, at 41.1%.

Additionally, 22 participants (6.5%) represented universities ranked among the top 100 worldwide. A significant majority, 88.7% of participants, held a positive perception towards their universities' international ranking position. While the largest portion of participants came from the international office department (35.7%), with the majority being international officers (21.7%), 60.7% of participants had 10 years of experience or less. Furthermore, 40.5% of participants represented universities aged 31 to 99 years, and 60.1% of universities were represented by participants with 11 to 20 years of experience in TNE.

Table 6.1: Demographic profile of this study's participants compared to sample size (N=336)

Sample size (N)	N	%
Participated university localisation		
England	255	75.9
Scotland & Northern Ireland	50	14.9
Wales	31	9.2
Transnational education modes		
Franchised programme partnership	264	78.57
Top-up programme partnership	264	78.57
Joint degree partnership	243	72.32
Validation or quality assurance programme	237	70.53
Distance/online learning with no local support	215	64
Double dual or multiple degree partnership	195	58
Distance/online learning with local support	120	35
Distance/online learning blended	96	28.57
Branch campus	42	12.5
Study centre	40	11.90
Flying faculty or outreach	39	11.60
Destination of transnational education		
Asia; Africa	116	34.5
Europe; Asia; Africa	94	28.0
Asia	59	17.6
Europe; Asia; Africa; North America; South America	26	7.7
Europe; Asia;	15	4.5
Europe; Asia; Africa; North America	12	3.6
Europe; Asia; Africa; South America	8	2.4
Asia; Africa; South America	4	1.2
Asia; Africa; North America; South America	2	0.6
Number of countries with TNE partnership		
50 countries or less	84	25
51 to 100 countries	138	41.1
Over 100 countries	114	33.9
University international ranking position		
Top 100 universities	22	6.5
Between 101-400	112	33.3
Over 401	202	60.2
Participants' perception towards international		

ranking position of their universities		
Positive	298	88.7
Negative	38	11.3
Departments involved in study		
International office	120	35.7
Marketing department	62	18.5
Admission team	47	14.0
TNE quality assurance department	39	11.6
TNE partnership department	31	9.2
International students' recruitment	21	6.3
Business development	16	4.8
Participants' position		
International officer	73	21.7
Marketing manager	61	18.2
TNE partnership manager	38	11.3
Admission manager	34	10.1
Students' recruitment officer	28	8.3
Regional manager	22	6.6
Global business development manager	21	6.3
TNE development manager	16	4.8
Head of international student recruitment	14	4.2
Assistant marketing manager	9	2.7
TNE quality assurance manager	8	2.4
Head of international office	8	2.4
Head of TNE development	4	1.2
Participants' experience		
10 years or less	204	60.7
11 to 15 years	115	34.2
Over 16 years	17	5.1
University Age		
30 years or less	65	19.3
31 to 99 years old	136	40.5
Over 100 years old	135	40.2

University experience in TNE		
10 years or less	33	9.8
11 to 20 years	202	60.1
21 to 29 years	62	18.5
Over 30	39	11.6

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

6.2.1. PREPARING DATA

6.2.1.1. The coding and editing of data

An examination process was applied to the collected data, and every item was coded before being imported into the SPSS software (De Vaus, 2002; Kumar, 2019; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Thereafter, data editing was conducted to ensure that the coding process had been completed properly. Moreover, values that were detected as out of range were double-checked.

6.2.1.2. The sample's data screening and characteristics

The researcher conducted pre-analysis data screening to ensure that the fundamental analysis would be impartial and able to produce effective outcomes from the gathered data (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). The data cleaning and screening processes included checks for missing responses and inconsistencies (Malhotra, 2017). The researcher followed the steps of data screening as outlined by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), with the screening data being used prior to conducting multivariate analysis. Firstly, the accuracy of the gathered data and consideration of factors may result in distorted correlations. The researcher assessed and addressed incomplete data through screening for missing data. All collected data were checked to remove questionnaires with poor-quality responses or substantive missing data and values before analysis. Then, the researcher assessed the effect of extreme values on the analysis.

6.2.1.3. Analysis of missing data

The first step of missing data analysis was assessing the gathered data from the main survey for missing values. The results of data analysis can be affected by missing data, which can then cause problems with reliability and validity (Field, 2013). Any patterns in the missing data should be identified to address possible bias. Ignorable missing data refers to cases where the observed values represent a random sample of all values, observed and explicitly or implicitly missing, accommodated in the employed technique.

The use of the SPSS missing value analysis process through the techniques of Expectation-Maximization (EM) reveals no missing data either at the levels of items or constructs (Appendix 6.1). Therefore, the research did not need to test any patterns or remedies to solve the problem of missing data. This fact emphasizes the effectiveness of the questionnaire, as it was well understood by participants and compatible with their work circumstances.

6.3. THE NORMALITY, OUTLIERS, LINEARITY, AND MULTI-COLLINEARITY ASSESSMENT

6.3.1. Examination of normality assumption

A normality test, conducted after coding the data, was applied to verify that the normality assumption had not been violated. In multivariate analysis, normality is considered a fundamental assumption, especially in SEM. The graphical technique known as the normal probability plot is used to assess whether the dataset is approximately normally distributed (Foroudi et al., 2021a; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Malhotra et al., 2017).

The distribution of values, as observed through visual inspection of figures (Appendix 6.2), indicates that the range of variables was clustered along a straight line. Thus, there is no need for amendment to the sample observations during the transformation process. Moreover, the normal probability plot was used to evaluate multivariate normality, which was found to be normal as well based on Figure 6.1. Additionally, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk (K-S) methods were employed to determine if the distribution deviates from a normal distribution (Hair et al., 2012). The K-S test reflects a lower distance assessment and is employed as a non-parametric test of one-dimensional probability distribution equality.

Figure 6.1 Multivariate normal P-P plot of regression standardised residual

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistics were applied to constructs (Table 6.2) and items (Appendix 6.3) in this study. The assumption of the K-S test indicates that the outputs were not tenable at either level (item or construct). The volatility of the K-S test is widely recognized in data from large samples (Shiu et al., 2009; Foroudi et al., 2021a).

Table 6.2: The normality test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov(a)			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
TMG_TOTAL	.349	336	.000	.624	336	.000
TMD_TOTAL	.363	336	.000	.608	336	.000
TMR_TOTAL	.370	336	.000	.583	336	.000
TC_TOTAL	.344	336	.000	.620	336	.000
UIRP_TOTAL	.333	336	.000	.642	336	.000
DHIP_TOTAL	.374	336	.000	.595	336	.000
HIR_TOTAL	.354	336	.000	.614	336	.000
TBP_TOTAL	.384	336	.000	.581	336	.000

A Lilliefors significance correction

Jarque-Bera (skewness and kurtosis) is another method employed as an essential component of normality assessment. Skewness measures the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a real-valued random variable. A positively skewed variable translates to a distribution where most values are concentrated on the left side, away from the distribution centre (Foroudi et al., 2021a; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Skewness is used to assess the balance of the distribution and the extent to which the data are non-balanced, with most scores clustered in one portion of the distribution and fewer outliers in the distribution tail (Foroudi et al., 2021a).

When skewness and kurtosis values are zero, they represent a normal distribution (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). However, when cases pile up to the right with a very long left tail, the skewness is negative (Hair et al., 2016). Kurtosis values below zero illustrate a distribution that is too flat (with many cases in the tails), while values above zero indicate a peaked distribution with short and thick tails. Non-normal kurtosis leads to a variance undervalue of the variable, but positive or negative kurtosis and skewness are acceptable as long as they fall within the ordinary range. Similarly, positive or negative values of kurtosis and skewness reflect the essential nature of the measured constructs (Shiu et al., 2009; Foroudi et al., 2021a). In this stage of analysis, variables satisfied the ideal values (i.e., $< \pm 3$) of kurtosis and skewness (Hair et al., 2016) (Appendix 6.4).

6.3.2. Outliers: testing univariate and multivariate

The examination of constructs reveals both multivariate and univariate outliers. The researcher identifies univariate outliers by converting all scores for a variable to standard scores. In relation to univariate outliers, the rule of thumb suggests that a case is considered an outlier when the sample size is greater than 80 cases (336), and the outlier is identified with a standard score of ± 3.0 or beyond (Hair et al., 2016; Foroudi et al., 2021a). This rule of thumb is valid for ordinal and interval level variables, which are referred to as metric, but it does not apply to variables of nominal level.

Several univariate outliers were detected during the analysis conducted. Therefore, the researcher decided to exclude outliers from the subsequent analysis. Univariate outliers were identified by grouping items together to form one construct. Using the descriptive statistics function of SPSS, the data values for each observation were transformed into standardised scores (z-scores) (Hair et al., 2016; Foroudi et al., 2021a). Table 6.3 illustrates several univariate outliers based on the dataset of this research; specifically, constructs TMR and TBP contain the highest number of outliers (three each), while constructs TC and UIRP contain only one outlier each.

Table 6.3: Univariate outliers

S.NO	Variable	Case of outlier	Standardised values i.e., z-scores > ± 3.0
1	TMG (TNE marketing generation)	31	-3.14111
		334	-3.05992
2	TMR (TNE marketing responsiveness)	307	-3.17864
		322	-3.00159
		309	-3.00159
	TC	237	-3.35861
	UIRP	256	-3.10734
	TBP (TNE business performance)	167	-3.23674
		169	-3.23674
		158	-3.07046

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

The method of linear regression was employed in this study to compute the Mahalanobis D2 value. The significance t-value was obtained using SPSS 25 with the function '1-CDF.CHISQ(quant, df)', where df=13 and quant=D2. The results identified 39 observations with significant outliers in the sample of 336, where $p < 0.005$ (Table 6.4). Additionally, multivariate outliers were detected using a Box Plot (Figure 6.3), where all observations fell within the mild outlier range (i.e., interquartile range (IQR) > 1.5) (Hair et al., 2016). Therefore, after observing the results of univariate and multivariate analyses (Table 6.3 and Appendix 6.5), the observed outliers were retained by the researcher for the following stage.

Figure 6.2: Box-plot representing multivariate outliers

6.3.3. Linearity and multi-collinearity

The Pearson's correlation matrix is employed at the 2-tailed (0.01 significance level) to determine the multicollinearity and linearity of TNE market orientation, revealing considerably positive correlations between independent variables and dependent variables (Table 6.5).

The test's outcomes illustrate that variables are linearly related to each other (Figure 6.3). Through Pearson's correlation, the bivariate correlation matrix was calculated. Table 6.4 represents the results of the correlation matrix, which confirm that all variable correlations were not highly correlated (i.e., $=$ or > 0.90) with each other (Hair et al., 2016), fulfilling the multicollinearity assumption. Multicollinearity can be checked by verifying the tolerance effect and the scores of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Multicollinearity is detected when the VIF is larger than 10 and the tolerance is below 0.1 (Shiu et al., 2009; Foroudi et al., 2021a).

Table 6.4: Correlation matrix and descriptive statistics for every construct

	TMG	TMD	TMR	TC	UIRP	DHIP	HIR	TBP
TMG	1							
TMD	.760**	1						
TMR	.804**	.817**	1					
TC	.763**	.756**	.779**	1				
UIRP	.739**	.728**	.744**	.732**	1			
DHIP	.795**	.791**	.805**	.788**	.731**	1		
HIR	.806**	.800**	.810**	.777**	.756**	.804**	1	
TBR	.787**	.776**	.793**	.789**	.735**	.799**	.807**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (Pearson correlation sig. (2-tailed)).

Figure 6.3: Transnational education market orientation constructs scatter plot matrix

Source: Analysis of survey data

The researcher utilised a multiple regression procedure and the collinearity diagnostic option to calculate the VIF and tolerance effects. Table 6.5 shows that none of the constructs violate the assumptions of tolerance or multicollinearity. Therefore, there is no need to delete any variables at this stage.

Table 6.5: Regression to observe tolerance and VIF effect

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-.705	1.694		-.416	.677		
TCTOTAL	.177	.076	.122	2.320	.021	.279	3.584
UIRPTOTAL	.232	.077	.141	3.003	.003	.353	2.832
DHIPTOTAL	.308	.073	.232	4.232	.000	.256	3.899
HIRTOTAL	.362	.075	.270	4.819	.000	.246	4.061
TBPTOTAL	.188	.057	.184	3.314	.001	.252	3.974

a. Dependent Variable: TMGTOTAL

6.3.4. Homoscedasticity/homogeneity

For computing the variance of metric variables, the researcher used Levene’s test, which is considered equal across a non-metric variable (university location). The Levene’s test, as shown in Table 6.6, is not significant (above 0.05), indicating no difference between variances. Levene’s test, along with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests, is believed to be sensitive in relation to sample size; it might be significant in large samples (Field, 2009). Thus, in this study, which includes a sample of 336, the homogeneity of Levene’s test supported the outcomes of the variability between independent and dependent variables.

Table 6.6: Test of homogeneity of variance (Levene’s test)

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
TMG	2.834	11	324	.001
TMD	3.493	11	324	.000
TMR	4.558	11	324	.000
TC	3.101	11	324	.001
UIRP	2.056	11	324	.023
DHIP	6.988	11	324	.000
HIR	4.742	11	324	.000
TBR	5.358	11	324	.000

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

6.4. NON-RESPONSE BIASNESS

The non-response bias probability was calculated by evaluating how the Mann-Whitney U-test among late and early respondents differs from the means of every variable (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012) (see Table 6.7). The questionnaires were returned based on the following proportion: the first 50 observations were considered as the early respondents, while the final 50 to be returned were considered as late respondents. The significance value in all variables is above 0.5 probability value (insignificant), thus the early and late respondents show no major statistical difference. Therefore, there is no concern about non-response bias.

Table 6.7: Observing non-response biasness through Mann-Whitney U-test

	TMG_TOTAL	TMD_TOTAL	TMD_TOTAL	TC_TOTAL
Mann-Whitney U	557.000	647.500	710.000	778.000
Wilcoxon W	857.000	947.500	1010.000	1078.000
Z	-2.152	-1.328	-.752	-.129
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.031	.184	.452	.898
	UIRP_TOTAL	DHIP_TOTAL	HIR_TOTAL	TBP_TOTAL
Mann-Whitney U	764.000	705.000	776.000	677.500
Wilcoxon W	1064.000	1005.000	2987.000	977.500
Z	-.257	-.800	-.147	-1.053
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.797	.424	.883	.292

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

6.5. DATA ANALYSIS AND FACTOR LOADING

The factors or underlying variables were identified using the statistical approach of factor analysis (FA) to determine the pattern of relationships among a range of studied variables. This approach is commonly employed to reduce data and identify several factors that explain the observed variances in manifest variables with much larger numbers (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

6.5.1. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

The researcher conducted exploratory factor analysis (EFA) for items generated from the literature and qualitative study (interviews). Initially, EFA was employed to examine 58 items linked to TNE market orientation, contributing to eight constructs. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure, as indicated in Table 6.8, is 0.982 (above 0.6, indicating accepted sampling adequacy). Additionally, Bartlett's test of sphericity (BTS) met the required criteria (BTS = <0.001) and was significant (Malhotra et al., 2017). Eigenvalues, or latent roots, illustrate the number of variances considered for a variable. Every variable with a component analysis variance that contributes to a principal factor extraction (one or above) is considered significant (Hair et al., 2016; Field, 2013; Malhotra et al., 2017) and then disregarded (Hair et al., 2013, p. 120). The results indicate five factors with eigenvalues higher than one, and the loading of items is separately loaded in various components. The following items were removed in the second part of EFA (i.e., with cross-loading): TMD_3, TMR_8, UIRP_4, HIR_3, and TBP_2).

Table 6.8: KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy. .982	
Approx. chi-square	17890.283
df	1596
Sig.	.000

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

A communality value exceeding 0.6 was achieved for all the retained variables in the factor loading (Table 6.9). The results also illustrate high variation among the variables, ranging from 0.662 to 0.778. Therefore, all items, without exception, share communalities above 0.6 with their components, indicating a good fit of items compared to the others in the same components (Hair et al., 2016).

Table 6.9: The shared communalities by individual items

Variables	Initial	Extract	Variable	Initial	Extrac	Variable	Initial	Extrac
		ion	s		tion	s		tion
TMG_1	1.000	.759	TMR_9	1.000	.696	HIR_7	1.000	.733
TMG_2	1.000	.767	TMR_11	1.000	.736	HIR_6	1.000	.721
TMG_3	1.000	.704	TC_1	1.000	.714	HIR_7	1.000	.743
TMG_4	1.000	.756	TC_3	1.000	.731	TBP_1	1.000	.735
TMG_5	1.000	.745	TC_4	1.000	.690	TBP_2	1.000	.701
TMG_6	1.000	.755	TC_5	1.000	.659	TBP_3	1.000	.739
TMG_7	1.000	.711	TC_6	1.000	.711	TBP_4	1.000	.754
TMG_8	1.000	.736	TC_7	1.000	.739	TBP_5	1.000	.735
TMG_9	1.000	.731	TC_8	1.000	.666	TBP_6	1.000	.704
TMD_1	1.000	.744	UIRP_1	1.000	.741	TBP_7	1.000	.755
TMD_2	1.000	.752	UIRP_2	1.000	.720	TBP_9	1.000	.758
TMD_3	1.000	.744	UIRP_3	1.000	.697			
TMD_4	1.000	.732	UIRP_5	1.000	.755			
TMD_6	1.000	.712	UIRP_6	1.000	.772			
TMD_7	1.000	.749	DHIP_1	1.000	.775			
TMD_8	1.000	.781	DHIP_2	1.000	.687			
TMR_1	1.000	.683	DHIP_4	1.000	.738			
TMR_2	1.000	.671	DHIP_6	1.000	.772			
TMR_3	1.000	.732	DHIP_7	1.000	.734			
TMR_4	1.000	.692	DHIP_8	1.000	.753			
TMR_5	1.000	.689	HIR_1	1.000	.736			
TMR_6	1.000	.724	HIR_2	1.000	.719			
TMR_7	1.000	.699	HIR_3	1.000	.740			

Extraction method: principal component analysis.

Table 6.11 presents the total variance explained by all components. Only significant factors with eigenvalues >1 were retained, while the rest were disregarded (Hair et al., 2012; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Eight components with eigenvalues above one were identified through principal component analysis. The highest variance, 58.010%, was observed in TMG, while the lowest variance extracted by items into a construct was 1.726% in HIR (Table 6.10). A total variance of 72.9% is reflected by the range of eight components, as shown in the cumulative % column, which exceeds the recommendations (Hair et al., 2016; Foroudi et al., 2021a).

The third method used to determine the number of factors was the Scree test. The scree plot, a graphical measurement, assisted the researcher in identifying the optimal number of factors by examining eigenvalues to identify the extraction factors. The number of factors determines the position of plot levels, following a linear decreasing pattern. The eigenvalues associated with the Scree test were plotted against the factors and order of extraction, with the cut-off point evaluated based on the shape of the emerging curve (Hair et al., 2016). The negative decrease of the Scree plot indicates that the first factor and moderate factors have the highest eigenvalues, which then decrease for the following few factors, with the remaining factors achieving lower values (Field, 2013).

Table 6.10: Explanation of total variance

Component	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
		ce	%		ce	ive %		Variance	%
1	32.870	57.667	57.667	6.982	12.248	12.248	32.870	57.667	57.667
2	1.517	2.662	60.329	6.049	10.612	22.861	1.517	2.662	60.329
3	1.490	2.615	62.944	6.049	10.612	33.472	1.490	2.615	62.944
4	1.309	2.296	65.240	5.348	9.383	42.855	1.309	2.296	65.240
5	1.189	2.086	67.326	4.940	8.667	51.522	1.189	2.086	67.326
6	1.131	1.983	69.309	4.306	7.555	59.076	1.131	1.983	69.309
7	1.016	1.782	71.092	4.055	7.113	66.190	1.016	1.782	71.092
8	1.001	1.756	72.848	3.795	6.658	72.848	1.001	1.756	72.848
9	.647	1.135	73.983						
10	.606	1.062	75.045						
11	.588	1.031	76.076						
12	.575	1.010	77.085						
13	.562	.985	78.071						

Extraction method: Principal component analysis (57 items were examined, however, the table presents only 13 observations).

According to Hair et al. (2012), “starting with the first factor, the plot slopes steeply downward initially and then slowly becomes an approximately horizontal line. The point at which the curve first begins to straighten out is considered to indicate the maximum number of factors to extract” (p. 121). The scree plot test (Figure 6.4) confirms, via eigenvalues, the extracted

factors, with the number of factors confirmed using KMO's latent root criteria (i.e., eigenvalue greater than 1). The curve in the scree plot clearly breaks down between components seven and nine, where from component one to eight, the curve explains the variance deeply compared to the rest of the components.

Determining the most appropriate loading for every variable toward every factor is essential (Hair et al., 2016; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). To ensure effective factor loading in a research sample size of 336 (n=336 TNE marketing managers of UK universities), the suitable factor loading was set at 0.5 and greater at the significance level of 0.05 (Hair et al., 2016). According to Churchill's 1979 recommendation, items with a factor loading below 0.4 should be deleted. The results and the rotated component matrix of the scale illustrate that the loading of items is robust across eight factors, with a range between 0.543 and 0.96, satisfying the minimum criteria of factor loading (Churchill, 1979; Foroudi et al., 2021a; Hair et al., 2016; Shiu et al., 2009) (Table 6.11). Additionally, Cronbach's α is calculated to assess the correspondence of all components with their relevant items (Cronbach, 1951).

Figure 6.4: Scree plot of all dimensions

Five items were excluded from different constructs either due to cross-loading or low factor loading, while most of the items were loaded in their corresponding constructs (Appendix 6.6). EFA helps researchers determine if the items conform to theoretical factor structures. The internal consistency of items in each factor was confirmed by Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1984).

Table 6.11: Factor loadings

Items	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
TMG_1	.660							
TMG_2	.656							
TMG_3	.604							
TMG_4	.657							
TMG_5	.676							
TMG_6	.657							
TMG_7	.650							
TMG_8	.645							
TMG_9	.662							
TMD_1				.645				
TMD_2				.610				
TMD_3				.629				
TMD_4				.636				
TMD_6				.608				
TMD_7				.643				
TMD_8				.668				
TMR_1			.607					
TMR_2			.579					
TMR_3			.602					
TMR_4			.583					
TMR_5			.575					
TMR_6			.623					
TMR_7			.604					
TMR_9			.591					
TMR_11			.633					
TC_1					.667			
TC_3					.594			
TC_4					.597			
TC_5					.588			
TC_6					.631			
TC_7					.623			
TC_8					.548			
UIRP_1						.674		
UIRP_2						.679		
UIRP_3						.605		
UIRP_5						.700		
UIRP_6						.668		
DHIP_1							.637	

DHIP_2								.546
DHIP_4								.591
DHIP_6								.659
DHIP_7								.570
DHIP_8								.566
HIR_1								.617
HIR_2								.554
HIR_3								.547
HIR_5								.578
HIR_6								.570
HIR_7								.579
TBP_1		.643						
TBP_2		.610						
TBP_3		.626						
TBP_4		.612						
TBP_5		.617						
TBP_6		.602						
TBP_7		.681						
TBP_9		.691						
Cronbach's a	.954	.946	.945	.941	.924	.907	.930	.926

6.6. THE MODEL'S STRUCTURAL EVALUATION

In this stage, CFA was used to test the validity of the construct (Hair et al., 2016). The second stage is to test the structural model with the purpose of clarifying the associations existing between all observed constructs (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012).

6.6.1. First Step of testing the measurement model

6.6.1.1. Results of measurement model

The measurement model is the first level of model evaluation; it is based on CFA to test the model's reliability and validity. This can also be achieved by excluding items that cluster outside of the same group of items belonging to the same construct. Relying on the measurement model criteria, the following steps are analysed step by step.

6.6.1.2. The reliability measurement (items level)

According to the results reflected in Tables 6.12 to 6.19, the correlation between the factor loading (i.e., measuring manifest items) and its construct was higher than the minimum accepted value of 0.4. The factor loading met the reliability requirement, ranging between 0.781 (TC_1 <-- TC) and 0.869 (DHIP_6 <-- DHIP) (Churchill, 1979).

6.6.1.3. Reliability measurement (constructs level)

The Cronbach's α values, as shown in Tables 6.12 to 6.19, are greater than the recommended value, ranging between 0.864 and 0.925 (>0.70), meeting the test of psychometric reliability requirements (Hair et al., 2016; Nunnally, 1978), ensuring the internal consistency and unidimensionality of the multi-item scale measured by Cronbach's α (Cronbach, 1951). The efficiency of construct measurement is based on its assigned items and relies on construct reliability (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). In this study, squared multiple correlations (SMC) are used to measure the reliability of constructs. SMC reflects the correlation between the construct and its indicator variables separately, with the square of the indicator's standardized loading representing the SMC for an observed variable. The SMC in this study was above the recommended value (>0.5), where an SMC of 0.5 corresponds to a standardized loading of 0.7 (Foroudi et al., 2021a).

Table 6.12: The TNE Market Information Generation construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .925				Composite reliability = 0.93				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
TNE Market Information Generation (TMG) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.712
TMG	--->	TMG_1	.858	1				0.736	
TMG	--->	TMG_2	.883	1.034	0.048	21.758	***	0.780	
TMG	--->	TMG_5	.848	0.950	0.047	20.115	***	0.719	
TMG	--->	TMG_7	.811	0.883	0.047	18.645	***	0.658	
TMG	--->	TMG_9	.818	0.948	0.050	19.049	***	0.669	

Table 6.13: The TNE Market Information Dissemination construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .882				Composite reliability = 0.88				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
TNE Market Information Dissemination (TMD) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.712
TMD	--->	TMD_1	.840	1				0.706	
TMD	--->	TMD_4	.838	0.974	0.053	18.351	***	0.702	
TMD	--->	TMD_7	.854	1.005	0.053	18.798	***	0.729	

Table 6.14: The TNE Market Information Responsiveness construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .893				Composite reliability = 0.89				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
TNE Market Information Responsiveness (TMR) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.678
TMR	--->	TMR_3	.842	1				0.709	
TMR	--->	TMR_6	.824	0.920	0.050	18.330	***	0.679	
TMR	--->	TMR_7	.792	0.871	0.051	17.181	***	0.627	
TMR	--->	TMR_11	.835	.928	0.050	18.614	***	0.697	

Table 6.15: The Transnational Education Cooperation construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .864				Composite reliability = 0.87				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Transnational education cooperation (TC) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.682
TC	--->	TC_1	.781	1.000				0.610	
TC	--->	TC_3	.836	1.198	0.074	16.251	***	0.699	
TC	--->	TC_7	.859	1.213	0.071	17.036	***	0.738	

Table 6.16: The University International Ranking Position construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .907				Composite reliability = 0.91				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
University International Ranking Position (UIRP) Standard factor loading				Estimate/B-value	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.662
UIRP	--->	UIRP_1	.819	1.000				0.671	
UIRP	--->	UIRP_2	.785	0.936	0.057	16.361	***	0.616	
UIRP	--->	UIRP_3	.812	1.002	0.058	17.181	***	0.659	
UIRP	--->	UIRP_5	.796	0.969	0.058	16.768	***	0.634	
UIRP	--->	UIRP_6	.853	1.056	0.057	18.592	***	0.728	

Table 6.17: The Developed Country Higher Education Image Perception construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .884				Composite reliability = 0.88				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Developed Country Higher Education Image Perception (DHIP) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.717
DHIP	--->	DHIP_1	.841	1.000				0.707	
DHIP	--->	DHIP_6	.830	0.961	0.052	18.387	***	0.689	
DHIP	--->	DHIP_8	.869	0.992	0.051	19.437	***	0.755	

Table 6.18: The Higher Education International Reputation construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .875				Composite reliability = 0.88				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
Higher Education International Reputation (HIR) Standard factor loading				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.703
HIR	--->	HIR_2	.859	1				0.738	
HIR	--->	HIR_5	.816	0.994	0.054	18.298	***	0.666	
HIR	--->	HIR_7	.839	1.021	0.053	19.373	***	0.704	

Table 6.19: TNE Business Performance construct

Reliability Cronbach's alpha = .904				Composite reliability = 0.90				Squared multiple correlations	Average variance extracted
TNE Business Performance (TBP)				Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Value	0.704
Standard factor loading									
TBP	--->	TBP_1	.841	1				0.707	
TBP	--->	TBP_5	.855	0.981	0.051	19.409	***	0.731	
TBP	--->	TBP_7	.816	0.953	0.053	17.961	***	0.666	
TBP	--->	TBP_9	.843	0.971	0.051	18.991	***	0.711	

6.6.1.4. Validity measurement (convergent validity)

Convergent validity concerns the consistency of constructs, specifically how indicators of a particular construct come together or share a significant portion of common variance. To assess convergent validity alongside internal consistency, we examined whether the factor loading of items within their respective constructs was substantial (equal to or greater than 0.5) and statistically significant (Hair et al., 2016). Nunnally (1978) suggested that a reliability of 0.7 or higher indicates convergent validity. Furthermore, measures with reliabilities exceeding 0.85 encompass more than 50% error variance. In this study, based on Tables 6.12 to 6.19, the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct ranged from 0.62 to 0.717 (also see Table 6.20). A generally accepted guideline is that an AVE of 0.5 or above indicates satisfactory convergent validity.

Table 6.20: AVE and inter-construct correlation (for basic model)

	AVE	√AVE	TMG	TMD	TMR	TC	UIRP	DHIP	HIR	TBP
TMG	0.712	0.844	1.00							
TMD	0.712	0.844	0.59	1.00						
TMR	0.678	0.823	0.67	0.68	1.00					
TC	0.682	0.826	0.61	0.62	0.66	1.00				
UIRP	0.662	0.813	0.57	0.54	0.63	0.60	1.00			
DHIP	0.717	0.847	0.66	0.61	0.67	0.64	0.58	1.00		
HIR	0.703	0.838	0.68	0.66	0.67	0.68	0.61	0.70	1.00	
TBP	0.704	0.839	0.62	0.62	0.63	0.65	0.59	0.64	0.62	1.00

6.6.1.5. Validity measurement (discriminant validity)

The average variance extracted (AVE) results are higher than the squared correlation estimates (Foroudi et al., 2021a) (Table 6.21). Another method to test discriminant validity is by calculating the AVE for all constructs and comparing it with the squared correlation among them. In this study, discriminant validity is supported as the AVE is higher than all squared correlations of the latent variables (LV) of the factor they belong to (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Thus, the modified measurement model reflects discriminant validity without any cross-loading between assessed variables.

Table 6.21: The correlation matrix for every construct

Construct	TMG	TMD	TMR	TC	UIRP	DHIP	HIR	TBP
TMG	0.844							
TMD	0.765	0.844						
TMR	0.817	0.822	0.823					
TC	0.779	0.790	0.811	0.826				
UIRP	0.756	0.736	0.782	0.773	0.813			
DHIP	0.812	0.780	0.819	0.797	0.762	0.847		
HIR	0.825	0.811	0.816	0.824	0.782	0.834	0.838	
TBP	0.786	0.785	0.795	0.806	0.770	0.797	0.787	0.839

Note: Average variance was extracted from the square roots of average variance extracted.

6.6.1.6. Validity measurement (nomological validity)

The model's overall fit within CFA is employed as an adequate and important provision for examining nomological validity (Steenkamp and Baumgartner, 2000). Nomological validity relies on the construct correlation matrix elements, which must be related to each other (Table 6.22). Nomological validity concerns the overall fit of a model, as it relates to how the scale predicts the data based on theory and the validity of the entire model (Eriksson and Sharma, 1998; Foroudi et al., 2021a; Hair et al., 2016). The estimation of factor loading within CFA was carried out using maximum likelihood (ML) in all measurement model estimations. Model validation was supported by model fit indicators to address issues of standard errors and an unreliable Chi-square (χ^2) statistic due to the application of ML (Hu and Bentler, 1999).

Table 6.22: The model modification's Goodness-of-fit indices

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/ X^2	Df	RMSEA	GFI ¹	NFI	CFI	AGFI ¹	IFI	TLI
420.178	377	.018	.924	.952	.995	.907	.995	.994
<i>X² – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normed fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis Index</i>								

The information provided by the root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA) and the comparative fit index (CFI) is unique for assessing a model (Hair et al., 2016). An RMSEA lower than 0.08 reflects an acceptable fit (RMSEA = 0.018 < 0.08) (Garver and Mentzer, 1999). A CFI greater than 0.90 indicates a good fit, with 0.995 being an incremental index assessing a model's fit with the primary model (Hair et al., 2016). Researchers (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2016; Foroudi et al., 2021a) consider CFI as an advanced version of the normed fit index (NFI), which evaluates the degree to which a model is developed. An acceptable NFI must be greater than 0.08, as recommended by Hair et al. (2012), thus the result of NFI (0.952 > 0.08) is accepted. The goodness-of-fit index (GFI) measures the model's fitness compared to other models and is considered good when it exceeds 0.95 and accepted when 0.95 > GFI > 0.90 (GFI = 0.924) (Hair et al., 2012). The adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) adjusts for the complexity of the model, and it is accepted as well when 0.995 > AGFI = 0.907 > 0.90 (Hair et al., 2012).

The Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), as popular as the non-normed fit index (NNFI), calculates the difference between the χ^2 value of the model and that of an independence model, considering the degrees of freedom of the model (Hair et al., 2012; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Thus, the measurement model related to these factors was nomologically valid (Foroudi et al., 2021a). Additionally, the TLI and the incremental fit index (IFI) (0.994 and 0.995, respectively) exceeded the threshold of 0.90 (Hair et al., 2012). Therefore, all the fit criteria indicate that the model fit is accepted in this study.

Subsequently, the outcomes of the discriminant, nomological, and convergent validity assessments of the measurement models yielded theoretically and statistically effective constructs. Important re-specifications were applied to all construct scales based on the statistical requirements that were theoretically justified. Twenty-seven items were removed from the CFA models (TMG_3, TMG_4, TMG_6, TMG_8, TMD_2, TMD_3, TMD_6, TMD_8, TMR_1, TMR_2, TMR_4, TMR_5, TMR_9, TC_4, TC_5, TC_6, TC_8, DHIP_2, DHIP_4, DHIP_7, HIR_1, HIR_3, HIR_6, and TBP_2, TBP_3, TBP_4, TBP_6). Therefore, the fundamental variables needed for the next stage of model examination are complete.

6.6.2. Second step: hypothesis testing through structural model evaluation

The assumed causal and covariance linear connection between the endogenous (dependent) and exogenous (independent) latent variables is estimated in the second step. An evaluation of the path model or inner model is facilitated by the structural model. The TNE market orientation operational model is illustrated in Figure 6.6. The rationale for relationships between theoretical constructs is elucidated by the structural model (Hair et al., 2012; Foroudi et al., 2021a). For instance, this study hypothesised that the higher the market orientation among marketing managers of universities in TNE, the better the performance of the TNE business.

Relying on the structural model, the hypotheses were tested based on the t-value and standardised estimate. In this stage, the chi-square was 520.639, and the comparative fit index (CFI) was 0.984, indicating an improved fit of the model compared to the ground model (Hair et al., 2016). The incremental fit index (IFI) and normed fit index (NFI) scores of 0.984 and 0.940, respectively, are greater than 0.9 as recommended (Byrne, 2001; Hair et al., 2016). Thus, this provides additional confirmation of the adequate fit of the hypothesised model for the experimental data (Table 6.23).

Table 6.23: The model modification's Goodness-of-fit indices

Model fit indicators								
Chi-square/ X^2	Df	RMSEA	GFI ²	NFI	CFI	AGFI ²	IFI	TLI
520.639	387	.032	.907	.940	.984	.888	.984	.982
X^2 – Chi-square; Df – degree of freedom; RMSEA – Root mean square error of approximation; GFI – Goodness-of-fit index; NFI – Normed fit index; CFI – Comparative fit index; AGFI – Adjusted goodness-of-fit index; and TLI – Tucker-Lewis' index								

The total of the model-fit indices met the criteria of validity levels and indicated that the model achieved a good fit based on the collected data (Byrne, 2001; Foroudi et al., 2021a; Hair et al., 2016) (Table 6.23). Additionally, the goodness-of-fit index (GFI), as another comprehensive fit measure, indicates an acceptable fit of 0.907. The GFI index extends to the adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI) of 0.888, suggesting that the model fit is ultimately marginal. Evaluating the model fit, the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) is 0.032 (below 0.08), ensuring an acceptable level (Hair et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2020). Since there is no common agreement among researchers on the ideal goodness-of-fit index and due to the sensitivity of some indices to sample size, adopting different goodness-of-fit indices is the best strategy (Anderson and Gerbing, 1982; Foroudi et al., 2021a).

The proposed structural model fit met the criteria for adequate fit satisfactorily, as the accepted limits were achieved across all the fit indices in this research (Hair et al., 2016; Martinez-Lopez et al., 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). In conclusion, based on the observed data, the proposed model demonstrates a good fit. Seventeen hypotheses were examined, and the following chapter will discuss the implications of these results. The standardised regression coefficient is represented by path coefficients. The assumed linearity is reflected by the structural model, where the data collected from validated measures test the reasons for relations among constructs. In structural equations, the index of squared multiple correlation (R^2) shows that the highest variance between independent variables and dependent is in HIR (i.e., $R^2=79\%$) and TMR (i.e., $R^2=80\%$). Table 6.24 presents the weights of resulting regression and findings related to causal paths (standard error, standardised path coefficients (γ), p-value, and hypotheses result).

Table 6.24: The hypothesis testing results

	Standardised regression paths			Estimate	S.E	C.R	<i>p</i>	Hypothesis
		---		γ		<i>t</i> -value		
H1a	TC	---	TMG	.406	.097	4.171	***	Supported
H1b	TC	---	TMD	.556	.109	5.113	***	Supported
H1c	TC	---	TMR	.457	.096	4.744	***	Supported
H2a	UIRP	---	TMG	.183	.098	1.879	.060	Not Supported
H2b	UIRP	---	TMD	.134	.108	1.238	.216	Not Supported
H2c	UIRP	---	TMR	.245	.096	2.552	.011	Supported
H3a	DHIP	---	TMG	.489	.078	6.289	***	Supported
H3b	DHIP	---	TMD	.422	.083	5.077	***	Supported
H3c	DHIP	---	TMR	.421	.075	5.608	***	Supported
H4	UIRP	---	DHIP	.877	.064	13.620	***	Supported
H5a	TMG	---	HIR	.328	.066	4.947	***	Supported
H6a	TMG	---	TBP	.262	.079	3.334	***	Supported
H5b	TMD	---	HIR	.299	.070	4.265	***	Supported
H6b	TMD	---	TBP	.286	.083	3.445	***	Supported
H5c	TMR	---	HIR	.259	.078	3.320	***	Supported
H6c	TMR	---	TBP	.291	.089	3.285	.001	Supported
H7	HIR	---	TBP	.072	.109	.658	.510	Not Supported

*** $p < 0.001$

Notes: Path = Relationship between independent variable on dependent variable; γ = Standardised regression coefficient; S.E. = Standard error; p = Level of significance.

The standardised regression path among TNE coordination (TC) and TNE market information generation (TMG), TNE market information dissemination (TMD), and TNE market information responsiveness (TMR) is statistically significant ($\gamma = 0.406$, t -value = 4.171; $\gamma = 0.556$, t -value = 5.113; $\gamma = 0.457$, t -value = 4.744, respectively). This illustrates that H1a, H1b, and H1c are fully supported, while H2a and H2b were not supported, but H2c was supported, based on the significant relation between university international ranking position (UIRP) and TMG, TMD, and TMR ($\gamma = 0.183$, t -value = 1.879; $\gamma = 0.134$, t -value = 1.238; $\gamma = 0.245$, t -value = 2.552, respectively). The results for the developed country higher education image perception (DHIP) with TMG, TMD, and TMR were statistically significant ($\gamma = 0.489$, t -value = 6.289; $\gamma = 0.422$, t -value = 5.077; $\gamma = 0.421$, t -value = 5.608, respectively), thus H3a, H3b, and H3c were fully supported. The fourth hypothesis was accepted because it was statistically significant between UIRP and DHIP ($\gamma = 0.877$, t -value = 13.620).

For the paths from TMG, TMD, and TMR to higher education international reputation (HIR), the results were statistically significant ($\gamma = 0.328$, $t\text{-value} = 4.947$; $\gamma = 0.299$, $t\text{-value} = 4.265$; $\gamma = 0.259$, $t\text{-value} = 3.320$, respectively). Thus, hypotheses H5a, H5b, and H5c were accepted. Hypotheses H6a, H6b, and H6c, which reflect the connection among TMG, TMD, and TMR and TNE business performance (TBP), showed the hypothesized direction of significance ($\gamma = 0.262$, $t\text{-value} = 3.334$; $\gamma = 0.286$, $t\text{-value} = 3.445$; $\gamma = 0.291$, $t\text{-value} = 3.285$, respectively). Hypothesis 7, which clarifies the relation between HIR and TBP, was not found to be significant within the hypothesized path ($\gamma = 0.072$, $t\text{-value} = 0.658$) (Table 6.24). The final model is shown in Figure 6.6. The following chapter will include the discussion, implications, and conclusions of the results.

Figure 6.5: The validated structural model

Guide:

- (1) $\xrightarrow{\text{Estimate } y \text{ \& (C.R t-value)}} \text{ : Accepted Hypothesis}$
- (2) $\xrightarrow{\text{Estimate } y \text{ \& (C.R t-value)}} \text{ : Not accepted Hypothesis}$
- (3) $R^2 \text{ : The square multiple correlation}$

Figure 6.6: Model of study

6.7. SUMMARY

The objectives of this study were achieved by analysing the data through three phases, each covering several steps. The VIF values were within range, suggesting the absence of multicollinearity, which was further tested using bivariate Pearson correlation. The results of the Mann-Whitney-U test to examine non-response error among respondents did not yield significant differences between late and early respondents.

The two-step procedure was adapted to demonstrate the connection of variables to factors through the technique of EFA. The scree plot and eigenvalues were utilised to aid in the extraction of factors. The use of the orthogonal technique (Varimax) in principal component analysis helped indicate the maximum variance of factor loading based on the rotated factors. Following the tests of reliability and EFA, six items were removed from six constructs. This removal was due to their high cross-loading on other factors, which could not be justified by theory, along with low reliability or communalities.

The scree plot was utilized to examine the factors extracted based on EFA. An AVE value above 0.5 was presented in all variables, indicating discriminant validity and adequate convergence for the measurements. Nomological validity analysis relied on the constructs' correlation matrix. Therefore, correlation analysis was used to assess the interrelations among research variables and to test the potential of multicollinearity.

The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) constitutes the second phase of the analysis, involving the examination of multiple measurement models for goodness-of-fit assessment. AMOS 25 was employed to conduct confirmatory analysis on 336 cases, evaluating several measurement models and the structural model of the proposed TNE market orientation model. In terms of assessing goodness-of-fit, the CFA indicated that all indicators were loaded with high values within their respective factors, and overall goodness-of-fit indices predicted an acceptable model. Additionally, each construct underwent examination for Cronbach's alpha, reliability and validity, composite reliability, and average variance extracted. The results demonstrated that the instrument exhibited good reliability and validity. Furthermore, discriminant, convergent, and nomological validity for all constructs were confirmed. The CFA provided strong evidence regarding the validity of the constructs, relying on the evaluation of the measurement model fit and psychometric properties in this study.

The last phase involved the evaluation and development of the structural equation model (SEM) for this study. To estimate the SEM, the researcher applied an overall model fit assessment where the path coefficient was related to the associated causal effects. The SEM implemented the proposed model using a two-step approach. In the first step, the approach evaluated the measurement model to assess construct and item reliability, convergent and discriminant validity. The model, based on findings, reflects a strong examination of the hypotheses related to the constructs. Fourteen out of seventeen hypotheses were accepted.

CHAPTER 7: DISCUSSION

7.1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this chapter is to detail the results and fulfil the research objectives by examining the connections in the studied conceptual framework and responding to research questions. A mixed-methods approach (qualitative and quantitative) was utilized to enhance the measurement scale and test hypotheses (Foroudi et al., 2021a).

The research discussion will be covered as follows: Section 7.2 will present an overview of this study and the findings of hypotheses. The next section (7.3) will focus on hypotheses concerning factors (antecedents) that affect TNE market orientation (TNE market information generation; TNE market information dissemination; and TNE market information responsiveness) (H1a to H4). Then, section 7.4 will discuss hypotheses regarding the validation of TNE market orientation and their outcomes from the perspective of managers (H5a to H7). Section 7.4 will address the appraisal of the TNE market orientation scale. The tests of hypotheses will be discussed in section 7.5, followed by a summary in section 7.6.

7.2. RESEARCH OVERVIEW

The development of the conceptual model indicated the factors' (antecedents') influence, which impacts on the focal construct TNE market orientation (TNE market information generation, TNE market information dissemination, TNE market information responsiveness), and subsequently influences higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. The theoretical model was examined through a sample of UK university managers. The two-step approach provides a comprehensive understanding of all stages of analysis. The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) reflects results that confirm the model has a significant fit: the chi-square (χ^2) = 520.639, $p < .001$, CFI = 0.984, TLI = 0.982, GFI = 0.907, IFI = 0.984, AGFI = 0.888, NFI = 0.940, and RMSEA = 0.032, in accordance with the recommendations of researchers (Diamantopoulos et al., 2012; Foroudi et al., 2021a; Hair et al., 2016).

For the hypothesised model test, most of the relations suggested among constructs were statistically supported, excluding three connections. The results show that H1a (TMG --> TC), H1b (TMD --> TC), H1c (TMR --> TC), H2c (TMR --> UIRP), H3a (TMG --> DHIP), H3b (TMD --> DHIP), H3c (TMR --> DHIP), H4 (DHIP --> UIRP), H5a (HIR --> TMG), H6a (TBP --> TMG), H5b (HIR --> TMD), H6b (TBP --> TMD), H5c (HIR --> TMR), and H6c (TBP --> TMR) were statistically significant. However, hypotheses H2a (TMG --> UIRP), H2b (TMD --> UIRP), and H7 (HIR --> TBP) were rejected because they were not significantly different from 0 at the 0.001 significance level ($\gamma = 0.183$, $\gamma = 0.134$, $\gamma = 0.072$ respectively) (Table 6.24). The next section will provide a detailed understanding of the conceptual model by summarising the evidence covered in the qualitative and hypotheses findings.

7.3. TNE MARKET ORIENTATION CONSTRUCT (FOCAL CONSTRUCT)

TNE market information generation:

Our university regularly conducts surveys to assess international students' perceptions of the quality of our TNE programmes (TMG_1). We maintain continuous communication with international students to promptly identify any issues related to TNE programmes (TMG_2). We stay updated on the diverse needs of international students by participating in international fairs worldwide (TMG_5). Our international office conducts secondary research on TNE market trends, including economic and political factors, in attractive markets (TMG_7). Additionally, we consistently analyse the potential impact of various changes, such as regulations and technological advancements, on TNE in the markets where we operate (TMG_9). The factor loadings ranged from 0.811 (TMG --> TMG_7) to 0.883 (TMG --> TMG_2), meeting reliability requirements (Churchill, 1979) (items and TNE market information generation construct reliability in Table 6.12).

The findings reveal a Cronbach's alpha (α) reliability of 0.925, surpassing the accepted threshold for Cronbach's alpha, and meeting the requirements of psychometric reliability tests based on the results (Hair et al., 2016; Foroudi et al., 2021a). This section underscores the significance of the connection among items related to TNE market information generation, which has been augmented through the quantitative study, and the TNE market information generation construct, as indicated by the qualitative study results. The quantitative study results identify five aspects of the TNE market information generation construct within the context of UK universities.

The next quotation, generated from the interview study, suggests that TNE market information generation is significant for maintaining updates on how international students perceive the quality of the delivered TNE, as this element is described: "Our university conducts regular surveys to evaluate international students' attitude about the quality of our TNE." This confirms the results (TMG ---> TMG_1). The quotation includes:

We contact our students' union as the first platform to raise students' voice. We conduct regular surveys with our international students on issues related to TNE, so we can monitor our education quality and track their perception on courses' content, teaching quality, students support, and academic services satisfaction.
(University 1)

Therefore, this statement supports the concept that TNE market information generation enables the management of an organisation to identify and address aspects that require attention and improvement. It can provide decisive information and shed light on TNE issues (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2009; Healey, 2020).

Another element of TNE market information generation is "Our continuous contact with international students aims to quickly spot issues related to TNE programmes" (TMG_2). As confirmed in previous research, universities aim to establish strong relationships with students in the international market (Asaad et al., 2015; Girdzijauskaitė et al., 2019; Grecic, 2022). This concept has also been affirmed in the qualitative study and corroborated the results (TMG --> TMG_2). The quotation is as follows:

Generating TNE market information relies on what type of TNE our university intends to deliver or where and with whom we will cooperate. However, we usually consider our international students first as we can be in touch with them frequently, followed by the international students enrolled with our TNE's partners, with an aim to detect our TNE weaknesses. (University 4)

The above quotation supports the view that TNE market information generation is a dynamic tool to keep universities updated on the efficiency of their TNE. TNE market information generation is used to prevent universities from losing control of market trends and students' opinions (Chung, 2012; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; James and Derrick, 2021).

Researchers have emphasised the necessity of approaching international students through different types of communication (Asaad et al., 2015; Abbasov, 2019; He et al., 2018; James and Derrick, 2021). The results clarified that staying close to international students permits the generation of valuable information on the TNE market (Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; James and Derrick, 2021). This is demonstrated in the following quotation from an interviewee:

We involve parents in our strategy plan to generate TNE market information through organising private fairs overseas or participating in international fairs. (University 5)

This illustrates a finding consistent with previous studies in marketing (Molesworth et al., 2011; Naidoo and Williams, 2015; Naidoo and Wu, 2011; Nixon et al., 2010), which emphasize the importance of maintaining a continued relationship with customers (students) to keep both sides (university and students) in touch with each other. This creates a good platform for exchanging information (Vangelis et al., 2018). Thus, "we monitor the diverse needs of international students via participating in international fairs worldwide" (TMG_5) is an important factor of TNE market information generation (TMG --> TMG_2)).

Another factor of TNE market information generation is "Our international office conducts secondary research about TNE market trends (e.g., economic, political) in attractive markets" (TMG_7) (TMG --> TMG_7), which has suggested to be significant for this construct in the literature (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 1999) and qualitative study, further supported by quantitative results. The qualitative study also examined "We regularly study the effect of possible changes (e.g., regulation, technology) on TNE in markets where we operate" (TMG_9), which was adopted from the literature review (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 1999; Yu et al., 2018) and confirmed in the quantitative study (TMG --> TMG_9)

Therefore, the adjusted scales demonstrate that the range of items related to TNE market information generation is familiar to the managers (target audience group). This result is consistent with the perspective supported by academics, which aligns with the export market orientation theory (Asaad et al., 2015; Diamantopoulos and Cadogan, 1996).

TNE market information dissemination:

Our university holds regular meetings between heads of its different departments to discuss TNE issues (TMD_1). Our international office communicates effectively with our TNE partners, which makes us more familiar with TNE markets in which we operate (TMD_4). The activities of our TNE competitors are frequently discussed among the heads of different departments in our university (TMD_7). The factor loading ranged between 0.838 (TMD --> TMD_4) and 0.854 (TMD --> TMD_7), meeting reliability requirements (Churchill, 1979) (see Table 6.13 for items and TNE market information dissemination construct reliability). The findings indicate that the reliability of Cronbach's alpha (α) is 0.882, exceeding the accepted value, and the psychometric reliability test based on results satisfies the requirements (Hair et al., 2016; Foroudi et al., 2021a). This part elucidates the importance of the connection among the items of TNE market information dissemination, enhanced through the quantitative study, and the TNE market information dissemination construct from the qualitative study results. The result of the quantitative study indicates three aspects of the TNE market information dissemination construct in the context of UK universities.

The quotation below, generated from the interview study, suggests that TNE market information dissemination is important and related to this element: "Our university holds regular meetings between heads of its different departments to discuss TNE issues" (TMD_1); this also confirms the findings (TMD --> TMD_1). An example described by a TNE manager:

Different formal or informal meetings with managers from the international office and other departments in our university, and with managers of our TNE partners' administration (Skype for meeting or the Webinar for smart training) on a regular basis and in emergencies such as the Covid-19 pandemic. Heads of our faculties/schools also received reports on TNE practice or any TNE environment change through emails. (University 1)

This assessment confirms the opinion that TNE market information dissemination is one of the elements of TNE market orientation with the ability to share important information and strategies of a university with the purpose of attaining a common vision among stakeholders. It enables a quick spread of information and enhances knowledge on desired cases, fostering a positive connection within the entire TNE management (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2009; Casidy, 2014; Silva et al., 2023). Thus, "Our university holds regular meetings between

heads of its different departments to discuss TNE issues" (TMD_1) is admitted as an item to measure the "TNE market information dissemination" construct.

Our international office communicates effectively with our TNE partners, making us more familiar with TNE markets where we operate" (TMD_4) is another element of TNE market information dissemination in this study. In the literature, internal communication among employees and departments of an organisation contributes to the understanding of the market (Kohli and Jaworski, 1990). Interviewees mentioned a culture of sharing information. TNE market information dissemination is employed as a tool to permit all levels of an organisation (university) to stay updated on cases related to TNE (Asaad et al., 2015; Casidy, 2014; Yu et al., 2018). A participant commented that:

Sharing information is part of our organisational culture; every day, personnel from the same or different departments in our university exchange information on the university's issues or its progress. (University 4)

The above quotation is consistent with studies conducted in marketing literature (Devece et al., 2017; Firmansyah et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2011) that consider a common vision among the push factors, which supports personnel in acquiring a positive attitude toward the related business (Feldman and Sandoval, 2018; Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka, 2015a). Therefore, "Our international office communicates effectively with our TNE partners, making us more familiar with TNE markets in which we operate" (TMD_4) is a significant factor of TNE market information dissemination (TMD --> TMD_4).

Another aspect of TNE market information dissemination is "Our TNE competitors' activities are discussed frequently among the heads of different departments in our university" (TMD_7) (TMD --> TMD_7), which has been drawn from the literature (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012; Casidy, 2014; Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka, 2010) and elucidated in the interviews, further confirmed in the quantitative study. The following quotation is an example from an international partnership development manager:

All departments receive our monthly internal electronic newspaper via email, it covers the latest news and plans of our university including TNE competitors' activities. To approve a TNE programme or partnership, the international office

manager meets with heads of other departments from our faculties/schools to share with them information and plans and get their opinion and feedback. (University 2)

Thus, the adjusted scales suggest that the range of items related to TNE market information dissemination is familiar to the managers (target audience group). This result is compatible with the perspective achieved by academics that supports the export market orientation theory (Asaad et al., 2015; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014).

TNE market information responsiveness:

Our university provides understandable, clear, and accurate information to TNE students (TMR_3). Our university adapts very quickly to important changes related to our TNE environment (e.g., economic, political) (TMR_6). Our university responds to threats from TNE competitors very quickly (TMR_7). The quality of our TNE programmes is periodically reviewed to ensure international students' satisfaction (TMR_11). The factor loading ranged between 0.792 (TMR --> TMR_7) and 0.842 (TMR --> TMR_3), meeting reliability requirements (Churchill, 1979) (items and the TNE market information responsiveness construct reliability in Table 6.14). The findings indicate that the reliability of Cronbach's alpha (α) is 0.893, which exceeds the accepted value, and the psychometric reliability test based on results satisfies the requirements (Hair et al., 2016; Foroudi et al., 2021a). This section clarifies the importance of the connection among the items of TNE market information responsiveness, enhanced through the quantitative study, and the TNE market information responsiveness construct from the qualitative study results. The result of the quantitative study indicates four aspects of the TNE market information responsiveness construct in the context of UK universities.

The following quotation from the qualitative study suggests that TNE market information responsiveness is significant to "Our university providing understandable, clear, and accurate information to TNE students" (TMR_3), which supports the outcomes (TMR --> TMR_3). The international marketing manager said:

We are very clear with TNE students. For example, we supported international students applying for e-learning programmes that were not able to take the IELTS test as the British Council and other English centres were closed during the Covid-

19 pandemic. Our university delivered accurate information on the process of application and managed an online English test at a low cost. (University 5)

Another measurement item of TNE market information responsiveness in the current research is "Our university adapts very quickly to important changes related to our TNE environment (e.g., economic, political)" (TMR_6). As confirmed in previous research, universities attempt to establish a strong relationship with students in the international market (Asaad et al., 2015; Girdzijauskaitė et al., 2019; Grecic, 2022). This concept has also been confirmed in the qualitative study and affirmed the results (TMR --> TMR_6). Interviewees referenced the clarity and support provided to international students based on the market information responsiveness of TNE. TNE market information responsiveness is used as a motivator for stakeholders to uphold university promises and maintain trust between parties (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012; Casidy, 2014). Here are two comments supporting this:

It is among our priorities; we respond promptly to whatever is related to our TNE practices. The responses are based on collective agreements between decision-makers from different departments. Delays in responding might cause an accumulation of tasks, inability to catch up with the market trends, and dissatisfaction of international students. (University 2)

Responses to TNE market information in this university are accurate, quick, and effective, with the purpose to cover the latest changes affecting TNE and keep our students satisfied about the quality of TNE programmes. (University 3)

Another factor of TNE market information generation is "Our university responds to threats from TNE competitors very quickly" (TMR_7) (TMR --> TMR_7), which has suggested to be significant for this construct in the literature (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012; Yu et al., 2018) and confirmed by the qualitative study, followed by quantitative results. The qualitative study also examined "Our TNE programmes' quality is periodically reviewed to ensure international students' satisfaction" (TMR_11), which has been adopted from the literature review (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012); this was confirmed by the quantitative study as described in the quotation above (TMR --> TMR_11).

In general, the adjusted scales indicate that the range of items related to TNE market information responsiveness is familiar to the managers. This result is compatible with the

perspective achieved by academics, which supports the export market orientation theory (Asaad et al., 2015). The next sections demonstrate the outcomes gained from hypothesis testing.

7.4. APPRAISAL OF THE TNE MARKET ORIENTATION SCALE

The measures of TNE market orientation allow for the absorption of diversified activities. Indeed, as illustrated in this research, the comprehensiveness of the TNE market orientation construct links TNE and strategic market orientation with special intangible processes, which need to be assimilated and coherent within the export of higher education in UK universities. TNE market orientation is a key component of the export of education. Managers in universities must use TNE market orientation to develop a deep understanding of the TNE market, international students' needs, and competitors' activities. This understanding is then shared across all levels of the university to effectively respond to market needs and threats, thus enhancing the international reputation of higher education and TNE business performance.

The TNE market orientation scale confirmed that TNE market information generation, dissemination, and responsiveness, as a marketing strategy, are employed to maximise perceptions of quality and transparency. These must be linked to the university's values and position to ensure an effective reputation and business performance regarding TNE. Therefore, this scale supports TNE market orientation as a dynamic method for a university to achieve its goals and proposes that it must play a very important role for marketing managers. Therefore, according to the experimental study and literature review, TNE market orientation can be defined as follows:

TNE Market Orientation is the strategy that enables a university to export its programmes outside its main campus in a manner that detects the current and future needs of international students and TNE partners, then fulfils these needs (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2009; James and Derrick, 2021; Yu et al., 2018).

Figure 6.6 illustrates that the TNE market orientation construct was integrated into a model that established causal connections among its sub-dimensions and other constructs. The following sections, drawing on the literature and research outcomes from qualitative study and hypothesis testing, will discuss the antecedents and consequences of TNE market orientation.

7.5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF HYPOTHESES

The findings of these research hypotheses will be discussed in this section to align with the research objectives and address four goals: first, to explore the role of TNE market orientation in the success of UK TNE; second, to recognize how UK TNE can sustain its development in foreign markets; third, to enhance understanding of the interconnectedness among the UK higher education variables, TNE market orientation, and TNE business performance; finally, to develop and evaluate a theoretical and experimental basis that would support further research on TNE for managers, policymakers, and academics.

After examining this study's focal construct, the discussion continues to explore how TNE coordination, university international ranking position, and developed country higher education image perception influence TNE market orientation, and how the latter influences higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. The aim of separating the hypotheses into several relationships was to cover the main exploratory effects of the relationship of each construct (Table 6.24 summaries all the paths). The next section will examine the results for the antecedents and consequences.

7.5.1. TNE market orientation antecedents

According to the qualitative study results, interviewing managers and experts in TNE, the factors (antecedents) that supported fully the influence on TNEMO are TNE coordination and developed country higher education perception. While university international ranking position has only a partial influence on TNEMO.

TNE coordination:

TNE coordination has been identified as positively influencing all aspects of TNEMO. The research highlights the critical role that TNE coordination plays in predicting TNEMO outcomes in the realm of higher education, aligning with the findings of earlier studies (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2016; Chang and Wang, 2018; Girdzijauskaite et al., 2019) that have emphasized the significant effect of TNE coordination on TNEMO. This study further enhances our understanding of the TNE coordination-TNEMO dynamic by confirming its validity within the context of higher education. By fostering unity among TNE administrators and across various academic departments, TNE coordination underpins the processes involved

in generating, sharing, and reacting to TNE-related information. This insight is consistent with the notion of coordination as a foundational element of marketing effectiveness. Moreover, the practical implications of TNE coordination on TNEMO in the higher education sector are supported by the perspectives of TNE, international office, and marketing managers.

Managers described that in their universities they believe in the effectiveness of coordination in matters related to generating market information on TNE. This quotation is an example from an international office manager:

Our good TNE coordination facilitates the TNE market information generation, as our contact with partners is already based on effective communication in all aspects ... It increases the positive relationship between key players of our university and TNE partners that increases the amount of effective TNE market information generation. (University 8)

The hypothesis H1a was completely supported ($\gamma=0.373$, t -value= 5.208) (see Table 6.24). This is considered as a statistical support of this claim: if TNE is well-coordinated, the generation of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

The presence of good TNE coordination plays a significant role to disseminate the generated TNE market information. The following comment is an example from an international office manager:

The absence of work conflicts among departments of our universities contributes to the creation of good communication and attitude between managers and facilitates TNE market information dissemination that increases knowledge on threats and opportunities of TNE among different managements' hierarchy in the university ... It increases the positive relationship between key players of our university and TNE partners which contributes to the enhancement of effective TNE market information dissemination. (University 5)

Hypothesis H1b was completely supported ($\gamma=0.499$, t -value= 6.281) (see Table 6.24). This is considered as a statistical support of this claim: if TNE is well-coordinated, the dissemination of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

Again, respondents from the qualitative study described that responding to TNE market information could be very effective with the existence of TNE coordination. These quotations are examples from a marketing manager and the second focus group:

The effects of our TNE coordination, including our coordination with educational partners, contribute to diversified proposals and plans that make effective interventions towards matters related to TNE. (University 6)

The results of TNE market information responsiveness become more effective due to the continuous coordination within the different levels of TNE ... effective strategies can be implemented under the same vision. (Focus group 2)

Hypothesis H1c was completely supported ($\gamma=0.423$, t -value= 5.995)(see Table 6.24). This is considered as a statistical support of this claim: if TNE is well-coordinated, the responsiveness of TNE market information by the university will be enhanced.

University international ranking position:

The findings did not validate completely the anticipated positive link between the university international ranking position and TNEMO. Instead, the data indicated that the university international ranking position had a direct positive impact solely on TNE market information responsiveness, without affecting other TNEMO dimensions. This outcome diverges from several studies in higher education literature that have explored the influence of university international rankings on marketing practices (Asaad et al., 2015; Melewar et al., 2018). However, these results align with Foroudi's (2017) research, which suggested that institutions with higher rankings tend to be more attuned to the needs of their consumers than those with lower rankings.

Nonetheless, the research revealed that the dissemination and responsiveness of TNE market information was not significantly impacted. This could be due to certain organisational factors

that inhibit the influence of ranking position on the spread of information within universities. For example, it is reasonable to assume that an organisational structure marked by poor coordination could impede the efficient flow of information, thus hampering the dissemination and responsiveness process regardless of a university's ranking position.

Universities from those with high rankings to those with lower standings, are progressively adopting marketing strategies and tools to attract students from abroad. Institutions that enjoy a high ranking leverage their esteemed status as a significant asset in penetrating international markets for student recruitment (Ghobehei et al., 2019). On the other hand, for universities that find themselves lower in the rankings, a concerted marketing effort becomes essential to convey the institution's merits. This is particularly important since a ranking position may not always accurately reflect the true academic quality of a university (Ipek and Bicakcioglu-Peynirci, 2020). The below justifications are generated from some of interviewees' comments:

Unranked universities or those with low-ranking are presented in the TNE market more than universities with good ranking position and there are some differences in ranking lists which effects the choice making of international students, therefore, the TNE market information generation will not be accurate and valid. (University 1)

If you ignore the ranking position of a university, it will affect the belongness of managers to that university, but good dissemination of TNE market information is more effective when there is management of how work should be done, where managers are familiar with it. (Focus group 1)

Thus, Hypotheses H2a and H2b were rejected because they are statistically insignificant and Hypothesis H2c was accepted as it is statistically significant (see Table 6.24). For an additional critical regard of the insignificant relationship of results, the qualitative data and literature were reviewed. The constructs' discriminant validity was supported by the structural model's evaluation, which confirms the constructs' measures were truly distinct. Both the estimated correlations between factors and the one of discriminant validity met the recommended values (Hair et al., 2012; Foroudi et al., 2021a).

This study pioneers the exploration of the connection between universities international ranking positions and TNEMO. Thus, it underscores the importance of further investigation

into how international ranking systems influence the particular marketing activities undertaken by managers in TNE.

Developed country higher education image perception:

A prior investigation (Baker and Ballington, 2011) identified the image of the service country as a precursor to export marketing strategy, but this hypothesis remains unverified. The current study is the inaugural empirical evaluation of how the higher education image of a developed country is perceived by marketing and TNE managers within universities. The findings completely validated this relationship, which aligns with existing literature on higher education marketing.

Overall, the way higher education images of developed countries are perceived can either facilitate or impede access to international markets. A positive image of a developed country's higher education system can serve as an effective marketing asset in the promotional activities of developed countries' universities (Bennell, 2022; Firmansyah et al., 2023; Ghobehei et al., 2019). One TNE manager said:

Strong image of our higher education influences positively the choice of international students to participate in our research about the TNE market, even if they are not our students. (University 3)

The findings confirmed the predicted positive impact of the developed country higher education image perception on the generation and dissemination of TNE market information. This outcome diverges from the research conducted by Baker and Ballington (2011) and Raymundo-Delmonte (2023), which focused more on responsiveness instead of other aspects of market orientation, when assessing the effect of country image on marketing strategies. A comments regarding this observation are as follow:

Higher education image of the UK is influenced somewhat by the image of the country itself as it is one of the leading countries, leaving no room for the difference between London School of Economic and London School of Commerce. This supports our marketing activities abroad such as generating information about TNE. (University 5)

The reality that the image of UK higher education is highly favourable motivates our working spirit, especially when it is related to share information about our TNE activities to international students, many positive features of our higher education can be used. (University 7)

In particular, the understanding of TNE managers towards how foreign markets perceive them serves as a foundation for market response strategies. Such responsiveness involves tailoring all elements of the marketing mix and deploying suitable marketing tactics, such as positioning and branding (Baker and Ballington, 2011; Raymundo-Delmonte, 2023). This underscores the important link between the developed country higher education image perception and its responsiveness in the market, as mentioned by the fourth focus group:

Positive perception towards UK higher education image creates between managers the spirit of assuming responsibility to protect this perception, hence TNE market information responsiveness is one of the protection manners. (Focus group 4)

Thus, the results of structural equation modelling in Table 6.24 confirmed the significance of developed country higher education image perception as an essential determinant of TNEMO. Hence, a more positive image of higher education in a developed country would serve as an enabler for direct generation, dissemination, and responsiveness to TNE markets.

7.5.3. Higher education international reputation: a consequence of TNE market orientation

As anticipated, the present results (Hypothesis 5a, 5b, and 5c; see Table 6.24) reveal a significant association between all aspects of TNEMO and the higher education international reputation. The generation, dissemination, and responsiveness to TNE market information are identified as key precursors to a higher education international reputation. This outcome implies that the impact of TNEMO on reputation is mainly an internal process within the TNE department. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, only Asaad's et al. (2015) study that has explored the outcomes of disseminating export market information in universities.

Previous research (Thatcher et al., 2016; Wilkins and Huisman, 2015) has identified market-oriented behaviours as a fundamental precursor to the reputation of universities. Similarly, marketing studies (Foroudi et al., 2016b; Gupta et al., 2011; Melewar et al., 2018; Miotto et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2018) highlight the role of certain marketing practices, such as marketing

communications, in establishing a strong international reputation for various types of universities. These marketing efforts are vital for enacting the information-centric actions characteristic of a market-oriented approach in higher education. As mentioned by Asaad et al. (2013), a market-oriented institution in higher education engages and communicates with its target market. Therefore, the information shared forms the foundation for developing a higher education international reputation.

The significance of Market Orientation in shaping the higher education international reputation is particularly pronounced at the global level. The challenges posed by geographical distances and the spread of foreign markets complicate the management of a university's reputation abroad. As a result, there is a heightened need for market-oriented initiatives to maintain and enhance the higher education international reputation when focusing on overseas markets. This research marks the first empirical investigation into the effects of TNEMO on the higher education international reputation. It concludes that the reputational outcomes of a TNE market-oriented approach are pertinent to the domain of higher education operating within a global framework. In response to a query about the expected benefits of adopting a TNEMO approach, the interviewees stated:

A TNE manager said that:

TNE market information generation supplies important information about how UK higher education is perceived by our international students. However, it is hard to control as it is a result of collective output of all UK universities but effective for quick interventions. (University 1)

An international partnership development manager's asserted:

TNE market information dissemination increases our personnel awareness of different matters such as international reputation of UK higher education, hence if managers are conscious ahead of the matter, then they will call an emergency meeting to discuss and find solutions. Also, good internal TNE market information dissemination can positively advance the solving of problems related to UK higher education international reputation. While the external dissemination of our good TNE market information through marketing can positively influence the

international students' opinion regarding the UK higher education reputation.
(University 2)

A TNE manager articulated:

The increase of international students' enrolment during the previous five years and the expansion of our TNE programmes and courses overseas are results of how effectively we respond to TNE market information and confirm the extent to which international students are satisfied about our higher education; this influences positively on their perception of the UK higher education reputation. (University 5)

7.5.4. TNE business performance: a consequence of TNE market orientation

Investigating the TNE business performance remains scarce (Hailat et al., 2019; Mac and Evangelist, 2016; Wilkins and Huisman, 2021), especially regarding the management aspect of business performance within the higher education sector (James and Derrick, 2021). In the study by Asaad and colleagues (2015) that explored the connection between EMO and university performance, the authors measured university performance through a managerial lens, focusing specifically on university export performance. Moreover, they assessed university export performance as a unified, comprehensive metric.

This study offers a different perspective on understanding a service export performance by examining TNE as an aspect of business performance from the managerial viewpoint. This approach aligns with James and Derrick's (2021) view of university performance as an organisational result stemming from the strategic orientation of universities. James and Derrick (2021) identify three key elements of TNE business performance: enrolment, revenues, and educational partnerships. Similarly, this study's findings highlight TNE business performance in terms of international student enrolment (Thatcher et al., 2016; Warwick, 2014), revenue from the recruitment of international students (Asaad et al., 2013), and the development of educational partnerships with numerous universities abroad (Yu et al., 2018). Some examples of comments include:

Participants from focus group 2 agreed that:

The effective responsiveness to TNE market information influences our alumni and leads to an increase in numbers of intakes and the enrolled international students.. (Focus group 2)

Marketing manager stated:

Responding to TNE market information can ameliorate the outcomes of our TNE practice, including increase of enrolment volume and revenues, where a large part of the enrolment comes from our alumni. (University 5)

TNE manager added that:

Having more than two intakes and TNE partners in all continents is a result of several improvements that we have done to our TNE curriculums, teaching methodology, research, and publications. (University 4)

Additionally, the qualitative study identified two other critical elements of TNE business performance. The first pertains to the share of the international student market that a university holds in comparison to other UK universities (Yu et al., 2018), The above TNE manager supported this by adding:

Therefore, the total number of our international students is considered one of the largest among UK universities. (University 4)

The qualitative study revealed, and the quantitative study confirmed, international students' satisfaction (Warwick, 2014; Wilkins and Huisman, 2021) as a key performance indicator. The findings indicate that TNE management places international students at the heart of their marketing strategies, thereby prioritising international students' satisfaction in their performance evaluations. This aspect was further validated through follow-up interviews, as illustrated by those two managers:

The surveys we undertake of our international students indicate a high satisfaction on our TNE, therefore, TNE market information generation is a measurement of TNE business performance. (University 6)

Responding to TNE market information can ameliorate the outcomes of our TNE practice, including increase of enrolment volume and revenues, where a large part of the enrolment comes from our alumni. This describes the satisfaction of international students and therefore affects positively the satisfaction of our university on TNE business performance. (University 5)

The current findings suggest that TNE market-oriented universities exhibit superior performance in their international markets. This aligns with earlier research (Asaad et al., 2013; James and Derrick, 2021; Yu et al., 2018; Warwick, 2014), which identified TNEMO activities as crucial predictors of TNE business performance. Similarly, literature on higher education marketing (Foroudi et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2017) supports a positive correlation between market orientation (MO) and the overall performance of TNE departments. The study's results indicate that the TNE market information generation (H6a) directly contributes to TNE business performance. Additionally, a positive impact of TNE market information dissemination (H6b) on TNE business performance was observed. Furthermore, the TNE market information responsiveness (H6c) was determined to be a significant determinant of TNE business performance (see Table 6.24).

Responsiveness to TNE market information was not emerged as the most pivotal aspect of TNEMO affecting TNE business performance compared to the other two dimension of TNEMO. However, this was similar to what Asaad et al. (2015) noted, that although generating and disseminating market information across the school or department are essential initial actions, it is the act of responding to this information that enables the meeting of market demands, thereby driving TNE business performance.

A TNE manager, in this regard, Indicated:

The market information we generate about TNE changes the old concept of how we affect the orientation of international students' decision towards our higher education programmes causing an increase of international attention to our TNE and increases our opportunity to remain active in TNE markets. (University 1)

Earlier studies have confirmed a connection between a unified global measure of TNEMO and export performance (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012; Warwick, 2014). The researcher goes a step further by examining the influence of various facets of TNEMO on the TNE

businesses performance, extending the scope beyond previous studies. Additionally, the study's findings aim to emphasise the applicability of TNEMO in realms beyond the higher education and marketing sectors, demonstrating its relevance in export and business literature.

7.5.5. Higher education international reputation and TNE business performance: a consequence of TNE market orientation

The relationship between higher education international reputation and TNE business performance was not statistically significant. The evaluation of the structural model indicates a non-relationship between the two constructs, where Hypothesis H7 (HIR → TBP, $\gamma = -0.72$) was rejected because it was not significantly different from 0 at the 0.001 level (see Table 26). Therefore, higher education international reputation cannot be considered a mediator between TNEOM and TNE business performance and has no significant influence on TNE business performance. Thus, Hypothesis H7 was deemed redundant, and the connection was removed from the model (see Figure 6.7).

Regarding Hypothesis 7, the result was not in line with Yu et al. (2017) in the context of universities, which found that the international reputation of a university significantly affects the selection of a study destination for international students. As a potential justification for this absence of an indirect connection, the study by Thatcher et al. (2016) argued that western universities do not limit their management to reputation; instead, they seek to enhance their competitiveness in a manner that creates and promotes a better identity. Thus, it is challenging to establish an influence from higher education international reputation on TNE business performance. Additionally, in the qualitative study, a member of focus group 4 expressed similar thinking:

The reputation of the UK higher education attracts the attention of international students, but we cannot confirm that all the UK universities that shape the higher education of this country are reputably equal. (Focus group 4)

This quotation describes the lack of connection between the higher education international reputation and TNE business performance constructs.

In addition to the above discussion, the measurement items quoted from relevant literature and qualitative study can be considered as factors for the unexpected non-significant connection between the two constructs (HIR and TBP). The qualitative data and literature were reviewed for a thorough critical examination of the resulting non-significant connection between higher education international reputation and TNE business performance.

The developed measurement items to evaluate the higher education international reputation and TNE business performance constructs had broad meanings. This could lead to a misunderstanding of questions when respondents (managers) filled out the questionnaire. However, the discriminant validity of the constructs was supported by the evaluation of the structural model, demonstrating adequacy between the measures of the constructs. Statistically, the estimated discriminant validity correlations were significant with $p < 0.05$ and differed from other operationalisations, where each construct is independent from the rest of the constructs (Hair et al., 2016; Peter and Churchill, 1986; Steenkamp and Baumgartner, 2000). Moreover, the cross-loadings between HIR and TBP measured variables were absent (see Table 6.24).

7.6. SUMMARY

This chapter has examined and discussed the results of the research based on theoretical expectations. The results of qualitative data were compared to the relevant literature and findings from the qualitative study (interviews and focus groups). Some comments quoted from the qualitative study enhanced the understanding of the studied phenomenon. Most suggested connections among the constructs were confirmed and statistically significant using structural equation modeling. However, the results illustrated that one of the proposed antecedents of TNEMO (i.e., university international ranking position) has a partial impact on TNEMO. It is statistically insignificant towards TNE market information generation and dissemination, but it does influence the TNE market information responsiveness and the developed country higher education image perception. Additionally, the results illustrated that higher education international reputation is not a mediating construct between TNEMO and TNE business performance.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

8.1. INTRODUCTION

This study has investigated the association among TNE market orientation (TNE market information generation, dissemination, and responsiveness), higher education reputation, and TNE business performance. The robust model presented in this research strongly contributes to understanding the phenomenon of TNE market orientation. The final model demonstrates a clear positive influence on higher education reputation and TNE business performance. Additionally, this study offers a novel perspective to the growing literature on TNE. Likely areas for additional research are indicated in the discussion of this study, and limitations are noted.

The researcher provides managerial implications for TNE managers and international office managers who aim to enhance higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. The results are expected to support future studies exploring additional avenues. Therefore, Chapter 8 outlines the research contributions in terms of theoretical, public policy, and managerial aspects. Section 8.2 discusses the implications of the research findings. Section 8.3 presents the research limitations along with implications and recommendations for future research directions. Section 8.4 summarises some key conclusions.

8.2. RESEARCH FINDINGS' IMPLICATIONS

The current research claims to apply effective contributions to literature. The major contribution responded to the literature's gaps such as 'How do universities in the UK perceive and practice TNE activities?'; 'What are the elements that shape TNE market orientation in the UK?'; 'What are the key factors that influence TNE market orientation in the UK?'; and 'What are the consequences/benefits of TNE market orientation according to UK universities?'

The following summarises the gaps in the literature. Firstly, there is a gap in systematic studies in marketing literature regarding the impact of effective TNE market orientation on universities' expansion and development (Asaad et al., 2015; He et al., 2018; Kleibert, 2023). Additionally, many universities lack the necessary advanced business capabilities for constructing comprehensive TNE business cases and managing international movements of individuals and finances across borders (British Council, 2018; Healey 2016). Furthermore, there's a lack of

research on how decision makers in TNE select partners or countries for expansion, emphasising the need for further investigation into success criteria among TNE providers (Grecic, 2022; Olssen, 2016; Raymundo-Delmonte, 2023). Compliance with host countries' rules and regulations poses another challenge in TNE due to the lack of accurate data (Healey, 2020). Despite the UK's historical leadership in international student recruitment, it has lost ground to competitors, necessitating a re-evaluation of strategies, particularly in revenue generation through TNE programs (Universities UK, 2018). Moreover, empirical research into the specifics of TNE market orientation is lacking in marketing literature (Asaad et al., 2015, Melewar et al., 2018). The researcher constructed this study to address these research gaps.

This research was introduced by differentiating among several approaches linked to TNE, including marketing orientation, marketisation of higher education, exporting in universities, EMO in universities, higher education customers, universities' business approach, and export performance (see Chapter 2). It posits that universities participating in TNE require strategic importance in addition to a multidisciplinary approach. TNE market orientation plays a crucial role in university practices, as its utilisation is regarded as a tangible indication of staying up-to-date with the export market of higher education.

This research tested managers' perception-based attribution of TNE market orientation and its antecedents and consequences. Evidence from qualitative studies illustrated the connection between TNE market orientation and the volume of university partnerships in TNE. Therefore, TNE market orientation is one of the marketing measures of the exporting in universities and is formed by a particular TNE coordination and the image perception of higher education in a developed country. A well-managed TNE market orientation must reflect the extent of the university's presence in the export of higher education. TNE market orientation can influence managers' perceptions at a university, thereby consolidating and strengthening the market share of international students (Healey, 2018). Since this research is unique in examining TNE market orientation and its connection to higher education international reputation and TNE business performance, it is difficult to make direct comparisons with previous research.

The results extend the opinions of scholars (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2020; James and Derrick, 2021) that the attribution of international students, concerning the export of higher education, could generate judgmental and attributional consequences (e.g., international reputation) (Olssen, 2016). Through a radical approach, the results permit it to contribute to marketing

theory. The contribution is to provide a broader understanding of the export of higher education parallel to marketing through TNE by examining whether TNEMO practices in universities impact their higher education international reputation and TNE business performance from the perspective of managers.

This research is considered one of the primary studies to experimentally support the hypothesis that TNE market orientation influences higher education international reputation and TNE business performance (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2018; Kayabasi et al., 2016; Yu et al., 2018) in the UK context. Therefore, this finding contributes significantly to the growth of knowledge and provides encouragement to refine and validate the findings in the literature related to this topic.

8.2.1. Theoretical contribution of the research

The literature will be enhanced by the following theoretical contributions: theory extension, conceptualisation and measurement of the theory, and testing and generalisation of the theory.

8.2.1.1. Extending the theory

The current research contributed to the literature of export marketing and higher education in different ways, through researching the developed hypotheses and bringing additional theoretical results. However, this research most evident contribution is the examination of the export market orientation construct within the TNE service context, setting the compound perception of TNE market orientation by manager. Regardless of the several research on EMO (Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; Cadogan *et al.*, 2012; James and Derrick, 2021; Jaworski and Kohli, 2017), only few studies have targeted this theory across services industry (Abbasov, 2019; Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2016). Therefore, the contribution of this study is towards the EMO theory through offering a validated framework that simulates the connections among the EMO construct in higher education (TNEMO), its antecedents and outcomes, with the goal of filling this gap and heeding prior appeals for studies on export marketing theories through the lens of international services marketers (Asaad et al., 2013).

The results of this study suggest that the core nature of the EMO construct remains consistent within the context of TNE. Furthermore, the aspects of TNEMO embraced by a university are linked also to the processes of generating, disseminating, and responding on information in the TNE market. Nevertheless, the presence of unique factors specific to the higher education

landscape such as the students are customers and degrees are intangible commodities (Dollinger and Lodge, 2019) necessitates adjustments to these factors when applying the EMO construct within a TNE context. Within this setting, the qualitative data revealed specific elements that reflect some distinctive features of higher education organisations. To illustrate, considering that universities offerings are regarded as a luxury provided to international students, careful delivery of programmes and courses is essential: "...quality education, research, and inventions are part of our priority to deliver good experience to international students..." Furthermore, attracting international students presents a significant experience for these students, thereby underscoring the need to incorporate the following element. "a control out of the whole TNE activities either among the university TNE management or with TNE partners, linking events, preparing for potential crisis, coordinating plans, and sharing opportunities or threats". Hence, this study broadens the application of the EMO theory within the realm of TNE.

The export market orientation has been frequently debated in literature, but without a systematic effort to examine similar characteristics relevant to all variation in findings within the total available projects (He et al., 2018; Jaworski and Kohli, 1993; Hemsley-Brown and Oblatka, 2010; Narver and Slater, 1990). Also, contributes to improve and test a standard that determines TNE market orientation with regards to its field of impact. Academically, the results use a more methodical and inclusive approach compared to any beforehand.

According to the conceptual framework, literature treated EMO within the service market as a unified measure in exploring its antecedents and outcomes (Cadogan *et al.*, 2012; Cadogan et al., 2016). However, this study conducted empirical investigations into the connections between each aspect of TNEMO, its antecedents, and its outcomes. This method of analysing each component separately provided a more thorough and nuanced comprehension of the elements that promote or hinder each TNE market-oriented activity, as well as the influence of each facet of TNEMO. As a result, this approach will provide managers with more concrete recommendations for carrying out certain actions to better specific results (e.g. to expand TNE activities' market share). Thus, the study results promise benefits in the TNE context.

8.2.1.2. Level of measurement and conceptualisation

The findings contribute to the continuing discussion on how TNE business performance is defined and measured. While previous studies have proposed a multidimensional construct for

business performance (Chung, 2012; Kumar et al., 2011; Murray et al., 2007), there remains a lack of agreement on the precise dimensions that make up higher education business performance (Asaad et al., 2015). This study introduced a novel perspective in defining and implementing the concept of TNE business performance within the context of universities. Export performance was identified as a unidimensional construct encompassing aspects such as satisfaction among international students, revenues, enrolment, and market share.

The results enrich the body of higher education literature, where the assessment of university business performance has been diverse and lacks a dominant construct definition (Healey, 2018; Zebal and Goodwin, 2012). A majority of research has identified business performance of higher education solely in terms of academic quality (Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016), with limited exploration from a business or organisational angle. This research in line with Hazelkorn (2018), focuses on the business dimension of TNE performance, thereby broadening the scope of knowledge in the higher education arena by adapting the notion of TNE business performance to the context of export market orientation.

The researcher aimed to expand the understanding of the MO-Export Performance theory in higher education. Past studies (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2016; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014) explored a direct relationship between EMO and export performance. Subsequent researchers (Asaad et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2018) filled this research gap by investigating how an organisation's international reputation mediates the impact of EMO on export performance. To test the applicability of this theory within the TNE context, the current study analysed the influence of the three primary elements of TNEMO (TNE market information generation, dissemination, and responsiveness) on higher education international reputation, and if this, in turn, affects TNE business performance. Thus, further contribution is added to the export marketing field.

While marketing is considered an important practice for internationally active universities (Knight and John, 2017), a considerable amount of the evidence available is based on conjecture or still anecdotal. Against this backdrop, this study further enriches the higher education marketing literature. It does so by offering a systematic approach to TNEMO, which in turn advises universities on the implementation of marketing strategies targeted at their international markets.

The current research is considered to be the first to operationalise and conceptualise the connotations of the effective TNE market orientation and its impacts on higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. This study achieves an attempt to build an additional premise with important implications for export marketing and higher education marketing.

8.2.1.3. Examination and generalisation of theory

Through examining the suggested model in the UK TNE context, the researcher expects to generate more insights from this research into the existing knowledge, then contribute to theory examining and generalisation. UK managers could possess special features that influence these research findings; the results may be popularised in other developed countries that export higher education (Asaad et al., 2015).

The measurements scales used in constructs were ensured through an examination process (identified, adopted and refined) to be reliable and valid and can be utilised in subsequent studies (Asaad et al., 2015; Cadogan et al., 2012). Additionally, the outcomes of the hypothesis tests show that all antecedents exert a direct or indirect influence on TNEMO within the UK universities. Moreover, TNEMO plays a direct role in boosting the higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. The results aid in identifying the determinants of TNEMO and the beneficial effects of adopting this approach within the specific setting of TNE. Furthermore, additional items were quoted from interviews and focus groups, to increase a good understanding of TNE market orientation and its constructs concept.

To summarise, this study marks the first effort to define and implement the concept of TNEMO and TNE business performance specifically in the context of the UK higher education. It merges insights from two distinct fields, export marketing and higher education marketing, aiming to establish a novel framework. This foundation is expected to have meaningful consequences for different managerial positions across The UK universities.

8.2.2. Managerial contribution of the research

This study provides several practical implications for those involved in international marketing for higher education, including top management and managers from various departments within the university such as international office, transnational education programmes development, and international partnership development.

The UK represents a favoured destination for international students from across the globe. The growing TNE activity of UK educational organisations underscores the importance of grasping and applying export marketing principles. Consequently, TNE marketing managers are strongly advised to consistently implement TNEMO strategies. Therefore, the TNE marketing managers can follow the practical advice of this research on how to effectively managing their marketing activities when targeting overseas markets. Universities with a focus on TNE markets should generate information, determine global opportunities, and respond to information globally. Additionally, A practical suggestion for TNE marketing managers is to include TNEMO measurement within their marketing strategies to address matters.

The beneficial impact that TNEMO has on the TNE business performance supports the call for its implementation within universities. TNEMO will assist various types of TNE managers to understand its significance role and its various aspects, then facilitate its implementation. Moreover, the results show that TNEMO contributes positively to the higher education international reputation. This observation is particularly valuable for TNE managers aiming to boost the higher education international reputation of their country, considering the critical role that external indicators play to influence the perceptions of transnational students towards TNE services (Tomlinson, 2017; Vangelis et al., 2018; Wilkins et al., 2012b).

Additionally, the research identified several factors that could promote the implementation of TNEMO. One variable examined in this study, specifically the university international ranking position, may be seen as an uncontrollable factor. University rankings internationally are challenging to influence because they are typically generated by independent and separate commercial publishers. Nonetheless, it is important for managers to understand the impact of this factor on crafting a TNE marketing strategy while adopting a TNEMO.

The study also leads to an insight regarding the influence of a university international ranking position on TNEMO. Universities with higher or lower ranking position should be driven by the TNE market. The ranking of a university would affect the nature of marketing efforts directed towards international markets and not only on the extent of TNEMO adopted. Thus, TNE managers at lower-ranked universities should not feel discouraged by their ranking. Instead, they should be motivated to engage in international competition by highlighting their unique strengths. While, TNE managers at highly ranked universities should emphasize their advantageous ranking status in their marketing initiatives.

When TNE managers understand the demands of the international market, along with recognising their university's ranking and any other strengths or weaknesses, they could make informed choices about which export markets to pursue or the most suitable channels to meet the markets' demands. Therefore, they have a fundamental role to implement the TNEMO activities, however, this can only be achieved by well-established coordination.

TNE coordination with various departments inside and outside the university is crucial. The primary managerial consequences of this research concern the deep link between TNE coordination and TNEMO. Given that this factor is largely controllable, a clear action point for senior management aiming to encourage TNEMO practices within the university is to explicitly highlight the significance of TNEMO to heads of school and managers of other departments inside (schools and branch campuses) and outside (partners) the university. Additionally, senior management should stress the need for efficient TNE coordination between all departments linked to the TNE marketing department.

Senior management can assess the university's organisational structure to identify opportunities for improving TNE coordination (e.g. making internal communication systems and processes designed to support seamless cross-departmental dialogue). Also, the issue of organisational conflict within the university deserves attention, as disagreements between departments over adopting an TNEMO strategy may undermine the success of planned marketing initiatives. A well control of organisational conflict can foster a more effective TNEMO approach within university. It is observed that a sense of unified vision within the university is related to those managerial programmes aimed at enhancing communication, promoting shared values, and mitigating counterproductive conflict.

Managers across various departments of university need to be more attuned to the needs of TNE markets, especially since responsiveness to TNE market information significantly influences the outcomes of TNEMO. Therefore, there is a need for managers to initiate service improvement programmes to enhance both primary and supplementary TNE services. This involves adopting a listening stance towards international students to better understand and meet their needs, ultimately improving their overall experience and boosting the university's international reputation and TNE business performance. Then, it is crucial to invest in marketing efforts that highlight the university's strengths, serving as another strategy to manage and enhance its international standing.

The strong link found between the developed country higher education image perception and responsiveness to TNE market information implies that top TNE managers should focus on promoting a positive image of their country's higher education system to their university's senior TNE managers. It is important to incorporate positive views of the developed country's higher education image into promotional strategies (e.g. emphasising the UK's long-standing tradition of excellence in higher education and its host of renowned universities). Furthermore, TNE managers of various UK universities should collaborate to foster and present a unified image of UK higher education as a whole.

Finally, the results of this study, as explained in the previous chapter, can support TNE and marketing managers and be applied in other developed countries such as USA, Australia, and Canada.

8.2.3. Contribution to policymakers (public policy)

The current study aligns with the keen interest of policymakers in promoting the international expansion of universities. TNE is attractive due to its positive effects on a nation's balance of payments and its contribution to the economy (Greene et al., 1989; Rossano et al., 2016; Wilkins et al., 2012b). There is a growing expectation from governments for their domestic universities to be more dynamic, financially self-sufficient, and therefore more attuned to TNE markets (Knight, 2011; Rinaldi et al., 2018; Williamson, 2021). The empirical model introduced in this study provides guidelines on TNE marketing strategies that are advantageous for universities and acts as a blueprint for national policymakers to facilitate the adoption of these strategies in educational institutions. Importantly, the government of the UK and other developed countries have shown considerable support for the TNE by implementing promotional strategies that enhance the recruitment of international students and the provision of education abroad (Healey, 2020; Kaplan, 2001). This highlights the strong interest of some governments towards TNE services. Thus, the contribution of the TNEMO study to public policymakers lies in several key areas:

Informing Policy Development:

The insights from TNEMO studies can help policymakers understand the dynamics of the global education market and the factors that drive the success of TNE initiatives. This understanding is crucial for developing policies that foster a supportive environment for TNE programmes, including regulations, quality assurance standards, and funding mechanisms.

Guiding Quality Assurance and Accreditation:

By identifying the components that contribute to effective TNEMO, such as TNE market information generation, TNE dissemination, and TNE responsiveness, TNEMO study can guide the development of quality assurance frameworks that ensure the delivery of high-quality education across borders. Policymakers such as the General Agreement on Tariffs and trade of Services (GATS), can use these frameworks to regulate TNE programmes and protect students' interests.

Enhancing International Collaboration:

TNEMO research can highlight the benefits of international collaboration in higher education, encouraging policymakers to pursue and facilitate partnerships between domestic and foreign educational institutions. This can lead to the development of joint degrees, research collaborations, and student exchange programmes that enhance the educational experience and global competitiveness of students.

Supporting Economic Development:

Policymakers can leverage TNEMO findings to position education as a key driver of economic development. By understanding how TNE contributes to the export of education services, policymakers can promote higher education as a strategic sector that attracts international students, fosters innovation, and contributes to the knowledge economy.

Addressing Market Needs:

TNEMO studies can provide policymakers with insights into the needs and preferences of international students and the evolving demands of the global job market. This can inform the design of curricula, the development of skills-oriented programmes, and the implementation of policies that ensure the alignment of TNE offerings with market needs, enhancing the employability of graduates.

Promoting Social and Cultural Exchange:

By understanding the marketing strategies that effectively attract international students, policymakers can support initiatives that not only boost educational exports but also promote social and cultural exchange. This can enhance mutual understanding, foster global networks, and build soft power.

In essence, the TNEMO study offers a comprehensive framework for public policymakers to understand and support the complex ecosystem of TNE, ensuring that it contributes positively to educational quality, economic development, and cultural diplomacy.

8.3. LIMITATIONS OF RESEARCH AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The presented study breaks through the conceptualisation of TNEMO, addressing its presence in higher education international reputation and TNE business performance. However, these outcomes must be explained with regard to several significant limitations that could be addressed in future studies (e.g., sampling and analysis methods, and measurement); more explanation is provided below.

8.3.1. Limitations of the research

The research seeks to create a greater understanding of the TNEMO construct and its main antecedents and consequences, even though the results are associated with limitations. The limitations of the study are reflected in the sampling and analysis methods, as well as in the measurement level.

8.3.1.1. Method of sampling and analysis

This study employed a method of sampling/analysis with limitations that must be considered. The study was conducted in one setting, focusing on a context related to the UK. The results in other countries may not align with those of the current research. Subsequently, for future research, it is suggested to replicate TNE market orientation studies in different countries to enhance the generalisability of the results.

Furthermore, the research also conducted the survey questionnaire in relation to all UK universities with the intention of covering a large sample size to fulfil the requirements of the adopted SEM approach in this study (Hair et al., 2016). However, the study was restricted by the limited number of 142 UK universities, where the sample size achieved only 336 cases, but it met the required sample size to use the AMOS technique (Byrne, 2001; Foroudi et al., 2021a). The pandemic limited the process of data collection to include only digital means of communication due to the lockdown. Additionally, the number of respondents from each university was limited to an average of two managers from every participating university, which cannot fully reflect all TNE managers' opinions. Furthermore, the research was unable

to visit universities and meet marketing managers and heads of TNE face-to-face, as most respondents participated through requests made by the British Universities International Liaison Association (BUILA). In future research, it is suggested to include a larger sample size than in this study and to make personal contact with different levels of marketing managers from every participating university to enhance the reliability and validity of responses.

This topic might have another limitation inherent in its research design. The researcher adopted semi-structured interviews and focus groups with TNE marketing experts to examine their beliefs, feelings, understanding, and experience about the research concept and also to produce more items for measurement. Thus, additional research related to this aspect is recommended, as this study aligns with qualitative questions, which might have limited opportunities to generalise items for measurement.

Also, in the research design, the quantitative study was limited to university managers relevant to TNE. However, the study did not consider the perspective of international students (representing a one-sided view). In fact, university managers are more likely to remain discreet about some aspects that could negatively affect their organisational structure, compared to students who might openly share their experiences. Incorporating the perspective of international students would broaden the study's scope. Thus, the findings could differ if future research includes international students, and interpreting the results should be done with greater care.

8.3.1.2. Measurement limitations

This pioneering research in the field is considered to be the first to examine the construct of TNEMO, along with its antecedents and outcomes, drawing from the limited existing literature. To improve the validity of the study's measurement scales, additional research must be conducted.

Regarding the measurement level, the study adopts the creation of new scales, adjusted from the existing literature, and revised and expanded by incorporating findings from interviews and focus groups. Similar to marketing research, every measurement was thoroughly examined before conducting the survey. Thus, significant efforts are required in future research to refine and expand the suggested measurement scales. Furthermore, this research must be replicated, and its scales extended for use in other samples to enhance validity.

Research in the future might yield different results based on the same research constructs and scales. Even though the researcher used mixed methods, extended research could enrich the literature concerning the concept of TNEMO. However, the availability of resources limits the inclusion of information deemed beyond the scope of this study. Despite these limitations, the research results remain significant.

8.3.2. Future studies avenues

It is important to clarify that this study's objective is not to present a sophisticated approach to TNEMO, but rather to examine it on a micro level by determining the key TNE-specific antecedents and outcomes of TNEMO. However, scholars (Asaad et al., 2015; James and Derrick, 2021) have identified the significance of the macro environment (e.g., regulatory and economic factors) in shaping the behavioural marketing strategy of TNE. Therefore, future studies can incorporate additional variables that address the macro environment of higher education in the TNEMO framework. For instance, exploring the influence of quality assurance control with overseas partners on the association between TNEMO and performance could be an extension of this study in the future. Additionally, investigating the economic performance as another factor influencing the TNE expansion strategy of universities in developed countries could shape the potential field of research in the future.

Bearing in mind that this research is the first effort to conceptualize TNEMO in the UK context, further studies are invited to enhance the development of this field with consideration of various stakeholders (e.g., international students, parents) (Busch, 2017; Caruana and Montgomery, 2015). Additionally, investigating specific modes of TNE services, such as blended education overseas, would be beneficial (Bilencen, 2020; Williamson, 2021). Therefore, future research is necessary to explore whether the domain constructs of TNEMO vary and if the connection of the suggested model differs depending on the type of TNE activity. Another worthwhile direction for further study is to focus on a specific course or program relevant to a particular TNE to enhance the understanding of the influences on TNEMO and its consequences accurately (Healey, 2020).

The foundation of this study lies in the insights provided by managers. However, it is imperative to incorporate the viewpoints of academics and international students in future investigations on TNEMO, as they constitute significant stakeholders in universities. This approach signifies a revitalisation of Marketing Office (MO) theory within TNE. The commitment of academics to TNEMO is crucial because effective marketing strategies extend beyond the responsibilities of the international marketing office alone. Successful TNE marketing requires coordination across all university departments. Furthermore, there's a need for further exploration to ascertain whether the components of the TNEMO construct evolve over time and which metrics indicate effective for specific stakeholders of TNE like managers, academics, and public policy. Consequently, an additional area of focus should be assessing the impact of TNEMO on academic quality and redefining performance in terms of academic excellence.

8.4. SUMMARY

The present study contributes to the understanding of the role of TNEMO in fostering the international reputation of higher education institutions and enhancing the performance of TNE businesses. It represents the primary experimental research conducted within the UK TNEMO context. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the researcher aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of this complex phenomenon to ensure accurate results. Utilising interviews and focus groups, the study facilitated the development of a theoretical framework, which was subsequently tested through a survey. The research meticulously examines methodological decisions and their impact on the relationships among TNEMO, its antecedents, and its consequences. The study offers insights into the relevant findings concerning the development and validation of TNEMO within a managerial context.

SEM was employed to analyse the collected data, reflecting satisfactory psychometric properties. The results indicate that TNEMO is influenced by TNE coordination and the perceived image of higher education institutions in developed countries, which, in turn, is influenced by their international ranking positions. Furthermore, the study underscores TNEMO as an intangible asset that university managers leverage to attract the attention of international students and fulfill their objectives. Additionally, the structural equation analysis demonstrates satisfactory fit indices and construct validity. However, the results also reveal some insignificant relationships within the construct. Notably, previous research on TNEMO lacked theoretical justification, making this study the first to establish the current construct.

Due to certain limitations, further research has been recommended to bolster this field of study. In future investigations, it is advisable to validate additional measurements and explore the relationships among the concepts in consideration of various stakeholders' perspectives in different countries.

REFERENCES

- Abbasov, A. (2019) *Revitalizing the Soviet Higher Education Export: Comparative Case Study of IBCs in Six Post-Soviet Countries*, New York: Teachers College, Columbia University.
- Abrahams, J. and Brooks, R. (2019) 'Higher education students as political actors: Evidence from England and Ireland'. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 22(1), pp. 108-123.
- Acikdilli, G. (2015) 'Marketing Capabilities-Export Market Orientation and Export Performance Relationship: Establishing an Empirical Link', *Advances in Business Related Scientific Research Journal*, 6(1), pp. 49-62.
- Agasisti, T. and Soncin, M. (2021) 'Higher education in troubled times: on the impact of Covid-19 in Italy', *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(1), pp. 86-95.
- Ahimbisibwe, G., Ntayi J., and Ngoma, M. (2013) 'Export Market Orientation, Innovation and Performance of Fruit Exporting Firms in Uganda', *European Scientific Journal*, 9(4), pp. 295-313. Accessed September, 2018 <http://www.eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/view/782>
- Alotaibi, B. J., and Zhang, Y. (2017) 'The relationship between export market orientation and export performance: an empirical study', *Applied Economics*, 49(23), pp. 2253-2258.
- Altbach, P., and de Wit, H. (2020) 'Rethinking the Relevance of International Branch Campuses', *International Higher Education*, 35(1), pp. 14-16.
- Amaia, L., Pilar, Z., and Javier, F. (2018), 'A review of higher education image and reputation literature: Knowledge gaps and a research agenda', *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 24(1), pp. 8-16.
- Anderson, J. C., and Gerbing, D. W. (1982) 'Some methods for respecifying measurement models to obtain unidimensional construct measurement', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 12(4), pp. 453-460.
- Andriopoulos, C. and Lewis, M. (2009) 'Exploitation-exploration tensions and organisational ambidexterity: Managing paradoxes of innovation', *Organisation Science, Special Issue on Ambidextrous Organisations*, 20(4), pp. 696-717.
- Arenas, A., Barca, D. J. and Rosemartin, D. S. (2015) 'Successes and snags of a sustainability course in higher education', *International Journal of Innovation and Sustainable Development*, 9(3/4), pp. 365-383.
- Armstrong, J. and Overton, S. (1977) 'Estimating Nonresponse Bias in Mail Surveys', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 14, pp. 396-402.

- Asaad, Y., Melewar, T. C., and Cohen, G. (2015) 'Export market-orientation behaviour of universities: The British scenario', *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 25, pp. 127-154.
- Asaad, Y., Melewar, T. C., Cohen, G., and Balmer, J. M. T. (2013) 'Universities and Export Market Orientation: An Exploratory Study of UK Post-92 Universities', *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, 31(7), pp. 838-56.
- Ashwin, P. and McVitty, D. (2015) 'The meanings of student engagement: Implications for policies and practices', in A. Curaj, L. Matei, R. Pricopie, J. Salmi, and P. Scott (Eds.), *The European higher education area*, pp. 343-359.
- Bachan, R. (2017) 'Grade inflation in UK higher education', *Studies in Higher Education*, 428, pp. 1580-1600.
- Baker, M., and Ballington, L. (2011) 'Country of origin as a source of competitive advantage', *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 10(1), pp. 157-168.
- Ball, S. (2012) *Global education Inc*. London: Routledge.
- Bamberger, A., Morris, P., and Yemini, M. (2019) 'Neoliberalism, Internationalisation and Higher Education: Connections, Contradictions and Alternatives', *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 40(2), pp. 203-216.
- Bastedo, M., and Bowman, N. (2010) 'US news and world report college rankings: Modelling institutional effects on organizational reputation', *American Journal of Education*, 116(2), pp. 163-183.
- Bell, D. V. J. (2016) 'Twenty first century education: Transformative education for sustainability and responsible citizenship', *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 18(1), pp. 48-56.
- Beneke, J., Blampied, S., Dewar, N., and Soriano, L. (2016) 'The impact of market orientation and learning orientation on organisational performance: A study of small to medium-sized enterprises in Cape Town', *South Africa. Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship*, 18(1), pp. 90-108.
- Bennell, P. (2022) 'Limits to growth? Key enrolment trends for UK transnational higher education', *Higher Education*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-022-00902-z>.
- Bilecen, B. (2020) 'Commentary: COVID-19 Pandemic and Higher Education: International Mobility and Student's Social Protection', *International Migration*, 58, 4, pp 263-266. Accessed May, 2021 <https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12749>

- Binsardi, A. and Ekwulugo, F. (2003) 'International marketing of British education: Research on the students' perception and the UK market penetration', *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, 21(4/5), pp. 318-327.
- Birru, W. T., Runhaar, P., Zaalberg, R., Lans, T. and Mulder, M. (2019) 'Explaining organizational export performance by single and combined international business competencies', *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(3), pp. 1172-1192.
- Bleiklie, I., Enders, J., and Lepori, B. (2017) *Managing universities: Policy and organizational change in a western European comparative perspective*. London: Palgrave Macmillan/Springer.
- Bobe, B. J. and Kober, R. (2015) 'Measuring organisational capabilities in the higher education sector', *Education + Training*, 57(3), pp. 322-342.
- Bollen, K. A. (1989) *Structural Equations with Latent Variables*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, US.
- Boso, N., Annan, J., Adeleye, I., Iheanachor, N., and Narteh, B. (2018) 'Examining the paths from export strategic orientations to export performance: The mediating role of export resource transformation capability', *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 60(2), pp. 207-230.
- Bovill, C., Jordan, L. and Watters, N. (2015) 'Transnational approaches to teaching and learning in higher education: challenges and possible guiding principles', *Teaching in Higher Education*, 20(1), pp. 12-23.
- Bovill, C. (2017) *Breaking Down Staff-Student Barriers: Moving Towards Pedagogic Flexibility*, In *Pedagogic Frailty and Resilience in the University*, edited by I. M. Kinchin and N. Winstone, pp. 151-61.
- Bowles, T. V. and Brindle, K. A. (2017) 'Identifying facilitating factors and barriers to improving student retention rates in tertiary teaching courses: A systematic review', *Higher Education Research and Development*, 36(5), pp. 903-919.
- Boyd, B. Bergh, D., and Ketchen, D. (2010) 'Reconsidering the reputation-performance relationship: a resource-based view', *Journal of Management*, 36(3), pp. 588-609.
- Brankovic, J. (2018) 'The status games they play: Unpacking the dynamics of organisational status competition in higher education', *Higher Education*, 75(4), pp. 695-709.
- Brankovic, J., Ringel, L., and Werron, T. (2018) 'How rankings produce competition: The case of Global University rankings', *Zeitschrift für Soziologie*, 47(4), pp. 270-288.
- British Council (2018). Annual Report & Accounts 2017-2018. Accessed November, 2023 <https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/2017-18-annual-report.pdf>

- Brooks R. (2019) 'The construction of higher education students within national policy: A cross-European comparison', *Compare*, 48(4), pp. 500-517.
- Brown, D., Foroudi, P. and Hafeez, K. (2019) 'Marketing management capability: the construct, and its dimensions: An examination of managers and entrepreneurs' perception in the retail setting', *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 22(5), pp. 609-637.
- Brown, R. (2015) 'The marketisation of higher education: Issues and ironies: New Vistas', *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 1(1), pp. 4-9.
- Brown, R. and Carasso, H. (2013) *Everything for sale? The marketisation of UK higher education*, [London]: Routledge.
- Brown, S. (2011) 'Bringing about positive change in the higher education student experience: a case study: Quality Assurance in Education', *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 19(3), pp. 195-207.
- Bryman, A. (2015) *Social research methods*: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A. (2016) *Social research methods (5th ed.)*. Oxford, 373-374.
- Bryman, A. and Bell, E. (2015) *Business research methods*: Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Bunce, L., Baird, A., and Jones, S. E. (2017) 'The student-as-consumer approach in higher education and its effects on academic performance', *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(11), pp. 1958-1978.
- Burgess, P. and Berquist, B. (2012) 'Cross-border delivery: Programmes, programmes, and providers', In D. K. Deardorff, J. Heyl, and T. Adams (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of international higher education*, pp. 325-342. London: Sage.
- Busch, L. (2017) *Knowledge for sale: The neoliberal takeover of higher education*. MIT Press
- Byrne, B. M. (2001) *Structural Equation Modeling with AMOS*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, New Jersey, US.
- Cadogan, J. W., Cui, R. E., and Morgan, V. M. (2006) 'Story Factors facilitating and impeding the development of export market-oriented behaviour: A study of Hong Kong manufacturing exporters', *Industrial Marketing Management*, 35(5), pp. 634-647.
- Cadogan, J. W., Sundqvist, S., Salminen, R.T., and Puumalainen, K. (2016) 'Export market orientation and international performance in the context of SMEs' *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 28(5), pp. 361-375.

- Cadogan, J. W., Kuivalainen, O., Sundqvist, S. (2009) 'Export market-oriented behavior and export performance: Quadratic and moderating effects under differing degrees of market dynamism and internationalization', *Journal of International Marketing*, 17(4), pp. 71-89.
- Cadogan, J. W., Diamantopoulos, A., and De Mortanges, C. P. (1999) 'A measure of export market orientation: Scale development and cross-cultural validation', *Journal of International Business Studies*, 30(4), pp. 689-707.
- Cadogan, J. W., Diamantopoulos, A., and Siguaw, J. A. (2002) 'Export market-oriented activities: Their antecedents and performance consequences', *Journal of International Business Studies*, 33(3), pp. 615-626
- Cadogan, J. W., Sundqvist, S., Puumalainen, K., and Salminen, R. T. (2012) 'Strategic flexibilities and export performance: The moderating roles of export market-oriented behaviour and the export environment', *European Journal of Marketing*, 46(10), pp. 1418-1452.
- Carasso, H. and Locke, W. (2015) *Paying the price of expansion: Dimensions of Marketisation in Higher Education*, pp. 26-37.
- Carey, P. (2018) 'The impact of institutional culture, policy and process on student engagement in university decision-making', *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 22(1), pp. 11-18.
- Caruana, V. and Montgomery, C. (2015) 'Understanding the transnational higher education landscape: shifting positionality and the complexities of partnership', *Learning and Teaching*, 8(1), pp. 5-29.
- Casidy, R. (2014) 'The role of perceived market-orientation in the higher education sector', *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 22, pp. 155-163.
- Chabowski, B., Kekec, P., Morgan, G. N. A., Hult, T. M., Walkowiak, T., and Runnalls, B. (2018) 'An Assessment of the Exporting Literature: Using Theory and Data to Identify Future Research Directions', *Journal of International Marketing*, 26(1), pp. 118-143.
- Chang, W., Franke, G. R., Butler, T. D., Musgrove, C. F., and Ellinger, A. E. (2014) 'Differential Mediating Effects of Radical and Incremental Innovation on Market Orientation-Performance Relationship: A Meta-Analysis', *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 22(3), pp. 235-250.
- Chang, Y. S. and Fang, S. R. (2015) 'Enhancing export performance for business markets: Effects of interorganizational relationships on export market orientation (EMO)', *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing*, 22(3), pp. 211-228.

- Chankseliani, M., Qoraboyev I., and Gimranova. D. (2020) 'Higher Education Contributing to the Local, National, and Global Development: New Empirical and Conceptual Insights', *Higher Education*, 50(3), pp. 250-260.
- Chankseliani, M. (2017) 'Four Rationales of HE Internationalisation: Perspectives of UK Universities on Attracting Students from Former Soviet Countries', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 22(1), pp. 53-70.
- Christensen, T., Ramirez, F. O., and Gornitzka, A. (Eds.). (2018) *Universities as agencies, Reputation and professionalization*, Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Chubb, J. and Watermeyer, R. (2017) 'Artifice or integrity in the marketization of research impact? Investigating the moral economy of (pathways to) impact statements within research funding proposals in the UK and Australia', *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(12), pp. 2360-2372.
- Chung, H. F. (2012) 'Export market orientation, managerial ties, and performance', *International Marketing Review*, 29(4) pp. 403-423.
- Churchill, G. A. (1979) 'A paradigm for developing better measures of marketing constructs', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 16(1), pp. 64-74.
- Churchill, G. A. (1999) *Marketing Research: Methodological Foundations*, The Dryden Press, IL.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K. (2011) *Planning educational research: Research methods in education*: New York: Routledge Editors.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013) *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches (3rd ed)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches (4th ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crick, J. M. (2021) 'The dimensionality of the market orientation construct', *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 29(4), pp. 281-300.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1951) 'Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests', *Psychometrika*, 16(3), pp. 297-334.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1984) *Essentials of Psychological Testing*, Harper and Row, NY.
- Cuomo, M. T., Tortora, D., Foroudi, P., Giordano, A., Festa, G., and Metallo, G. (2021) 'Digital transformation and tourist experience co-design: Big social data for planning cultural tourism', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 162, 120345.
- Czinkota, M., Kaufmann, H. R., and Basile, G. (2014) 'The relationship between legitimacy, reputation, sustainability and branding for companies and their supply chains', *Industrial Marketing Management*, 43, pp. 91-101.

- Davey, T. (2015) *Entrepreneurship at Universities – Exploring the Factors Influencing the Development of Entrepreneurship at Universities* (Amsterdam, University-Industry Innovation Network Publishing).
- de Wit, H. and Altbach, P. G. (2021) ‘Internationalization in higher education: global trends and recommendations for its future’, *Policy Reviews in Higher Education*, 5(1), pp. 28-46.
- De Vaus, D. (2002) *Surveys in social research*, Routledge: London.
- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. K. (2017) *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative research (5th ed.)*. SAGE Publications, Manchester Metropolitan University, UK.
- Devece, C., Llopis-Albert, C., and Palacios-Marqués, D. (2017) ‘Market-orientation, organizational performance, and the mediating role of crowdsourcing in knowledge-based firms’, *Psychology and Marketing*, 34, pp. 1127-1134.
- DeVellis, R. F. (2003) *Scale Development: Theory and Application, Second Edition*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Diamantopoulos, A., and Cadogan, J. W. (1996) ‘Internationalizing the market orientation construct: an in-depth interview approach’, *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 4, 1, pp. 23-52.
- Diamantopoulos, A., Sarstedt, M., and Fuchs, C. (2012) ‘Guidelines for choosing between multi-item and single-item scales for construct measurement: a predictive validity perspective’, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 40, pp. 434-449.
- Diamantopoulos, A., Ring, A., Schlegelmilch, B. B., and Doberer, E. (2014) ‘Drivers of export segmentation effectiveness and their impact on export performance’, *Journal of International Marketing*, 22(1), pp. 39-61.
- Dollinger, M., and Lodge, J. (2019) ‘Student-staff co-creation in higher education: evidence informed model to support future design and implementation’, *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, pp. 1-15. Accessed May, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2019.1663681>
- Drucker, P. F. (1954) *The practice of management*. New York: Harper & Brothers.
- Dwyer, T. (2022) ‘Conceptualisations of market orientation in the higher education literature’, *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, pp.1-23. Accessed March, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08841241.2022.2089941>
- Edirisinghe, D., Nazarian, A., Foroudi, P., and Lindridge, A. (2020) ‘Establishing psychological relationship between customers and retailers: a study of the clothing retail industry’, *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 23(3), pp. 471-501.
- Espeland, W. N. and Sauder, M. (2016) *Engines of anxiety. Academic rankings, reputation, and accountability*. New York, NY: Russel Sage Foundation.

- Fakhreddin, F., Foroudi, P., and Ghahroudi, M. R. (2021) 'The bidirectional complementarity between market orientation and launch proficiency affecting new product performance', *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 26(s2), pp. 1-21.
- Fang, S. R., Chang, E., Ou, C. C., and Chou, C. H. (2014) 'Internal market orientation, market capabilities and learning orientation', *European Journal of Marketing*, 48(2), pp. 170-192.
- Feldman, Z. and Sandoval, M. (2018) 'Metric Power and the Academic Self: Neoliberalism, Knowledge and Resistance in the British University', *Triple C*, 16(1), pp. 214-233.
- Field, A. (2009) *Discovering Statistics using SPSS*, Sage Publications, London.
- Field, A. (2013) *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics (4th ed.)*. SAGE Publications, London.
- Firmansyah, D., Saepuloh, D., and Kurniawan, B. (2023) 'Market Orientation as a Culture Aspect: Marketing and Leadership Style of Principals', *Formosa Journal of Applied Sciences*, 2(2), pp. 279-302. <https://doi.org/10.55927/fjas.v2i2.3085>.
- Fombrun, C. J. and Van Riel, C. B. M. (2004) *Fame and fortune: how successful companies build winning reputation*, Financial Times Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- Fornell, C. and Larcker, D. (1981) 'Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), pp. 39-50.
- Foroudi, P., Gupta, S., Kitchen, P., Foroudi, M.M., and Nguyen, B. (2016a) 'A framework of place branding, place image, and place reputation: antecedents and moderators', *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 19(2), pp. 241-264.
- Foroudi, P., Jin, Z., Gupta, S., Melewar, T. C., and Foroudi, M. M. (2016b) 'Influence of innovation capability and customer experience on reputation and loyalty', *Journal of Business Research*, 69(11), pp. 4482-4489.
- Foroudi, P., Melewar, T. C., and Gupta, S. (2014) 'Linking corporate logo, corporate image, and reputation: An examination of consumer perceptions in the financial setting', *Journal of Business Research*, 67(11), pp. 2269-2281.
- Foroudi, P., Palazzo, M., and Stone, M. (2021a) *Mixed methods research: why and how to use it. In: The Routledge Companion to Marketing Research*. Wright, Len Tiu, Moutinho, Luiz, Stone, Merlin and Bagozzi, Richard P., eds. Routledge Companions in Business, Management and Marketing. Routledge, London / New York, pp. 73-106.
- Foroudi, P., Palazzo, and Sultana, A. (2021b) 'Linking brand attitude to word-of-mouth and revisit intention in the restaurant sector', *British Food Journal*, 23 (13), pp. 221-240.

- Foroudi, P., Yu, Q., Gupta, S., and Faroudi, M. M. (2019) 'Enhancing university brand image and reputation through customer value co-creation behaviour', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 138, pp. 218-227.
- Foroudi, P., Dinnie, K., Kitchen, P. J., Melewar, T. C., and Foroudi, M. M. (2017) 'IMC antecedents and the consequences of planned brand identity in higher education', *European Journal Of Marketing.*, 51(3), pp. 528-550.
- Frosen, J., Luoma, J., Jaakkola, M., Tikkanen, H., and Aspara, J. (2016) 'What Counts Versus What Can Be Counted: The Complex Interplay of Market Orientation and Marketing Performance Measurement', *Journal of Marketing*, 80(3), pp. 60-78.
- Garrett, R. (2018) 'International Branch Campuses: Success Factors', *International Higher Education*, 2(93), pp. 14-16.
- Garrett, R., Kinser, K., Lane, J. E., and Merola, R. (2016) 'International Branch Campuses—Trends and Developments 2016', *OBHE with SUNY*, Albany, and Pennsylvania State University.
- Ghobehei, M., Sadeghvaziri, F., Ebrahimi, E., and Bakeshoo, K. A. (2019) 'The effects of perceived brand orientation and perceived service quality in the higher education sector', *Eurasian Business Review*, 9, pp. 347-365.
- Ghorbani, H., Dalvi, M. R., and Hirmanpour, I. (2014) 'Studying the effect of market orientation on marketing effectiveness case study: Hotels in Isfahan province', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(1), pp. 570-579.
- Girdzijauskaitė, E., Radzevičienė, A., and Jakubavičius, A. (2019) 'Impact of international branch campus KPIs on the university competitiveness: FARE method', *Insights into Regional Development*, 1(2), pp. 171-180. Accessed May, 2020 [https://doi.org/10.9770/ird.2019.1.2\(7\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/ird.2019.1.2(7))
- Glaveli, N., and Geormas, K. (2018) 'Doing well and doing good: Exploring how strategic and market-orientation impacts social enterprise performance', *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 24, pp. 147-170.
- Gnangnon, S. K. (2021) 'Manufacturing Exports and Services Export Diversification', *The International Trade Journal*, 35(3), pp. 221-242.
- Gouvea, R., Kassicieh, S., and Montoya, M. J. R. (2013) 'Using the quadruple helix to design strategies for the green economy', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 80(2), pp. 221-230.
- Grant, C. (2013) *Losing our Chains? Contexts and Ethics of University Internationalisation*. Stimulus Paper Series, Leadership Foundation for HE, London.

- Grecic, D. (2022) 'The epistemological chain: A tool to guide TNE development', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, pp.1-16, SAGE Publications.
- Greene, J. C., Caracelli, V. J., and Graham, W. F. (1989) 'Toward a Conceptual Framework for Mixed-method Evaluation Designs', *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 11(3), pp. 255-74.
- Gruber-Muecke, T. and Hofer, K. M. (2015) 'Market orientation, entrepreneurial orientation, and performance in emerging markets', *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 10(3), pp. 560-571.
- Guerrero, M., Cunningham J. A., and Urbano, D. (2015) 'Economic impact of entrepreneurial universities' activities: An exploratory study of the United Kingdom', *Research Policy*, 44, pp. 748-764.
- Guilbault, M. (2016) 'Students as customers in higher education: Reframing the debate', *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 26(2), pp. 132-142.
- Guilbault, M. (2018) 'Students as customers in higher education: The (controversial) debate needs to end'. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 40, pp. 295-298.
- Gupta, S., Melewar, T. C., and Bourlakis, M. (2010) 'Transfer of brand knowledge in business-to-business markets: a qualitative study', *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 25(5), pp. 395-403
- Gupta, S., Navare, J., and Melewar, T. C. (2011) 'Investigating the implications of business and culture on the behaviour of customers of international firms', *Industrial Marketing Management*, 40(1), pp. 65-77.
- Guruz, K. (2011) *Higher Education and International Student Mobility in the Global Knowledge Economy*. Albany: State University of New York Press.
- Hafeez, K., Foroudi, P., Dinnie, K., Nguyen, B., and Parahoo, S. K. (2016) 'The role of place branding and image in the development of sectoral clusters: The case of Dubai', *Journal of Brand Management*, 23(4), 383-402.
- Hailat, K. Q., Alshreef, A. A., Azzam, I. A., and Darabseh, F. (2019) 'Stakeholder approach and the impact of brand image within higher education in the Middle East: Student and staff perspective', *Journal of Public Affairs*, e1941.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., and Anderson, R. E. (2010) *Multivariate data analysis: a global perspective* 7th edn, Prentice-Hall, London.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., and Ringle, C. (2016) *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLSSEM)*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.

- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., and Ringle, C. M. (2012) 'An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modelling in marketing research', *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 40(3), pp. 414-433.
- Hair, J. F., Anderson, R. E., Babin, B. J., and Black, W. C. (2013) *Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective*. Upper Saddle River, Pearson.
- Hair, J. F., Anderson, R. L., and Tatham, W. C. (1998) *Black Multivariate Data Analysis (5th ed.)*, Prentice-Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Hancock, C. (2015) 'Using images and deep emotions in marketing strategy in Higher Education', *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 22(1), pp. 53-70.
- Harris, R.O. (2020) 'Transnational Education in Sub Sahara Africa: Strategic Partnerships', *Journal of Higher Education theory and Practice*, 20(2), pp. 111-121.
- Harvey, I. S. and Alston, R. J. (2011) 'Understanding Preventive Behaviours Among Midwestern African American Men: A Pilot Qualitative Study of Prostate Screening', *Journal of Men's Health*, 8(2), pp. 140-151.
- Hazelkorn, E. (2011) *Rankings and the Reshaping of Higher Education: The Battle for World-Class Excellence*. New York: Palgrave-Macmillan.
- Hazelkorn, E. (2018) 'Reshaping the world order of higher education: The role and impact of rankings on national and global systems', *Policy Reviews in Higher Education*, 2(1), pp. 4-31.
- He, Y. and Hutson, B. (2018) 'Exploring and leveraging Chinese international students' strengths for success', *Journal of International Students*, 8(1), pp. 87-108.
- He, X. and Wei, Y. (2011) 'Linking market orientation to international market selection and international performance', *International Business Review*, 20(5), pp. 535-546.
- He, X., Brouters, K. D. and Filatotchev, I. (2018) 'Market orientation and export performance: The moderation of channel and institutional distance', *International Marketing Review*, 35(2), pp. 258-279.
- Healey, M. N. (2015) 'Towards a risk-based typology for transnational education', *Higher education*, 69, pp. 1-18.
- Healey, N. (2018) 'The challenges of managing transnational education partnerships: The views of "home-based" managers vs "in-country" managers', *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(2), pp. 241-256.
- Healey, N. and Michael, L. (2015) 'Towards a New Framework for Analysing Transnational Education', *Higher Education Policy*, 28(3), pp. 369-391. Accessed June, 2019 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057%2Fhpep.2014.17>

- Healey, N. M. (2020) 'The end of transnational education? The view from the UK, Perspectives', *Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 24(3), pp. 102-112,
- Healey, M., Flint, A. and Harrington, K. (2014) *Engagement Through Partnership: Students as Partners in Learning and Teaching in Higher Education*. New York, NY: Higher Education Academy.
- Healey, N. (2008) 'Is Higher Education in Really Internationalising?', *Higher Education*, 55(3), pp. 333-355.
- Healey, N. (2013) 'Is UK Transnational Education 'One of Britain's Great Growth Industries of the Future'?', *Higher Education Review*, 45(3), pp. 6-35.
- Hemsley-Brown, J. and Oplatka, I. (2015a) *Higher education consumer choice*, Springer.
- Hemsley-Brown, J. and Oplatka, I. (2015b) 'University choice: what do we know, what don't we know and what do we still need to find out?', *International Journal of Educational Management*, 29(3), pp. 254-274.
- Henderson, M., Barnett, R., and Barrett, H. (2017) 'New developments in transnational education and the challenges for higher education professional staff', *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 21(1), pp. 11-19.
- Hill, A. D., Kern, D. A., and White, M. A. (2014) 'Are we overconfident in executive overconfidence research? An examination of the convergent and content validity of extant unobtrusive measures', *Journal of Business Research*, 67(7), pp. 1414-1420.
- Hou, J., Montgomery, C., and McDowell, L. (2014) 'Exploring the diverse motivations of transnational higher education in China: Complexities and contradictions', *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 40(3), pp. 300-318.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2014.903028>
- Hoyt, J. and Howell, S. (2012) 'Why students choose the branch campus of a large university', *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 60(2), pp. 110-116.
- Hu, L. and Bentler, P. M. (1999) 'Cut off criteria for fit indices in covariance structure analysis: conventional criteria versus new alternatives', *Structural Equation Modeling*, 1(1), pp. 1-55.
- Hu, M. and Willis, L. D. (2017) 'Towards a Common Transnational Education Framework: Peculiarities in China Matter', *Higher Education Policy*, 30, pp. 245-261.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41307-016-0021-9>
- Hult, G. T. M. and Ketchen, J. D. J. (2017) 'Disruptive marketing strategy', *AMS Review*, 7(1-2), pp. 20-25.

- International Consultants for Education and Fairs (ICEF) (2018) 'Australia's International Education Exports Grew by 22% in 2017', *ICEF*. Accessed March, 2020 <https://monitor.icef.com/2018/04/australias-international-education-exportsgrew-22-2017/>.
- İpek, I. (2019) 'Organizational learning in exporting: A bibliometric analysis and critical review of the empirical research', *International Business Review*, 28(3), pp. 544-559.
- İpek, I. and Bicakcioglu-Peynirci, N. (2020) 'Export market orientation: An integrative review and directions for future research', *International Business Review*, 29(1), pp. 11-19.
- James, M. and Derrick, G. (2021) 'Export marketing in higher education: an international comparison', *Journal of International Education in Business*, 14(1), pp. 59-76.
- Javanmard, H. and Hasani, H. (2017) 'The impact of market-orientation indices, marketing innovation, and competitive advantages on the business performance in distributor enterprises', *International Journal of Industrial Distribution and Business*, 8, pp. 23-31.
- Jaworski, B. J. and Kohli, A. K. (1993) 'Market Orientation: Antecedents and Consequences', *Journal of Marketing*, 57(3), pp. 53-70
- Jaworski, B. J. and Kohli, A. K. (2017) 'Conducting field-based, discovery-oriented research: Lessons from our market-orientation research experience', *AMS Review*, 7(1-2), pp. 4-12.
- Jerez-Jerez, M. J., Melewar, T. C., and Foroudi, P. (2021) 'Exploring waiters' occupational identity and turnover intention: a qualitative study focusing on Michelin-starred restaurants in London', *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 47(1), pp. 22-34
- Jimenez-Castillo, D., Sanchez-Fernandez, R., and Iniesta-Bonillo, M. A. (2013) 'Segmenting university graduates on the basis of perceived value, image and identification', *International Review Public Non-profit Market*, 10, pp. 235-252.
- Jones, S. (2014) 'Gendered discourses of entrepreneurship in UK higher education: the fictive entrepreneur and the fictive student', *International Small Business Journal*, 32, pp. 237-258.
- Jones, S., Lefoe, G., Harvey, M., and Ryland, K. (2012) 'Distributed leadership: a collaborative framework for academics, executives and professionals in higher education', *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 34(1), pp. 67-78.
- Joreskog, K. G. and Sorbom, D. (1982) 'Recent developments in structural equation modeling', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 19(4), pp. 404-416.

- Jules, T. D. (2015) 'Educational exceptionalism in small (and micro) states: cooperative educational transfer and the case of TVET', *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 10(2), pp. 202-222.
- Jules, T. D. (2018) 'Educational regime complexity: nested governance and multi-stakeholderism in the fourth industrial revolution', in A. W. Wiseman (Ed.), *Annual Review of Comparative and International Education 2017*. Bingley, UK: Emerald Publishing, pp. 139-158.
- Kantola, M. and Kettunen, J. (2012) 'Integration of education with research and development and the export of higher education', *On the Horizon*. 20(1), pp. 7-16.
- Kaplan, R. S. (2001) 'Strategic performance measurement and management in non-profit organizations', *Non-profit Management Leadership*, 11(3), pp. 353-370.
- Kayabasi, A., Kayabasi, A., Mtetwa, T., and Mtetwa, T. (2016) 'Impact of marketing effectiveness and capabilities, and export market orientation on export performance: Evidence from Turkey', *European Business Review*, 28(5), pp. 532-559.
- Keay, J., May, H. and O'Mahony, J. (2014) 'Improving learning and teaching in transnational education: can communities of practice help?', *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 40(3), pp. 251-266.
- Kenny, D. A. (1979) *Correlation and causation*, John Wiley, NY.
- Khanna, G. (2021) 'How Higher Education Became an Important US Export', *Issues in Science and Technology*, 38(1), pp. 30-33.
- Khuwaja, F. M., Shaari, H. B., and Bakar, L. J. A. (2017) 'Market orientation: An important consideration for higher education of Pakistan', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7, pp. 419-436.
- Kleibert, J. M. (2023) 'Brexit geographies of transnational education: uncertainty, "global Britain" and European (re-)integration', *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 11(1), pp. 190-211, DOI: 10.1080/21622671.2020.1837222
- Knight, J. and John M. (2017) *Transnational Education: A Classification Framework and Data Collection Guidelines for International Programme and Provider Mobility (Ippm)* The British Council.
- Knight, J. (2016) 'Transnational education remodelled: toward a common TNE framework and definitions', *Journal of Studies in International Education*. 20(1), pp. 34-47.
- Kohli, A. K. (2017) 'Market-orientation in a digital world', *Global Business Review*, 18(Suppl. 3), S203-S205.

- Kohli, A. K., Jaworski, B. J., and Kumar, A. (1993) 'A Measure of Market Orientation', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 30(4), pp. 467-477
- Kohli, A. K. and Jaworski, B. J. (1990) 'Market orientation: The construct, research propositions, and managerial implications', *Journal of Marketing*, 54, pp. 1-18
- Koris, R., Örténblad, A., Kerem, K., and Ojala, T. (2015) 'Student–customer orientation at a higher education institution: The perspective of undergraduate business students', *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 25(1), pp. 29-44.
- Koris, R., and Nokelainen, P. (2015) 'The student-customer orientation questionnaire, application of customer metaphor to higher education', *International Journal Of Education Management*, 29(10), pp. 115-138.
- Krücken, G. (2021) 'Multiple competitions in higher education: a conceptual approach', *Innovation*, 23(2), pp. 163-181.
- Kumar, R. (2019) *Research methodology: A step-by-step guide for beginners*. Sage Publications Limited.
- Kumar, V., Jones, E., Venkatesan, R., and Leone, R. P. (2011) 'Is Market Orientation a Source of Sustainable Competitive Advantage or Simply the Cost of Competing?', *Journal of Marketing*, 75(1), pp. 16-30.
- Kwiek, M. and Maassen, P. (2012) *National Higher Education Reforms in a European Context: Comparative Reflections on Poland and Norway*. Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang.
- Larsen, M. A. (2016) *Transnational Programmes and Providers: Mobilities and Complex Spatial Flows*. In *Internationalization of Higher Education: An Analysis through Spatial, Network, and Mobilities Theories*, edited by M. A. Larsen, pp. 123-150. New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Levine, T., Hullett, C. R., Turner, M. M., and Lapinski, M. K. (2006) 'The Desirability of Using Confirmatory Factor Analysis on Published Scales', *Communication Research Reports*, 23(4), pp. 309-314.
- Lien, D. and Keithley, A. (2020), 'The determinants of international branch campuses', *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(2), pp. 452-463. Accessed April, 2011 <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2018.1539961>
- Lin, K. H., Huang, K. F., and Peng, Y. P. (2014) 'Impact of export market orientation on export performance: A relational perspective', *Baltic Journal of Management*, 9(4), pp. 403-425.
- Lozano, J. M., Bofarull, I., Waddock, S., and Prat-i-Pubill, Q. (2018) 'Avoiding the iron cage of business school rankings', *Higher Education Policy*, 6(11), pp. 1-23.

- Lund, T. (2012) 'Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches: Some Arguments for Mixed Methods Research', *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 56(2), pp. 155-165.
- Mac, L. F. and Evangelist, F. (2016) 'Evangelista the relative impact of market orientation and entrepreneurship on export performance: do we really know enough?', *Journal of Global Marketing*, 29(5), pp. 266-281.
- MacLean, S. and Gray, K. (1998) 'Structural equation modelling in market research', *Journal of the Australian Market Research Society*, 6, pp. 17-32.
- Maisuria, A. and Cole, M. (2017) 'The neo liberalization of higher education in England: An alternative is possible', *Policy Futures in Education*, 1(5), pp. 602-619.
- Makri, K., Theodosiou, M., and Katsikea, E. (2017) 'An empirical investigation of the antecedents and performance outcomes of export innovativeness', *International Business Review*, 26(4), pp. 628-639.
- Malhotra, N. and Birks, D. (2000) *Marketing Research: An Applied Approach*, Prentice-Hall, London.
- Malhotra, N., Nunan, D., and Birks, D. (2017) *Marketing Research: An Applied Approach*. (5th ed.) Pearson.
- Marginson, S. (2013) 'The Impossibility of Capitalist Markets in Higher Education', *Journal of Education Policy*, 28(3), pp. 1-18.
- Marginson, S. (2016) 'The worldwide trend to high participation higher education: Dynamics of social stratification in inclusive systems', *Higher Education*, 72(4), pp. 413-434.
- Mark, E. (2013) 'Student satisfaction and the customer focus in higher education', *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 35(1), pp. 2-10.
- Martínez-López, F.J., Gázquez-Abad, J.C. and Sousa, C.M.P. (2013) 'Structural equation modelling in marketing and business research: Critical issues and practical recommendations', *European Journal of Marketing*, 47(1/2), pp. 115-152.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012) *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach*, SAGE Publication, Incorporated.
- Melewar, T. C., Foroudi, P., Dinnie, K., and Nguyen, B. (2018) 'The role of corporate identity management in the higher education sector: an exploratory case study', *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 24(4), 337-359.

- Menendez, A. H. D. and Castilla, R. (2021) 'The marketisation of Higher Education through the English university model: key elements, criticisms, and possibilities', *Revista Española de Educación Comparada*, 37, pp. 234-255.
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., and Saldaña, J. (2013) *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated.
- Mingers, J., Mutch, A. and Willcocks, L. (2013) 'Critical Realism in Information Systems Research', *Management Information Systems Research Centre*, 37(3), pp. 795-802.
- Miotto, G., Del-Castillo-Feito, C., and Blanco-Gonzalez, A. (2020) 'Reputation and legitimacy: Key factors for Higher Education Institutions' sustained competitive advantage', *Journal of Business Research*, 112, pp. 342-353.
- Molesworth, M., Scullion, R., and Nixon, E. (2011) *The marketization of higher education and the student as consumer*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Morgan, T., Anokhin, S., Kretinin, A., and Frishammar, J. (2015) 'The dark side of the entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation interplay: A new product development perspective', *International Small Business Journal*, 33(7), pp. 731-751
- Murray, J. Y., Gao, G. Y., and Kotabe, M. (2011) 'Market orientation and performance of export ventures: The process through marketing capabilities and competitive advantages', *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 39(2), pp. 252-269.
- Murray, J. Y., Gao, G. Y., Kotabe, M., and Zhou, N. (2007) 'Assessing measurement invariance of export market orientation: a study of Chinese and non-Chinese firms in China', *Journal of International Marketing*, 15(4), pp. 72-80.
- Musselin, C. (2018) 'New forms of competition in higher education', *Socio-Economic Review*, 16(3), pp. 657-683.
- Naidoo, R. and Williams, J. (2015) 'The neoliberal regime in English higher education: Charters, consumers, and the erosion of the public good', *Critical Studies in Education*, 56(2), pp. 208-223.
- Narver, J. C. and Slater, S. F. (1990) 'The Effect of a Market Orientation on Business Profitability', *Journal of Marketing*, 54(4), pp. 20-35.
- Naylor, R., Dollinger, M., Mahat, M. and Khawaja, M (2021) 'Students as customers versus as active agents: conceptualising the student role in governance and quality assurance', *Higher Education Research and Development*, 40(5), pp. 1026-1039.
- New York Times Editors (2010). Are they students? Or «customers»? The student as cash cow. The New York Times. Accessed June 2019,

<https://archive.nytimes.com/roomfordebate.blogs.nytimes.com/2010/01/03/%20are-they-students-or-customers/#mark>

- Nixon, E., Scullion, R., and Hearn R. (2018) 'Her Majesty the student: Marketised higher education and the narcissistic (dis)satisfactions of the student-consumer', *Studies in Higher Education*, 43(6), pp. 927-943.
- Nixon, E., Scullion, R. and Molesworth, M. (2010) *How choice in higher education can create conservative learners*. In: Molesworth M, Scullion R and Nixon E (eds) *The Marketisation of Higher Education and the Student as Consumer*. London: Routledge, pp. 196–208.
- Novick, M. R. and Lewis, C. (1967) 'Coefficient alpha and the reliability of composite measurement', *Psychometrika*, 32, pp. 1-13.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978) *Psychometric theory*, McGraw-Hill, NY.
- Olssen, M. (2016) 'Neoliberal competition in higher education today: Research, accountability, and impact', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 37(1), pp. 129-148.
- Ones, P., Maas, G., Kraus, S., and Lloyd-Reason, L. (2021) 'An exploration of the role and contribution of entrepreneurship centres in UK higher education institutions', *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 43(6), pp. 927-943.
- Palfreyman, D. and Tapper, T. (2016) 'The marketization of English higher education and the financing of tuition fees', *London Review of Education*, 14(1), pp. 47-55.
- Palmer, A. (2011) 'Cooperative marketing associations: an investigation into the causes of effectiveness', *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 10(2), pp. 135-156.
- Pascucci, F., Bartoloni, S., and Gregori, G.L. (2002) 'Market-oriented behaviour: Comparing service with product exporters', *European Journal of Marketing*, 36(9/10), pp. 1076-1102.
- Patton, M. Q. (2014) *Qualitative research and evaluation methods: integrating theory and practice*. SAGE Publication, Incorporated.
- Paul, J. and Sánchez-Morcillo, R. (2019) 'Toward a new model for firm internationalization: Conservative, predictable, and pacemaker companies and markets', *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences / Revue Canadienne Des Sciences de L'Administration*, 36(3), pp. 336-349.
- Peter, J. P. (1979) 'Reliability: A Review of Psychometric Basics and Recent Marketing Practices', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 16(1), pp. 6-17.
- Peter, J. P. and Churchill, G. (1986) 'Relationships among Research Design Choices and Psychometric Properties of Rating Scales: A Meta-analysis', *Journal of Marketing Research*, 33, pp. 1-10.

- Pucciarelli, F. and Kaplan, A. (2016) 'Competition and strategy in higher education: Managing complexity and uncertainty', *Business Horizons*, 59, pp. 311-320.
- Qu, M. K., Li, W. D., Zhang, C. R., Wang, S. Q., Yang, Y., and He, L. Y. (2013) 'Source apportionment of heavy metals in soils using multivariate statistics and geostatistics', *Pedosphere*. 23(4), pp. 437-444.
- Racela, O. C., and A. Thoumrungroje (2014) 'Export Market Orientation, Interfirm Communication, Interfirm Cooperation and Export Performance', *International Journal of Management and Marketing Research*, 7(1), pp. 1-14.
- Raymundo-Delmonte, N. (2023). 'Frameworks and tools in developing marketing strategies for transnational Education (TNE) providers: A literature review'. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(4), pp. 333–346. Accessed January, 2024 [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).32](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).32)
- Rienties, B., Olney, T., Nichols, M., and Herodotou, C. (2019) *Effective usage of Learning Analytics: What do practitioners want and where should distance learning institutions be going?* Open Learning.
- Rinaldi, C., Cavicchi, A., Spigarelli, F., Lacchè, L. and Rubens, A. (2018) 'Universities and smart specialisation strategy: From third mission to sustainable development co-creation', *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 19(1), pp. 67-84. Accessed August, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-04-2016-0070>
- Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., and Elam, G. (2003) *Designing and selecting samples*, In Ritchie, J. and Lewis, J., *Qualitative research practice, A guide for social science students and researchers* (pp. 77-108) Sage Publications, CA.
- Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., and Elam, G. (2013) *Qualitative research practice, A guide for social science students and researchers*. Sage Publications, CA.
- Rossano, S., Meerman, A., Kesting, T., and Baaken, T. (2016) 'The Relevance of Problem-based Learning for Policy Development in University-Business Cooperation', *European Journal of Education*, 51(1), pp. 40-55.
- Rowley, M. and Skipper, Y. (2021) 'Student and staff expectations and experiences of a UK–China Transnational Education collaboration', *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 13(5), pp. 1374-1387.
- Rumbley, L. and Altbach, P. (2015) *The Local and the Global in Higher Education Internationalization: A Crucial Nexus*, In: *Global and Local Internationalization*, edited by E. Jones, R. Coelen, J. Beelen, and H. de Wit, pp. 7-13. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.

- Rutter, R., Lettice, F., and Nadeau, J. (2017) 'Brand personality in higher education: Anthropomorphized university marketing communications', *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 27, pp. 19-39.
- Universities UK (2018). Patterns and Trends in UK higher education 2018. Accessed November, 2023 <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/sites/default/files/field/downloads/2021-08/patterns-and-trends-in-uk-higher-education-2018.pdf>
- Safdar, B., Habib, A., Amjad, A., and Abbas, J. (2020) 'Treating Students as Customers in Higher Education Institutions and its Impact on their Academic Performance', *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 9(4), pp. 176-191.
- Saldana, J. (2013) *The coding manual for qualitative research (2nd ed)*. SAGE Publications: London.
- Sasson, I. (2018) 'Building a sustainable university-community partnership', *Studies in Higher Education*. 44(5), pp. 1-15.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A. (2007) *Research methods for business students*, Prentice Hall, London.
- Shiu, E., Hair, J. J. F., Bush, R. P., and Ortinau, D. J. (2009) *Marketing Research*, McGraw-Hill, London.
- Sidhu, R., and Christie, P. (2014) 'Making Space for an International Branch Campus: Monash University Malaysia', *Asia Pacific Viewpoint*, 55(2), pp. 182-195.
- Silva, G. M., Dias, Á. L., Lisboa, A. C. and Silva, F. P. (2023) 'Drivers and outcomes of sustainable export marketing strategies in international environments', *Review of International Business and Strategy*, ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RIBS-05-2022-0056>
- Silverman, D. (2015) *Interpreting Qualitative Data*. London, UK: Sage.
- Singh, H., and Mahmood, R. (2013) 'Determining the Effect of Export Market Orientation on Export Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Malaysia: An Exploratory Study', *Advances in Management and Applied Economics*, 3(6), pp. 223-232.
- Smithson, J. (2000) 'Using and analysing focus groups: limitations and possibilities', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 3(2), pp. 103-119.
- Spring, J. (2009) *Globalization of Education: An Introduction*. New York: Routledge.
- Steenkamp, J. B. E. M. and Baumgartner, H. (2000) 'On the Use of Structural Equation Models in Marketing Modeling', *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 17, pp. 195-202.

- Steiger, J. H. (1990) 'Structural model evaluation and modification: an interval estimation approach', *Multivariate Behavioural Research*, 25, pp. 173-180.
- Stevens, R. E., Wrenn, B., Ruddick, M. E. and Sherwood, P. K. (1997) *The Marketing Research Guide*, The Haworth Press, New York.
- Sukoco, B. M., Choirunnisa, Z., Mudzakkir, M. F., Nasution, R. A., Susanto, E. and Usman, I. (2021) 'Market orientation and capacity for change in higher education performance in Indonesia', *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, ahead-of-print. Accessed October, 2021 <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-01-20200021>
- Tabachnick, B. G. and Fidell, L. S. (2007) *Using multivariate statistics (7th edition)*, Allyn and Bacon, Boston.
- Teo, T. (2011) 'Using structural equation modeling (SEM) in educational research: practices and issues', *International Journal of Applied Educational Studies*, 10(1), pp. 49+.
- Terho, H., Eggert, A., Haas, A., and Ulaga, W. (2015) 'How sales strategy translates into performance: the role of salesperson customer orientation and value-based selling', *Industrial Marketing Management*, 45(1), pp. 12-21.
- Thatcher, J., Alao, H., Brown, C. J., and Choudhary, S. (2016) 'Enriching the values of micro and small business research projects: co-creation service provision as perceived by academic, business and student', *Studies of Higher Education*, 41(3), pp. 560-581.
- Thoenig, J.-C. and Paradeise, C. (2016) 'Strategic capacity and organizational capabilities: A challenge for universities', *Minerva*, 54(3), pp. 293-324.
- Tienari, J. and Aula, H. (2011) 'Becoming "World-class"? Reputation-Building in a University Merger', *Critical Perspectives on International Business*, 7(1), pp. 7-29.
- Tomlinson M. (2017) 'Students' perceptions of themselves as 'consumers' of higher education', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 38(4), pp. 450-467.
- Tomlinson, M. (2018) 'Conceptions of the value of higher education in a measured market', *Higher Education*, 75(4), pp. 711-727.
- Valentine, S., Nam, S. H., Hollingworth, D. (2014) 'Ethical Context and Ethical Decision Making: Examination of an Alternative Statistical Approach for Identifying Variable Relationships', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 124, pp. 509-526.
- Vangelis, T. and Christopher, H (2021) 'A prospective model for aligning educational quality and student experience in international higher education', *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(2), pp. 228-244.

- Vangelis, T., Ilieva, J., and Hill, C. (2018) *Transnational Education: Global Location, Local Innovation*, Birmingham, UK.
- Vercic, A.T., Vercic, D., and Znidar, K. (2016) 'Exploring academic reputation – is it a multidimensional construct? Corporate Communications', *International Journal*, 21(2), pp. 160-176.
- Vollero, A., Palazzo, M., Siano, A., and Foroudi, P. (2020) 'From CSR to CSI: analysing consumers' hostile responses to branding initiatives in social media-scape', *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 24(2), pp. 143-160.
- Wallace, M., and L. Dunn. (2013) *Teaching in Transnational Higher Education: Enhancing Learning for Offshore International Students*. New York: Taylor and Francis.
- Warwick, P. (2014) 'The international business of higher education – A managerial perspective on the internationalisation of UK universities', *The International Journal of Management Education*, 12(2), pp. 91-103.
- Watkins, B. A., and Gonzenbach, W. J. (2013) 'Assessing University Brand Personality Through Logos: An Analysis of the Use of Academics and Athletics in University Branding', *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 23(1), pp. 15-33.
- Wilkins, S. and Huisman, J. (2012) 'The International Branch Campus as Transnational Strategy in Higher Education', *Higher Education*, 64(5), pp. 627-645.
- Wilkins, S. and Huisman, J. (2021) 'Institution strategy in transnational higher education: late entrants in mature markets – the case of international branch campuses in the United Arab Emirates', *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(4), pp. 704-720.
- Wilkins, S. and Rumbley, L. (2018) 'What A Branch Campus Is: A Revised Definition', *International Higher Education*, 2(93), pp. 12-14.
- Wilkins, S., Balakrishnan, M. S., and Huisman, J. (2012a) 'Student Choice in Higher Education: Motivations for Choosing to Study at an International Branch Campus', *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 16(5), pp. 413-433.
- Wilkins, S., Balakrishnan, M. S., and Huisman. J. (2012b) 'Student Satisfaction and Student Perceptions of Quality at International Branch Campuses in the United Arab Emirates', *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 34(5), pp. 543-56.
- Williams, J. (2012) *Consuming Higher Education: Why Learning Can't Be Bought*. London: Bloomsbury Academic
- Williams, R.L. and Omar, M. (2014) 'How branding process activities impact brand equity within higher education institutions', *Journal of Marketing and Higher Education*, 24(1), pp. 1-10.

- Williamson, B. (2021) 'Making markets through digital platforms: Pearson, edu-business, and tI(e)valuation of higher education', *Critical Studies in Education*, 62(1), pp. 50-66.
- Wilson, K. L., Murphy, K. A., Pearson, A. G., Wallace, B. M., Reher, V. G., and Buys, N. (2016) 'Understanding the early transition needs of diverse commencing university students in a health faculty: Informing effective intervention practices', *Studies in Higher Education*, 41(6), pp. 1023-1040.
- Woodall, T., Hiller, A. and Resnick, S. (2014) 'Making Sense of Higher Education: Students as Consumers and the Value of the University Experience', *Studies in Higher Education*, 39(1), pp. 48-67.
- Wright S. and Shore C. (2017) *Death of the Public University? Uncertain Futures for Higher Education in the Knowledge Economy*. New York; Oxford: Berghahn Books.
- Yayla, S., Yenyurt, S., Uslay, C., and Cavusgil, E. (2018) 'The role of market orientation, relational capital, and internationalization speed in foreign market exit and re-entry decisions under turbulent conditions', *International Business Review*, 27(6), pp. 1105-1115.
- Yencken, E., Croucher G., Elliott K., and Locke W. (2021) 'Transnational education provision in a time of disruption', *International Journal of Chinese Education*, September—December. pp. 1-16.
- Yu, Q., Asaad, Y., Yen, D. A., and Gupta, S. (2018) 'IMO and internal branding outcomes: an employee perspective in UK HE', *Studies in Higher Education*, 43(1), pp. 37-56.
- Yu, Q., Foroudi, P., and Gupta, S. (2019) 'Far apart yet close by: Social media and acculturation among international students in the UK', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 145(Aug), 493-502.
- Yu, Q., Yen, D. A., Barnes, B. R., and Huang, Y. A. (2017) 'Enhancing firm performance through internal market-orientation and employee organizational commitment', *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30, pp. 964-987.
- Yudkevich, M., Altbach, P. G., and Rumbley, L. (2016) *International Faculty in Higher Education, Comparative Perspectives on Recruitment, Integration, and Impact*. New York: Routledge.
- Zebal, M. and Goodwin, D. (2012) 'Market Orientation and Performance in Private Universities', *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, 30(3), pp. 339-357.
- Zepke, N. (2015) 'What future for student engagement in neo-liberal times?', *Higher Education*, 69(4), pp. 693-704.
- Zhang, M., Dawson, J., and Kline, R. B. (2020) 'Evaluating the Use of Covariance-based Structural Equation Modelling with Reflective Measurement in Organisational and Management

Research: A Review and Recommendations for Best Practice', *British Journal of Management*, 32(2), pp. 257-272.

Zhou, Y. and Wu, J. (2016) 'The Game Plan: Four Contradictions in the Development of World Class Universities from the Global South', *Education and Science*, 41(184).

APPENDIX 4.1:

Interview Protocol

Introduction: Hello, my name is Mehdi Benazzouz.

Aim of the research: The aim of this research is to develop a model to conceptualise and interpret engagement in TNE market orientation, elucidating the reason behind a successful TNE business.

Your perspective on these matters is crucial for me to gain insight into the UK TNE market orientation of UK HE establishments. This study aims to explore how UK universities perceive and manage market orientation in their TNE operations.

I assure you of complete confidentiality regarding everything discussed during this interview. It would greatly assist our research if you could grant consent to record our discussion. However, if there's any point at which you feel uncomfortable with recording, I will pause the recorder immediately. Additionally, if there are any topics you're hesitant to discuss, feel free to move on to other issues or subjects. Your comfort and participation are my top priorities.

About the interviewee

Title:

...

Interviewee:

...

Position:

...

Personal

responsibility: ...

How long

have you been ...

with the

university?

Date:

Research Question 1 (Introductory question): How do universities in the UK perceive and practice the Transnational Education activities?	
<u>Transnational education</u>	
Definition: Transnational education is a means that enables learners to acquire foreign education and degrees in a country different to where the awarding university is based, then there will be no need to move abroad; it consists of distance education, collaborative ventures, franchised programmes, and international branch campuses (Stephen, 2011; Wenhong and Shen, 2014; Wilkins and Huisman, 2012).	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which type of TNE is delivered by your university? - What do you think about your university practice regarding TNE activities, such as distance or online learning, branch campuses, or collaborative provision? - How do you manage TNE in your university?
Research Question 2 (Main questions): What are the elements that shape Transnational Education Market Orientation in the UK?	
<u>Transnational Education Market Orientation</u>	
Definition: TNE market orientation is a type of higher education exports where marketing managers must value current and future needs of international students, then fulfil those needs (Asaad et al., 2013; Cadogan et al., 2009; James and Derrick, 2021; Yu et al., 2018).	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Would you please share with us your opinion on the following definition of Transnational Education Market Orientation in the UK? To what extent do you agree with this and illustrate why? - To what extent does your university consider Transnational Education Market Orientation? - What are the elements that shape Transnational Education Market Orientation in your university?
<u>TNE market information generation</u>	
Definition: TNE market information generation is the activities conducted by marketing managers to cover the opportunities or threats that would affect their TNE (Asaad et al., 2015; Bovill et al., 2015; Keay et al., 2014; Knight, 2016; Vangelis et al., 2018).	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does your university generate TNE market information? - How do you think your university practice in TNE market information generation is supporting the development of its transnational education?
<u>TNE market information dissemination</u>	

Definition: TNE market information dissemination is the activities conducted by marketing managers to share the collected information on the TNE market (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2015; Henderson et al., 2017; Vangelis et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018).	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does your university disseminate TNE market information? - How do you think your university practice in TNE market information dissemination is supporting the development of its transnational education?
<u>TNE market information responsiveness</u>	
Definition: TNE market information responsiveness is how marketing managers respond to TNE market information that has been generated and disseminated (Asaad et al., 2015; Healey, 2015; Henderson et al., 2017; Vangelis et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018).	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does your university responds to TNE market information? - How do you think your university practice in TNE market information responsiveness is supporting the development of its transnational education?
Research Question 3 (Main question): What are the key factors that influence Transnational Education Market Orientation in the UK?	
<u>Transnational education coordination</u>	
Definition: TNE coordination is the good work environment between managers of different departments of university on TNE matters (Asaad et al., 2015; Diamantopoulos et al., 2014; Healey, 2015; Healy, 2020 Feng et al., 2013).	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent are your university's departments coordinating with each other? - How does your university coordinate with transnational education partners?
<u>University international ranking position</u>	
Definition: University international ranking position is an assessment of the higher education quality and performance of a university internationally (Brown and Carasso, 2013; Ghobehei et al., 2019; Pucciarelli and Kaplan, 2016; Rutter et al., 2017).	
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How would you classify your university's international ranking position? - What are the elements involved in classifying your university?
<u>Developed country higher education image perception</u>	
Definition: Developed country higher education image perception is how stakeholders of a university in a developed country see and evaluate the image of their higher education (Asaad et al., 2015; Foroudi et al., 2019; Hailat et al., 2019).	

Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do you perceive the UK higher education image? - From your experience, what constitutes UK higher education image? 	
1- Transnational education coordination and components of transnational education market orientation		
Hypotheses	Evidence from literature	Questions answered by managers of international office in UK universities
<p>H1a: If transnational education is well-coordinated, the generation of transnational education market information by the university will be enhanced.</p>	<p>Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (2012); Healey (2020); He and Hutson (2018); He et al. (2018); Larsen (2016); Racela and Thoumrungroje (2014); Rumbley and Altbach (2015)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does TNE coordination affect the transnational education market information that your university generates? - How is your university's TNE coordination related to TNE market information generation?
<p>H1b: If transnational education is well-coordinated, the dissemination of transnational education market information by the university will be enhanced.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does TNE coordination affect the dissemination of TNE market information? - How is your university's transnational education coordination related to TNE market information dissemination?
<p>H1c: If transnational education is well-coordinated, the responsiveness to transnational education market information by the university will be enhanced.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does TNE coordination affect the responsiveness of TNE market information? - How is your university's transnational education coordination related to TNE market information responsiveness?
2- University international ranking position and components of transnational education market orientation		
Hypotheses	Evidence from literature	Questions answered by managers of international office in UK universities

<p>H2a: If a university's international position is top-ranked, the generation of transnational education market information in the university will be enhanced.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does your university's international ranking position affect the transnational education market information the university generates? - How is your university's international ranking position related to the generation of transnational education market information?
<p>H2b: If a university's international position is top-ranked, the dissemination of transnational education market information in the university will be enhanced.</p>	<p>Asaad et al. (2013); Bastedo and Bowman (2010); Brankovic et al. (2018); Bobe and Kober (2015); Cadogan et al. (2012); Hazelkorn (2018); Ghobehei et al. (2019); Pucciarelli and Kaplan (2016)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does your university's international ranking position affect the dissemination of transnational education market information? - How is your university's international ranking position related to the transnational education market dissemination?
<p>H2c: If a university's international position is top-ranked, the responsiveness to transnational education market information in the university will be enhanced.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does your university's international ranking position affect the responsiveness of the transnational education market? - How is your university's international ranking position related to the responsiveness of transnational education market information?
<p>3- Developed country higher education image perception and component of transnational education market orientation</p>		
<p>Hypotheses</p>	<p>Evidence from literature</p>	<p>Questions answered by managers of international office in UK universities</p>
<p>H3a: If the perceived developed country higher education image is positively perceived by managers, the generation of transnational education market information by the university will be enhanced.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How is the perceived UK higher education image related to the generation of transnational education market information at your university?

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does the perceived UK higher education image by marketing managers affect the transnational education market information your university generates?
H3b: If the perceived developed country higher education image is positively perceived by managers, the dissemination of transnational education market information by the university will be enhanced.	<p>Amaia et al. (2018); Assad et al. (2015); Baker and Ballington (2011); Ghobehei et al. (2019); Hemsley-Brown et al. (2016); Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); Zhou and Wu (2016)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How is the perceived UK higher education image related to transnational education market dissemination in your university? - To what extent does the perceived UK higher education image by marketing managers affect transnational education market information dissemination in your university?
H3c: If the perceived developed country higher education image is positively perceived by managers, the responsiveness to transnational education market information by the university will be enhanced.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How is the perceived UK higher education image related to the responsiveness of the transnational education market in your university? - To what extent does the perceived UK higher education image by marketing managers affect the responsiveness of transnational education market information in your university?
4- University international ranking position and developed country higher education image perception		
Hypotheses	Evidence from literature	Questions answered by managers of international office in UK universities
H4: If the university's international position is highly ranked, the perceived higher education image of the developed country will be enhanced.	Amaia et al., 2018; Baker and Ballington, 2011; Hazelkorn, 2018; Ghobehei et al., 2019	- How is your university international ranking position related to the perceived UK higher education image?

		- To what extent does your university international ranking position affect the perceived UK higher education image?
Research Question 4 (Main question): What are the consequences/benefits of Transnational Education market orientation according to UK universities?		
<u>Higher education international reputation</u>		
Definition: Higher education international reputation is the international prestige, deference, and honour reflected by stakeholders of higher education internationally due to its previous experience (Davey, 2015; Maisuria and Cole, 2017; Menendez and Castilla, 2021; Priporas and Kamenidou, 2011; Thatcher et al., 2016).		
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From your experience, how would you define and categorise the UK higher education international reputation? - From your experience at your university, what constitutes the international reputation of the UK higher education? 	
<u>Transnational education business performance</u>		
Definition: TNE business performance is the positive outcome of managers' activities in TNE, reflecting their efficiency to satisfy and achieve the set plans for TNE business growth (Hailat et al., 2019; Healey, 2013; Assad et al., 2015; Murray et al., 2011).		
Question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From your experience, how would you define and categorise TNE business performance? - From your experience at your university, do you think that UK TNE business performance can be achieved through transnational education market orientation? 	
5- Components of transnational education market orientation and transnational education business performance		
Hypotheses	Evidence from literature	Questions answered by managers of international office in UK universities
H5a: If TNE market information generation is enhanced, the UK transnational education business sustainability will be guaranteed.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does TNE market information generation affect the transnational education business performance in your university? - How is TNE market information generation related to the transnational education business performance in your university?

<p>H5b: If dissemination of TNE market information is enhanced, the UK transnational education business sustainability will be guaranteed.</p>	<p>Asaad et al. (2015); Cadogan et al. (2012); Espeland and Sauder (2016); Thatcher et al. (2016); Yu et al. (2018); Watkins and Gonzenbach (2013); Wilkins and Huisman (2015); Wilkins et al. (2012)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does dissemination of TNE market information affect the transnational education business performance in your university? - How is dissemination of TNE market information related to the transnational education business performance in your university?
<p>H5c: If responsiveness to TNE market information is enhanced, the UK transnational education business sustainability will be guaranteed.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what does extent responsiveness to TNE market information affect the transnational education business performance in your university? - How is responsiveness to TNE market information related to the transnational education business performance in your university?
<p>6- Components of transnational education market orientation and higher education international reputation</p>		
<p>Hypotheses</p>	<p>Evidence from literature</p>	<p>Questions answered by managers of international office in UK universities</p>
<p>H6a: If TNE market information generation is enhanced, the UK higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what extent does TNE market information generation affect the higher education international reputation in your university? - How is TNE market information generation related to the higher education international reputation in your university?
<p>H6b: If dissemination of TNE market information is enhanced, the UK higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To what does extent dissemination of TNE market information affect the higher education international reputation in your university?

	Ahimbisibwe et al. (2013); Chung (2012); Hailat et al. (2019); He and Wei (2011); Palfreyman and Tapper (2016); Racela and Thoumrungroje (2014); Mac and	- How is dissemination of TNE market information related to the higher education international reputation in your university?
H6c: If responsiveness to TNE market information is enhanced, the UK higher education international reputation will be guaranteed.	Evangelist (2016); Murray et al. (2007); Terho et al. (2015); Warwick (2014)	- To what extent does responsiveness to TNE market information affect the higher education international reputation in your university? - How is responsiveness to TNE market information related to the higher education international reputation in your university?
7- UK higher education international reputation and UK transnational education business performance		
Hypotheses	Evidence from literature	Questions answered by managers of international office in UK universities
H7: If UK higher education international reputation is guaranteed, the UK transnational education business sustainability will be guaranteed as well.	Cadogan et al. (2016); Guilbault (2018); Molesworth et al. (2011); Vangelis et al. (2018)	- How is higher education international reputation related to the transnational education business performance in your university? - To what extent does higher education international reputation affect the transnational education business performance in your university?

APPENDIX 4.2:

Focus Group Protocol

Group No:

Description of participants:

1
2
3
4
5
6

Place:

Date:

Length of session:

Moderator:

Questions

Introductory questions

- 1- Which type of TNE is delivered by your university? (Ask all participants)
- 2- What do you think about the university practice regarding the TNE activities, such as distance or online learning, branch campuses, or collaborative provision?
- 3- How can TNE be managed in universities?

Transition questions

- 1- How do you see transnational education market orientation in the UK?
- 2- To what extent do UK universities consider transnational education market orientation?
- 3- What are the elements that shape transnational education market orientation in universities?

Main questions

- 1- How universities generate TNE market information?
- 2- How do you think that universities' practice in TNE market information generation is supporting the development of transnational education?
- 3- How do universities disseminate TNE market information?
- 4- How do you think that universities' practice in TNE market information dissemination is supporting the development of transnational education?
- 5- How do universities respond to TNE market information?
- 6- How do you think that universities' practice in TNE market information responsiveness is supporting the development of its transnational education?
- 7- How should university's departments coordinate with each other?
- 8- How should universities coordinate with transnational education partners?
- 9- How would you classify UK universities' international ranking position?
- 10- What are the elements involved in classifying a university?
- 11- How do you perceive the UK higher education image?
- 12- What constitutes the UK higher education image?

Final questions

- 1- How can you define and categorise the UK higher education international reputation?
- 2- What constitutes the international reputation of the UK higher education?
- 3- How can you define and categorise TNE business performance?
- 4- Can the UK TNE business performance be achieved through transnational education market orientation?

APPENDIX 4.3:

Questionnaire –

Examining the Influence of Transnational Education Market Orientation in UK Universities: TNE's managers perception

Research Objective

The core theme of this research is the TNE market orientation in UK universities, exploring the role of marketing within UK universities in their TNE operations worldwide. This study specifically examines the traditional mode of TNE with partners and the provision of UK higher education to international students abroad through TNE.

The fundamental objective is to identify how UK universities can sustain their international market expansion and achieve successful TNE business performance globally.

Confidentiality

All information you contribute to this research will be kept strictly confidential:

- Any respondents or universities participating in this study will be anonymous.
- Any data generated in this study will be used only for statistical purposes and presented in aggregated form. All names will be undisclosed.

Your case is valid

The current research aims to involve the participation of all UK universities. This investigation pursues to include managers in the international office or TNE departments.

Your support is vital

The success of the research depends entirely on the data contributed to this investigation by individuals like yourself who are in charge of the international office and TNE within universities in the UK.

Examining the Influence of Transnational Education Market Orientation in UK Universities: A TNE manager perspective

HOW TO FILL IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Please select the option that best represents your opinion. In cases which none of them is applicable to you, simply select the “Not Applicable” option. However, there are no right or wrong answers to this questionnaire. It is more important to obtain your opinion on the specific aspects of transnational education market orientation in your university.
2. This questionnaire is structured so that its completion will be easy and quick. It will take approximately 15 minutes to complete.

Section 1 – Characteristics of Your University

1a. Where is the headquarters of your university based? (Please select ONE box only)

- England
- Wales
- Scotland & Northern Ireland

1b. The following categories represent the different transnational education programmes. From the below programmes, what is/are the programme(s) that your university delivers? (Please select all the programmes that apply)

- Distance/online learning with local support
- Distance/online learning with no local support
- Distance/online learning blended
- Double dual or multiple degree partnership
- Franchised programme partnership
- Joint degree partnership
- Top-up programme partnership
- Validation or quality assurance programme
- Branch campus
- Flying faculty or outreach
- Study centre
- Other

1c. In the 2019-2020 academic year, to how many countries did your university deliver transnational education programmes (including any transnational education programme)?

1d. In which continent are your most transnational education partners situated?

- Europe
- Asia
- Africa
- North America
- South America

Section 2 – Transnational education market orientation

To what extent do you disagree or agree with the following statements for the 2019-2020 academic year based on scores from -1- to -7-? (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neither agree nor disagree, and 7 = very strongly agree).

Transnational education market information generation

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Your university conducts regular surveys to evaluate international students' attitude about the quality of your transnational education.	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
Your continuous contact with international students aims to quickly spot issues related to transnational education programmes.	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
Your university receives a lot of market information regarding transnational education trends (e.g., economic, technology).	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Your relationships with different higher education organisations fulfil your needs for transnational education market information.

You monitor the diverse needs of international students via participating in international fairs worldwide.

Your university keeps up to date about your competitors' transnational education activities in markets where you operate.

Your international office conducts secondary studies about transnational education market trends (e.g., economic, political) in attractive markets.

Your university evaluates the interest of international students concerning the transnational education programmes trends.

You regularly study the effect of possible changes (e.g., regulation, technology) on transnational education in markets where you operate.

Transnational education market information dissemination

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Your university holds regular meetings between heads of its different departments to discuss transnational education issues.

You disseminate information between personnel on transnational education markets using the university portal.

The information you receive from international students about transnational education programmes is transferred to other departments to act.

Your international office's good communication to your transnational education's partners makes you more familiar with transnational education markets where you operate.

Your personnel exchange information daily about the university activities in transnational education markets (e.g., new partners or programmes).

Regular reports are raised to the deans/heads of your schools/faculties summarising information related to transnational education activities.

Your transnational education competitors' activities are discussed frequently between the heads of different departments in your university.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Your international office advises faculties/schools about international students' needs before designing new transnational education programmes or courses.

Transnational education market information responsiveness

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Your university develops transnational education programmes and courses based on international students' market trends.

Your university highly supports transnational education students (e.g., giving access to e-library and Turnitin, orientating students for UK academic skills).

Your university supplies understandable, clear, and accurate information to transnational education students.

Your university takes the initiative to solve matters related to your transnational education students' satisfaction.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Your university interventions towards changes in fee structure of your transnational education competitors is not quick.	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
Your university adapts very quickly to important changes related to your transnational education's environment (e.g., economic, political).	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
Your university responds to threats of transnational education competitors very quickly.	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
Your university transnational education programmes are motivated by internal interests rather than market needs.	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
All your university departments contribute to develop marketing strategy to increase transnational education students' enrolment.	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
Your transnational education programmes' quality is reviewed periodically to control international students' satisfaction.	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>

Section 3 – Elements of transnational education market orientation

3a. Transnational education coordination:

Please define to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements based on the scores from -1- to -7-? (1 = Very Strongly Disagree, 4 = Neither Disagree or Agree, and 7 = Very Strongly Agree)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Your university's departments work collectively as a team to achieve your transnational education objectives.

Your international office department receives support in transnational education activities from several key players in the university.

Your international office personnel share transnational education information with departments in your faculties/schools.

Your university experiences less departmental conflicts.

All your schools/faculties' departments contribute to the international strategy related to transnational education.

The working relationship between the international office's head and other departments' heads, including transnational education's partners, is very strong.

Your university solves conflicts and issues related to transnational education activities via group problem-solving and communication.

3b. University international ranking position:

What was the international ranking position of your university for the 2019-2020 academic year, according to the Times Higher Education guide 2020? (From the following)

- Top 100 Universities
- Between 101-400
- Over 401-700
- Do not know

How does the international ranking position of your university influence your transnational education marketing activities?

- Positively
- Negatively

Please evaluate the following academic quality indicators in your university for 2019-2020 academic year based on scores from 1 to 7? (1 = Extremely very low, 4 = Moderate, and 7 = Extremely very high).

	1	2	3	4	5
Teaching quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Teaching quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Graduation rates	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	1	2	3	4	5
Student/staff ratio	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Entry standards	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Graduation prospects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3c. Developed country higher education image perception:

Please define to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements based on scores from -1- to -7-? (1 = Very Strongly Disagree, 4 = Neither Disagree or Agree, and 7 = Very Agree). In 2019-2020 academic year, how did international office managers in your university perceive the image of UK higher education in terms of the following aspects:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Positive view from employers towards graduates	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Effective student support system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
High course quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Good teaching staff quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Allocating high resource level for research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Well recognised degrees internationally	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increasing rate of employment for graduates	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Section 4 - Higher education international reputation

4. Based on the 2019-2020 academic year, to what extent do you disagree or agree with the following statements referring to the score from '1' to '7'? (1 = Very strongly disagree, 4 = Neither disagree nor agree, and 7 = very strongly agree).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The students of UK transnational education receive education and services as they were promised before enrolment.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
UK higher education international reputation is better than that of other countries.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The reputation of UK higher education is internationally recognised.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

UK higher education offers high standards of education worldwide.

UK higher education has powerful brand names recognised worldwide.

A UK higher education degree is reputable internationally.

UK universities deliver high course quality internationally.

Section 5 – Transnational education business performance

5a. With reference to your university activities with transnational education partners, how do you evaluate the following performance indicators for the 2019-2020 academic year based on scores from -1- to -7-? (1 = extremely very low, 4 = moderate, and 7 = extremely very high).

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

The level of satisfaction between transnational education students.

The enrolment volume of transnational education students.

The percentage of transnational education revenues compared to total revenues of the university.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

The market share of transnational education student enrolment compared to other UK universities.

The number of transnational education students enrolled due to alumni.

The satisfaction of managers with the volume of transnational education student enrolment.

The satisfaction of managers with the university market share based on the enrolment volume of transnational education students.

5c. How do you evaluate the level of managers' attainment of the following targets for the 2019-2020 academic year based on scores from -1- to -7-? (1 = Not met at all, and 7 = Perfectly met)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

The target volume of transnational education student enrolment by managers.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

The target market share of transnational education student enrolment by managers.

Section 6 – Additional enquiries

The following questions are intended to fully understand your opinion on the benefits of transnational education market orientation.

15. In which department do you work?

16. What is your current position?

17. When did you start working for this university?

18. When was this university established?

19. How long has this university been delivering transnational education?

APPENDIX 4.4: Coded items measurements

Constructs	Items wording	Codes of items
TNE market information generation		
	Our university conducts regular surveys to evaluate international students' attitude about the quality of our transnational education.	TMG_1
	Your continuous contact with international students aims to quickly spot issues related to transnational education programmes.	TMG_2
	Your university receives a lot of market information regarding transnational education trends (e.g., economic, technology).	TMG_3
	Your relationships with different higher education organisations fulfil your needs for transnational education market information.	TMG_4
	You monitor the diverse needs of international students via participating in international fairs worldwide.	TMG_5
	Your university keeps up-to-date about the transnational education activities of your competitors in markets where we operate.	TMG_6
	Your international office conducts secondary research about transnational education market trends (e.g., economic, political) in attractive markets.	TMG_7
	Your university evaluates the interest of international students concerning transnational education programmes trends.	TMG_8
	You regularly study the effect of possible changes (e.g., regulation, technology) on transnational education in markets where we operate.	TMG_9
TNE market information dissemination		
	Your university holds regular meetings between heads of its different departments to discuss transnational education issues.	TMD_1
	You disseminate information between personnel on transnational education markets using the university portal.	TMD_2

The information you receive from international students about transnational education programmes is transferred to other departments to act.	TMD_3
Your international office communicates well to your transnational education partners, and makes us more familiar with transnational education markets where we operate.	TMD_4
Your personnel exchange information daily about the university activities in the transnational education market (e.g., new partners or programmes).	TMD_5
Regular reports are raised with the deans/heads of your schools/faculties, summarising information related to transnational education activities.	TMD_6
Your transnational education competitors' activities are discussed frequently between the heads of different departments in your university.	TMD_7
Your international office advises faculties/schools about international students' needs before designing new transnational education programmes or courses.	TMD_8

TNE market orientation responsiveness

Your university develops transnational education programmes and courses based on international students' market trends.	TMR_1
Your university highly supports transnational education students (e.g., gives access to e-library and Turnitin, orientating students for UK academic skills).	TMR_2
Your university supplies understandable, clear, and accurate information to transnational education students.	TMR_3
Your university takes the initiative to solve matters related to your transnational education students' satisfaction.	TMR_4

	Your university interventions towards changes in the fee structure of your transnational education competitors is not quick.	TMR_5
	Your university adapts very quickly to important changes related to your transnational education environment (e.g., economic, political).	TMR_6
	Your university responds to threats of transnational education competitors very quickly.	TMR_7
	Your university transnational education programmes are motivated by internal interests rather than market needs.	TMR_8
	All your university departments contribute to develop marketing strategy for increasing the transnational education students' enrolment.	TMR_9
	Your university neglects some of your transnational education students complains.	TMR_10
	Your transnational education programmes' quality is reviewed periodically to control international students' satisfaction.	TMR_11
TNE coordination		
	Your university's departments work collectively as a team to achieve your transnational education objectives.	TC_1
	Your university's heads are not all contributing to increase transnational education students' enrolment.	TC2
	Your international office department receives support in transnational education activities from several key players in the university.	TC_3
	Your international office personnel share transnational education information with departments in your faculties/schools.	TC_4
	Your university experiences less departmental conflicts.	TC_5
	All your schools/faculties' departments contribute to the international strategy related to the transnational education.	TC_6

	The working relationship between the international office's head and other departments' heads, including transnational education partners, is very strong.	TC_7
	Your university solves conflicts and issues related to transnational education activities via group problem-solving and communication.	TC_8
University international ranking position		
	Teaching quality	UIRP_1
	Research quality	UIRP_2
	Graduation rates	UIRP_3
	Student/staff ratio	UIRP_4
	Entry standards	UIRP_5
	Graduation prospects	UIRP_6
Developed country higher education image perception		
	Positive view from employers towards graduates.	DHIP_1
	Effective student support system.	DHIP_2
	Feasible tuition fees.	DHIP_3
	High course quality.	DHIP_4
	Good teaching staff quality	DHIP_5
	Allocating high resource level for research.	DHIP_6
	Degrees recognised internationally.	DHIP_7
	Increasing rate of employment for graduates.	DHIP_8

Higher education international reputation

The students of UK transnational education receive education and services as they were promised before enrolment.	HIR_1
UK higher education international reputation is better than that of other countries.	HIR_2
The reputation of UK higher education is internationally recognised.	HIR_3
UK higher education offers high standards of education worldwide.	HIR_4
UK higher education has powerful brand names recognised worldwide.	HIR_5
A UK higher education degree is reputable internationally.	HIR_6
UK universities deliver high quality courses internationally.	HIR_7

TNE business performance

The level of satisfaction between TNE's students	TBP_1
The enrolment volume of TNE's students.	TBP_2
The percentage of TNE revenues compared to total revenues of the university.	TBP_3
The market share of transnational education students' enrolment compared to other UK universities.	TBP_4
The number of transnational education students enrolled due to alumni.	TBP_5
The satisfaction of managers with the volume of transnational education students' enrolment.	TBP_6
The satisfaction of managers with the university market share based on the enrolment volume of transnational education students.	TBP_7
The target volume of transnational education student enrolment by managers.	TBP_8
The target market share of transnational education student enrolment by managers.	TBP_9

Source: Developed for the current study by the researcher

APPENDIX 4.5: Reliability measures for constructs (pilot study)

Constructs	Cronbach's alpha	Items	Correlated item – total correlation	Cronbach's alpha of the items deleted	Mean	Std. deviation
TNE market information generation (9)	.963					
		TMG_1	.878	.961	5.71	1.234
		TMG_2	.896	.961	5.51	1.314
		TMG_3	.903	.961	5.35	1.304
		TMG_4	.892	.960	5.59	1.145
		TMG_5	.897	.961	5.35	1.304
		TMG_6	.888	.961	5.49	1.329
		TMG_7	.889	.962	5.35	1.288
		TMG_8	.890	.961	5.71	1.250
		TMG_9	.854	.961	5.51	1.230
TNE market orientation dissemination (8)	.867					
		TMD_1	.674	.845	5.87	.968
		TMD_2	.740	.836	5.85	1.058
		TMD_3	.726	.837	5.79	1.076
		TMD_4	.683	.843	5.93	.987
		TMD_5	.767	.835	5.81	1.011
		TMD_6	.827	.826	5.81	1.070
		TMD_7	.673	.844	5.93	1.008
		TMD_8	.693	.839	5.94	.996
TNE market orientation responsiveness (11)	.884					

Transnational education market orientation elements	TMR_1	.759	.863	5.63	.972	
	TMR_2	.764	.859	5.65	.959	
	TMR_3	.745	.859	5.62	.967	
	TMR_4	.845	.851	5.90	.974	
	TMR_5	.763	.858	5.82	.941	
	TMR_6	.751	.865	5.64	.968	
	TMR_7	.868	.849	5.96	.947	
	TMR_8	.841	.851	5.90	.974	
	TMR_9	.811	.853	5.70	.995	
	TMR_10	.022	.952	5.26	1.712	
	TMR_11	.805	.855	5.88	.940	
	Transnational education coordination (8) .840					
		TC_1	.691	.885	5.22	1.004
		TC_2	.208	.923	4.99	1.598
		TC_3	.659	.797	5.80	.969
		TC_4	.792	.770	5.86	1.010
		TC_5	.771	.774	5.70	1.015
		TC_6	.774	.776	5.56	.972
		TC_7	.746	.775	5.67	1.082
		TC_8	.698	.789	5.11	1.069
	University international ranking position (6) .964					
	UIRP_1	.887	.961	5.63	1.339	
	UIRP_2	.910	.961	5.79	1.299	
	UIRP_3	.939	.960	5.45	1.344	
	UIRP_4	.951	.959	5.73	1.416	
	UIRP_5	.921	.960	5.73	1.387	
	UIRP_6	.961	.959	5.73	1.372	
Developed country higher education image perception .932						

(8)					
	DHIP_1	.850	.895	5.53	1.166
	DHIP_2	.873	.892	5.35	1.240
	DHIP_3	.158	.970	4.63	1.773
	DHIP_4	.874	.893	5.53	1.148
	DHIP_5	.837	.897	5.53	1.075
	DHIP_6	.866	.893	5.35	1.190
	DHIP_7	.869	.894	5.49	1.130
	DHIP_8	.869	.893	5.57	1.164
Higher education international reputation (7)					
	HIR_1	.707	.901	5.37	1.157
	HIR_2	.775	.896	4.69	1.270
	HIR_3	.893	.889	4.77	1.256
	HIR_4	.817	.894	4.89	1.257
	HIR_5	.854	.891	4.71	1.299
	HIR_6	.891	.890	4.85	1.168
	HIR_7	.651	.905	5.11	1.016
Transnational education business performance (9)					
	TBP_1	.756	.920	5.19	1.258
	TBP_2	.755	.920	5.18	1.346
	TBP_3	.829	.916	4.99	1.238
	TBP_4	.875	.911	4.65	1.510
	TBP_5	.756	.921	5.17	1.209
	TBP_6	.829	.914	4.63	1.498
	TBP_7	.841	.914	4.81	1.566
	TBP_8	.754	.919	4.97	1.385
	TBP_9	.774	.919	5.69	1.187

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

APPENDIX 4.6: Factor loadings

Items	Components							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
TMG_1	.696							
TMG_2	.730							
TMG_3	.763							
TMG_4	.768							
TMG_5	.765							
TMG_6	.783							
TMG_7	.781							
TMG_8	.794							
TMG_9	.771							
TMD_1		.774						
TMD_2		.763						
TMD_3		.792						
TMD_4		.805						
TMD_5		.781						
TMD_6		.767						
TMD_7		.779						
TMD_8		.799						
TMR_1							.658	
TMR_2							.624	
TMR_3							.670	
TMR_4							.761	
TMR_5							.746	
TMR_6							.694	
TMR_7							.744	
TMR_8							.732	
TMR_9							.720	
TMR_10			.444			.628	.584	
TMR_11							.681	
TC_1					.737			
TC_2						.543		
TC_3					.704			
TC_4					.752			
TC_5					.771			
TC_6					.802			
TC_7					.772			

TC_8		.747	
UIRP_1			.783
UIRP_2			.866
UIRP_3			.855
UIRP_4			.855
UIRP_5			.821
UIRP_6			.799
DHIP_1	.849		
DHIP_2	.848		
DHIP_3	.675		.563
DHIP_4	.841		
DHIP_5	.849		
DHIP_6	.876		
DHIP_7	.835		
DHIP_8	.819		
HIR_1	.765		
HIR_2	.786		
HIR_3	.888		
HIR_4	.873		
HIR_5	.851		
HIR_6	.873		
HIR_7	.863		
TBP_1		.706	
TBP_2		.739	
TBP_3		.743	
TBP_4		.786	
TBP_5		.804	
TBP_6		.704	
TBP_7		.670	
TBP_8		.726	
TBP_9		.693	

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

APPENDIX 4.7: The constructs' reliability measures (pilot study)

Constructs	Cronbach's alpha	Items	Correlated item – total correlation	Mean	SD	EFA Final loading	Removed items
TNE market information generation (9)							
		TMG_1	.761	5.71	1.234	.723	
		TMG_2	.822	5.51	1.314	.757	
		TMG_3	.817	5.35	1.304	.790	
		TMG_4	.849	5.59	1.145	.795	
		TMG_5	.802	5.35	1.304	.792	
		TMG_6	.857	5.49	1.329	.810	
		TMG_7	.879	5.35	1.288	.828	
		TMG_8	.791	5.71	1.250	.819	
		TMG_9	.811	5.51	1.230	.798	
TNE market orientation dissemination (8)							
		TMD_1	.753	5.87	.968	.795	
		TMD_2	.810	5.85	1.058	.784	
		TMD_3	.780	5.79	1.076	.813	
		TMD_4	.852	5.93	.987	.826	
		TMD_5	.845	5.81	1.011	.802	
		TMD_6	.808	5.81	1.070	.788	
		TMD_7	.766	5.93	1.008	.800	
		TMD_8	.796	5.94	.996	.820	
TNE market orientation responsiveness (10)							
		TMR_1	.719	5.63	.972	.685	TMR10
		TMR_2	.724	5.65	.959	.651	
		TMR_3	.670	5.62	.967	.697	
		TMR_4	.728	5.90	.974	.788	
		TMR_5	.792	5.82	.941	.773	
		TMR_6	.696	5.64	.968	.721	
		TMR_7	.729	5.96	.947	.771	
		TMR_8	.745	5.90	.974	.759	

	TMR_9	.725	5.70	.995	.747	
	TMR_11	.698	5.88	.940	.708	
Elements	Transnational education coordination (7) .903					
	TC_1	.813	5.22	1.004	.771	TC2
	TC_3	.879	5.80	.969	.738	
	TC_4	.818	5.86	1.010	.787	
	TC_5	.853	5.70	1.015	.803	
	TC_6	.799	5.56	.972	.836	
	TC_7	.859	5.67	1.082	.808	
	TC_8	.808	5.11	1.069	.781	
	University international ranking position (6) .971					
	UIRP_1	.858	5.63	1.339	.817	
	UIRP_2	.849	5.79	1.299	.893	
	UIRP_3	.913	5.45	1.344	.889	
	UIRP_4	.840	5.73	1.416	.890	
	UIRP_5	.881	5.73	1.387	.853	
	UIRP_6	.894	5.73	1.372	.833	
	Developed country higher education image perception (7) .938					
	DHIP_1	.872	5.53	1.166	.879	DHIP3
	DHIP_2	.804	5.35	1.240	.875	
	DHIP_4	.909	4.63	1.773	.873	
	DHIP_5	.828	5.53	1.148	.883	
	DHIP_6	.882	5.53	1.075	.908	
DHIP_7	.866	5.35	1.190	.866		
DHIP_8	.798	5.49	1.130	.855		
Higher education international reputation (7) .940						

HIR_1	.780	5.37	1.157	.790
HIR_2	.867	4.69	1.270	.812
HIR_3	.839	4.77	1.256	.895
HIR_4	.825	4.89	1.257	.896
HIR_5	.803	4.71	1.299	.876
HIR_6	.797	4.85	1.168	.897
HIR_7	.799	5.11	1.016	.889
Transnational education business performance (9)				
	.957			
TBP_1	.767	5.19	1.258	.731
TBP_2	.803	5.18	1.346	.765
TBP_3	.807	4.99	1.238	.770
TBP_4	.874	4.65	1.510	.809
TBP_5	.854	5.17	1.209	.829
TBP_6	.815	4.63	1.498	.728
TBP_7	.865	4.81	1.566	.704
TBP_8	.793	4.97	1.385	.754
TBP_9	.767	5.69	1.187	.720

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

APPENDIX 6.1: Missing data examination at items-level

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Missing	
				High	Count
TMG_1	336	5.36	1.617	0	.0
TMG_2	336	5.38	1.625	0	.0
TMG_3	336	5.40	1.593	0	.0
TMG_4	336	5.54	1.626	0	.0
TMG_5	336	5.38	1.579	0	.0
TMG_6	336	5.51	1.668	0	.0
TMG_7	336	5.35	1.510	0	.0
TMG_8	336	5.42	1.541	0	.0
TMG_9	336	5.36	1.607	0	.0
TMD_1	336	5.41	1.674	0	.0
TMD_2	336	5.49	1.623	0	.0
TMD_3	336	5.53	1.666	0	.0
TMD_4	336	5.43	1.634	0	.0
TMD_5	336	5.52	1.700	0	.0
TMD_6	336	5.50	1.595	0	.0
TMD_7	336	5.49	1.655	0	.0
TMD_8	336	5.54	1.675	0	.0
TMR_1	336	5.51	1.484	0	.0
TMR_2	336	5.52	1.537	0	.0
TMR_3	336	5.41	1.637	0	.0
TMR_4	336	5.55	1.558	0	.0
TMR_5	336	5.44	1.588	0	.0
TMR_6	336	5.50	1.540	0	.0
TMR_7	336	5.47	1.516	0	.0
TMR_8	336	5.49	1.568	0	.0
TMR_9	336	5.60	1.483	0	.0
TMR_11	336	5.52	1.532	0	.0
TC_1	336	5.50	1.397	0	.0
TC_3	336	5.50	1.565	0	.0
TC_4	336	5.50	1.429	0	.0
TC_5	336	5.50	1.462	0	.0
TC_6	336	5.46	1.482	0	.0
TC_7	336	5.60	1.540	0	.0

TC_8	336	5.52	1.378	0	.0
UIRP_1	336	5.49	1.472	0	.0
UIRP_2	336	5.44	1.436	0	.0
UIRP_3	336	5.59	1.488	0	.0
UIRP_4	336	5.60	1.487	0	.0
UIRP_5	336	5.51	1.466	0	.0
UIRP_6	336	5.54	1.492	0	.0
DHIP_1	336	5.33	1.600	0	.0
DHIP_2	336	5.48	1.498	0	.0
DHIP_4	336	5.46	1.543	0	.0
DHIP_5	336	5.44	1.605	0	.0
DHIP_6	336	5.44	1.544	0	.0
DHIP_7	336	5.59	1.550	0	.0
DHIP_8	336	5.46	1.502	0	.0
HIR_1	336	5.38	1.513	0	.0
HIR_2	336	5.35	1.518	0	.0
HIR_3	336	5.52	1.559	0	.0
HIR_4	336	5.51	1.486	0	.0
HIR_5	336	5.63	1.554	0	.0
HIR_6	336	4.43	1.538	0	.0
HIR_7	336	5.51	1.551	0	.0
TBP_1	336	4.38	1.598	0	.0
TBP_2	336	5.45	1.539	0	.0
TBP_3	336	5.45	1.647	0	.0
TBP_4	336	5.41	1.691	0	.0
TBP_5	336	5.43	1.542	0	.0
TBP_6	336	5.57	1.513	0	.0
TBP_7	336	5.45	1.570	0	.0
TBP_8	336	5.37	1.528	0	.0
TBP_9	336	5.43	1.548	0	.0
UL	336	6.05	3.810	0	.0
TNEM	336	35.7	24.568	0	.0
BTNE	336	3.62	1.301	0	.0
TNEP	336	7.01	2.763	0	.0
IRP	336	3.02	1.143	0	.0
IRPMP	336	1.11	0.317	0	.0

PD	336	3.04	2.197	0	.0
PP	336	5.31	4.059	0	.0
PE	336	2.42	0.627	0	.0
UA	336	2.08	1.079	0	.0
UXTNE	336	2.32	0.805	0	.0

APPENDIX 6.2: Normal Probability Q-Q plots

APPENDIX 6.3: Univariate variables

Tests of Normality

	Std. Deviation			Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Mean	n	Missing	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
TMG_1	5.36	1.617	.0	.259	336	.000	.824	336	.000
TMG_2	5.38	1.625	.0	.260	336	.000	.811	336	.000
TMG_3	5.23	1.593	.0	.243	336	.000	.831	336	.000
TMG_4	5.53	1.625	.0	.222	336	.000	.804	336	.000
TMG_5	5.37	1.578	.0	.248	336	.000	.831	336	.000
TMG_6	5.50	1.667	.0	.222	336	.000	.804	336	.000
TMG_7	5.34	1.667	.0	.251	336	.000	.847	336	.000
TMG_8	5.42	1.541	.0	.246	336	.000	.830	336	.000
TMG_9	5.35	1.607	.0	.260	336	.000	.825	336	.000
TMD_1	5.41	1.674	.0	.251	336	.000	.810	336	.000
TMD_2	5.48	1.622	.0	.236	336	.000	.811	336	.000
TMD_3	5.53	1.665	.0	.226	336	.000	.797	336	.000
TMD_4	5.43	1.633	.0	.256	336	.000	.806	336	.000
TMD_5	5.51	1.699	.0	.223	336	.000	.796	336	.000
TMD_6	5.50	1.594	.0	.224	336	.000	.818	336	.000
TMD_7	5.48	1.655	.0	.236	336	.000	.805	336	.000
TMD_8	5.53	1.674	.0	.216	336	.000	.796	336	.000
TMR_1	5.51	1.484	.0	.233	336	.000	.823	336	.000
TMR_2	5.52	1.537	.0	.233	336	.000	.816	336	.000
TMR_3	5.41	1.637	.0	.269	336	.000	.799	336	.000
TMR_4	5.55	1.558	.0	.228	336	.000	.810	336	.000
TMR_5	5.44	1.588	.0	.261	336	.000	.807	336	.000
TMR_6	5.50	1.540	.0	.239	336	.000	.817	336	.000
TMR_7	5.47	1.516	.0	.248	336	.000	.823	336	.000
TMR_8	5.49	1.568	.0	.248	336	.000	.811	336	.000
TMR_9	5.60	1.483	.0	.213	336	.000	.819	336	.000
TMR_1	5.52	1.532	.0	.236	336	.000	.816	336	.000
1			.0						
TC_1	5.49	1.397	.0	.236	336	.000	.837	336	.000
TC_3	5.50	1.564	.0	.253	336	.000	.797	336	.000
TC_4	5.5	1.428	.0	.241	336	.000	.831	336	.000

TC_5	5.49	1.461	.0	.242	336	.000	.823	336	.000
TC_6	5.46	1.481	.0	.255	336	.000	.820	336	.000
TC_7	5.59	1.540	.0	.228	336	.000	.797	336	.000
TC_8	5.52	1.377	.0	.228	336	.000	.843	336	.000
UIRP_1	5.48	1.472	.0	.239	336	.000	.830	336	.000
UIRP_2	5.44	1.436	.0	.245	336	.000	.841	336	.000
UIRP_3	5.58	1.480	.0	.219	336	.000	.812	336	.000
UIRP_4	5.60	1.486	.0	.215	336	.000	.816	336	.000
UIRP_5	5.50	1.466	.0	.233	336	.000	.829	336	.000
UIRP_6	5.54	1.491	.0	.230	336	.000	.816	336	.000
DHIP_1	5.32	1.600	.0	.267	336	.000	.827	336	.000
DHIP_2	5.482	1.498	.0	.222	336	.000	.838	336	.000
DHIP_4	5.464	1.542	.0	.233	336	.000	.829	336	.000
DHIP_5	5.44	1.604	.0	.239	336	.000	.821	336	.000
DHIP_6	5.44	1.544	.0	.238	336	.000	.832	336	.000
DHIP_7	5.59	1.550	.0	.202	336	.000	.814	336	.000
DHIP_8	5.45	1.501	.0	.229	336	.000	.827	336	.000
HIR_1	5.37	1.512	.0	.253	336	.000	.841	336	.000
HIR_2	5.34	1.518	.0	.263	336	.000	.835	336	.000
HIR_3	5.52	1.558	.0	.223	336	.000	.816	336	.000
HIR_4	5.50	1.486	.0	.234	336	.000	.826	336	.000
HIR_5	5.62	1.553	.0	.226	336	.000	.801	336	.000
HIR_6	5.42	1.537	.0	.242	336	.000	.832	336	.000
HIR_7	5.50	1.551	.0	.226	336	.000	.822	336	.000
TBP_1	5.37	1.597	.0	.261	336	.000	.823	336	.000
TBP_2	5.44	1.538	.0	.239	336	.000	.831	336	.000
TBP_3	5.44	1.647	.0	.244	336	.000	.811	336	.000
TBP_4	5.41	1.690	.0	.255	336	.000	.802	336	.000
TBP_5	5.42	1.541	.0	.245	336	.000	.827	336	.000
TBP_6	5.56	1.512	.0	.211	336	.000	.822	336	.000
TBP_7	5.45	1.569	.0	.238	336	.000	.827	336	.000
TBP_8	5.36	1.528	.0	.259	336	.000	.832	336	.000
TBP_9	5.42	1.547	.0	.242	336	.000	.832	336	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

APPENDIX 6.4: Multivariate normality

Items	Mean	SD	Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
TNE Market information						
Generation						
TMG_1	5.36	1.617	-1.118	.133	.719	.265
TMG_2	5.38	1.625	-1.25	.133	.917	.265
TMG_3	5.23	1.593	-1.064	.133	.647	.265
TMG_4	5.53	1.625	-1.261	.133	.948	.265
TMG_5	5.37	1.578	-1.157	.133	.867	.265
TMG_6	5.50	1.667	-1.239	.133	.818	.265
TMG_7	5.34	1.667	-.920	.133	.426	.265
TMG_8	5.42	1.541	-1.160	.133	.937	.265
TMG_9	5.35	1.607	-1.055	.133	.591	.265
TNE Market information						
Dissemination						
TMD_1	5.41	1.674	-1.154	.133	.707	.265
TMD_2	5.48	1.622	-1.170	.133	.800	.265
TMD_3	5.53	1.665	-1.209	.133	.761	.265
TMD_4	5.43	1.633	-1.116	.133	.696	.265
TMD_5	5.51	1.699	-1.249	.133	.808	.265
TMD_6	5.50	1.594	-1.120	.133	.712	.265
TMD_7	5.48	1.655	-1.175	.133	.764	.265
TMD_8	5.53	1.674	-1.284	.133	.929	.265
TNE Market information						
Responsiveness						
TMR_1	5.51	1.484	-0.924	.133	.46	.265
TMR_2	5.52	1.537	-1.081	.133	.742	.265
TMR_3	5.41	1.637	-1.169	.133	.872	.265
TMR_4	5.55	1.558	-1.198	.133	.961	.265
TMR_5	5.44	1.588	-1.152	.133	1.005	.265
TMR_6	5.50	1.540	-1.054	.133	.572	.265
TMR_7	5.47	1.516	-1.088	.133	.859	.265
TMR_8	5.49	1.568	-1.164	.133	.882	.265
TMR_9	5.60	1.483	-1.059	.133	.647	.265

TMR_11	5.52	1.532	-1.125	.133	.771	.265
TNE Coordination						
TC_1	5.49	1.397	-.876	.133	.491	.265
TC_3	5.50	1.564	-1.374	.133	1.557	.265
TC_4	5.5	1.428	-1.075	.133	.898	.265
TC_5	5.49	1.461	-.963	.133	.649	.265
TC_6	5.46	1.481	-1.076	.133	.855	.265
TC_7	5.59	1.540	-1.371	.133	1.57	.265
TC_8	5.52	1.377	-.953	.133	.641	.265
University International						
Ranking Position						
UIRP_1	5.48	1.472	-1.154	.133	1.047	.265
UIRP_2	5.44	1.436	-1.011	.133	.715	.265
UIRP_3	5.58	1.480	-1.274	.133	1.176	.265
UIRP_4	5.60	1.486	-1.207	.133	1.033	.265
UIRP_5	5.50	1.466	-1.161	.133	1.014	.265
UIRP_6	5.54	1.491	-1.289	.133	1.369	.265
Developed Country Higher						
Education Image						
Perception						
DHIP_1	5.32	1.600	-1.134	.133	.760	.265
DHIP_2	5.482	1.498	-1.021	.133	.419	.265
DHIP_4	5.464	1.542	-1.078	.133	.513	.265
DHIP_5	5.44	1.604	-1.139	.133	.619	.265
DHIP_6	5.44	1.544	-1.092	.133	.669	.265
DHIP_7	5.59	1.550	-1.117	.133	.507	.265
DHIP_8	5.45	1.501	-1.127	.133	.560	.265
Higher Education						
International Reputation						
HIR_1	5.37	1.512	-.977	.133	.594	.265
HIR_2	5.34	1.518	-1.098	.133	.782	.265
HIR_3	5.52	1.558	-1.231	.133	.930	.265
HIR_4	5.50	1.486	-1.165	.133	.696	.265
HIR_5	5.62	1.553	-1.251	.133	.819	.265
HIR_6	5.42	1.537	-1.105	.133	.679	.265
HIR_7	5.50	1.551	-1.173	.133	.794	.265

TNE Business Performance						
TBP_1	5.37	1.597	-1.12	.133	.831	.265
TBP_2	5.44	1.538	-1.005	.133	.474	.265
TBP_3	5.44	1.647	-1.166	.133	.773	.265
TBP_4	5.41	1.690	-1.245	.133	.852	.265
TBP_5	5.42	1.541	-1.008	.133	.355	.265
TBP_6	5.56	1.512	-1.099	.133	.555	.265
TBP_7	5.45	1.569	-1.079	.133	.587	.265
TBP_8	5.36	1.528	-1.007	.133	.461	.265
TBP_9	5.42	1.547	-.993	.133	.384	.265

Source: Analysis of survey data

APPENDIX 6.5: The detection of multivariate

Count	Case of outliner	Mahalanobis D2	D2/dfa	p- value	Count	Case of outliner	Mahalanobis D2	D2/dfa	p- value
1	31	55.30451	5.530451	.00000	21	242	42.59599	4.259599	.00000
2	172	52.84139	5.284139	.00000	22	325	41.75394	4.175394	.00000
3	307	51.54213	5.154213	.00000	23	301	41.64565	4.164565	.00000
4	334	51.32407	5.132407	.00000	24	202	41.64508	4.164508	.00000
5	298	48.61244	4.861244	.00000	25	196	41.59921	4.159921	.00000
6	239	48.41259	4.841259	.00000	26	304	41.52058	4.152058	.00000
7	237	48.15073	4.815073	.00000	27	249	41.30659	4.130659	.00000
8	322	47.48276	4.748276	.00000	28	252	40.23957	4.023957	.00000
9	241	47.39880	4.739880	.00000	29	178	39.48469	3.948469	.00000
10	284	46.93755	4.693755	.00000	30	236	38.74851	3.874851	.00000
11	170	46.35435	4.635435	.00000	31	229	37.98073	3.798073	.00000
12	190	46.02429	4.602429	.00000	32	230	37.88084	3.788084	.00000
13	309	45.79992	4.579992	.00000	33	217	36.83677	3.683677	.00000
14	181	45.45379	4.545379	.00000	34	282	36.81262	3.681262	.00000
15	246	45.11070	4.511070	.00000	35	227	35.38875	3.538875	.00000
16	208	45.10174	4.510174	.00000	36	199	35.06951	3.506951	.00000
17	154	45.01860	4.501860	.00000	37	205	33.77795	3.377795	.00000
18	319	44.08073	4.408073	.00000	38	36	29.34888	2.934888	.00000
19	233	43.83908	4.383908	.00000	39	24	29.15708	2.915708	.00000
20	224	43.59119	4.359119	.00000					

Source: Analysis of survey data (SPSS file)

APPENDIX 6.6: Rotated Component Matrix

	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
TMG_1	.646							
TMG_2	.638							
TMG_3	.604							
TMG_4	.649							
TMG_5	.661							
TMG_7	.635							
TMG_6	.644							
TMG_8	.640							
TMG_9	.656							
TMD_1				.659				
TMD_2				.625				
TMD_3			.304	.625				
TMD_4				.623				
TMD_5				.577				
TMD_6				.610				
TMD_7				.646				
TMD_8				.666				
TMR_1			.606					
TMR_2			.588					
TMR_3			.617					
TMR_4			.588					
TMR_5			.576					
TMR_6			.621					
TMR_7			.593					
TMR_8	.318	.301	.558					
TMR_9			.586					
TMR_11			.635					
TC_1						.653		
TC_3						.586		
TC_4						.596		

TC_5		.345				.570		
TC_6						.621		
TC_7						.627		
TC_8			.321			.552		
UIRP_1					.690			
UIRP_2					.677			
UIRP_3					.598			
UIRP_4	.325				.571			
UIRP_5					.700			
UIRP_6					.674			
DHIP_1				.307			.640	
DHIP_2							.536	
DHIP_4							.578	
DHIP_5		.323					.519	
DHIP_6	.313						.656	
DHIP_7							.579	
DHIP_8		.315					.564	
HIR_1				.319				.583
HIR_2							.315	.561
HIR_3		.357		.318				.505
HIR_4								.517
HIR_5								.562
HIR_6	.311		.303					.581
HIR_7								.591
TBP_1		.647						
TBP_2	.338	.601						
TBP_3		.623						
TBP_4		.611						
TBP_5		.624						
TBP_6		.604						
TBP_7		.669						
TBP_8		.593						
TBP_9		.670						